

D1.3 Annual Work Plan for the second year

WP1 Coordination

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: all partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1 WP1 - Coordination and Management

1.1 AWP objectives for month 13 to 24

The second year of the One Health EJP will be dedicated to ensuring the follow-up of the first round of selected scientific projects; the JRPs and JIPs will be supervised and monitored and a mid-term evaluation will be carried out to ensure the implementation of the projects according to the annual work plan of the first year. Also, the call for the second round of scientific projects will be launched and the corresponding scientific projects will be selected.

There will be various activities related to training and education carried out during this second period; organisation of the short-term missions, summer schools and workshops. Also, the PhD programmes selected during the first year of the project will start.

The Scientific Research Agenda (SRA) will be updated. The first Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) will be organised in Dublin from 22 until 24 May 2019 and the second ASM which will be held during the third year will be organised (bid, selection, organisation).

The One Health EJP website and social media accounts will be regularly updated and fed. The annual report for stakeholder will be prepared and disseminated.

1.2 Expected impacts

The set of activities described in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) from month 13 to 24 will contribute towards the implementation of the second of the five years of the EJP with the ongoing implementation of the scientific projects and the integrative activities.

1.2.1 WP1

In the second year the Coordination Team will ensure that the AWP Year 2 is correctly implemented. The Coordination Team will ensure the reporting, both technical and financial, of year 1 to the Research Executive Agency. The Support Team will support the organisation of PMT, PMC, SSB, POC and ESAB meetings. The website and social media will be regularly updated and the project results will be disseminated both within the consortium and to the wider public.

1.2.2 WP2

The second call for projects organized by WP3 and WP4 will be based on the SRA developed in WP2. Furthermore, OHEJP partners, international stakeholders and other EU projects will benefit from the dissemination of the OHEJP SRA. The results of this subtask will provide the basis for development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7. OHEJP Partners will benefit from the database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives, which is available to all OHEJP partners through the password-protected area of the One Health EJP website.

1.2.3 WP3

During these months the last procedures to organize the second call of projects will be finalized. This will be an important milestone to select the JRP and JIP that best comply with the SRA or, in other words, with the needs of all stakeholders. Also the first intermediate report (i.e. after 12 months of research and integrative activities) will become available. This will demonstrate how the partners have succeeded to collaborate and have been able to set up common integrative activities (pathogen collections, biobanks, data sets, protocols, ...). Finally, the first Annual Scientific Meetings will be organised in which scientific results from JRP, but also from JIP and Training & Education actions will be communicated and disseminated to the scientific community.

1.2.4 WP4

During the second year of the OHEJP, the second call for JIP proposals will be concluded. A prime objective will be to select projects that are well tailored to work towards the integrative needs of both co-funding MS as well as EU stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC, COM). The first annual report on JIP activities will be published and document how the partners have worked towards the joint integrative objectives. Two additional cogwheel workshops will contribute to the exchange with relevant One Health initiatives and projects across Europe. A first round of integrative missions will be launched, which will aid in the interaction and exchange between current JIP partners and the rest of the consortium, and specifically promote integration of partners who were not yet partners at the time of the first call. During the year it is also expected that output from the OHEJP will start becoming available and useful through the policy for open data management. Training of partners in open data management will serve to strengthen this capacity in general across the consortium.

1.2.5 WP5

The set of activities described in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) from month 13 to 24 will contribute towards the implementation of the second of the five years of the EJP with the ongoing implementation of the scientific projects and the integrative activities.

1.2.6 WP6

In Year 2, WP6 will organise the first satellite workshop and run this alongside the ASM in May 2019. WP6 will also organise a call for 10 Short Term Missions (STM), the reports from which will be made available on the One Health EJP website. Furthermore, WP6 will also organise the first CPD module in One Health.

1.2.7 WP7

After one year of activity there will be better knowledge of the EJP capacity and of the different sustainability opportunities. The stakeholders' needs will help us to find scenarios of sustainability. Also, the definition of the SRA will be framed in relation with the relevant stakeholders to ensure a sustainable EJP.

1.3 Correspondence with the description of work – Annex 1

The following actions are foreseen in the second year:

- 1.3.1 WP1 work will be dedicated to the reporting activities as well the preparation of the SPR for year 2 and the AWP for year 3. Organisation support for the Annual meetings of the governance bodies as well as the Annual Scientific Meeting will be provided.
- 1.3.2 WP2 activities will be undertaken to disseminate the SRA among OHEJP partners, stakeholders and other EU projects. Furthermore, relevant scientific developments will be monitored, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations. The database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be updated three times a year.
- 1.3.3 Within WP3 two guidelines have to be finalized: one on the evaluation of project proposals and the selection of the projects (Del 3.6), and the guidelines on the evaluation of the final

project reports (Del 3.9). The ongoing JRP will continue to be monitored (9 and 12 month reports). The second call of JRP (and JIP) will further be prepared as well. In addition, the first Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM, in Dublin) will take place and the abstract book of the first ASM will be submitted (Del 3.8) report will be drafted. The bid for the second ASM will be sent out.

- 1.3.4 During Y2, WP4 will implement the 2nd call for JIP's jointly with WP3, and prepare documents for project selection by the SSB. The supervision of the two JIP's ORION and COHESIVE will continue and preparations for their final evaluation will be initiated. Furthermore, WP4 will facilitate internal integration with JIPs through granting exchange visits and twinning activities, and arrange cogwheel workshops to align with related European initiatives. The OHEJP data management plan will be updated and continuous support for its implementation will be provided.
- 1.3.5 During the second year, the actions foreseen in WP5 include consolidation of communication links with stakeholders, regular update of research needs of stakeholders and closure of knowledge gaps and research needs of international stakeholders.
- 1.3.6 WP6 will organise the first satellite workshop and run this alongside the ASM in May 2019. WP6 will also organise a call for 10 Short Term Missions (STM), the reports from which will be made available on the One Health EJP website. Furthermore, WP6 will also organise the first CPD module in One Health.
- 1.3.7 The main activities of WP7 will include mapping the relevant stakeholders at national, European and international level in agreement with WP5. Results of WP5 tasks 5.1 will be considered and complemented. There will be a survey drafted in order to collect the stakeholders needs regarding the EJP. WP7 team will work on a method to identify and to share appropriate calls for funding in the scope of the EJP. Horizon Europe negotiations will be monitored. Also with regard to the relevance for the sustainability, there will be an evaluation of the activities of the first year and a revision of the SRA in cooperation with WP2.

2 Annual Work Plan Activities

2.1 Annual Work Plan

2.1.1 Structure of the Annual Work plan

The 2nd Annual Work Plan (AWP Y2) of the One Health EJP will start by implementation of the PhD programme. The second call of the PhD programme will be launched. The One Health EJP will develop its prioritization strategy for the subsequent years. Also, the new set of Joint Research and Joint Integrative Projects will start.

2.1.2 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

				GANTT CHART											
WP	Task	Subtask	Title	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
WP1	1.1		Management of EC contractual obligations									1.6			
	1.2		Project management	PMT	SSB		PMT		PMT		SSB	PMPCOC			
	1.3		Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings												
	1.4		Communication tools												
	1.4.0		Communication groups												
	1.4.1		Web site/interface												
	1.4.2		Internal communications		1.4										
	1.4.3		External communications: Press releases												
	1.4.4		External communications: Professional social networks												
	1.4.5		Special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal												
1.4.6		External communications: Merchandise and branding													
1.4.7		Annual and final report		1.5											
WP2	2.1	2.1.1	Identification and updating of priority research and integrative topics												
	2.1	2.1.2	Development and updating of the strategic research agenda												
	2.2	2.2.1	Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives												
WP3	3.1		Guidelines for project coordinators to report + request extension (JRP&JIP)												
	3.1		Updated guidelines for Submission and selection of project proposals (JRP&JIP)												
	3.1		Guidelines for WP3/WP4 to monitor projects (JRP&JIP) (at start, periodic and end-												
	3.1		Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects (JRP&JIP)	3.6											
	3.1		Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports						3.9						
	3.2	3.2.2	Follow up of recently started projects												
	3.2	3.2.3	Monitoring: mid- and end-term reports		3.7										
	3.2	3.2.4	Evaluation of JRP reports by external experts: final report												
	3.3		Second call for projects: Evaluation of full proposals								3.10				
	3.4	3.4.1	Protocol for Annual Scientific Meeting organisation												
WP4	4.1	4.1.1	Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals												
	4.1	4.1.2	Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of, JIP progress						4.12						
	4.1	4.1.3	Guidelines for final evaluation of JIPs												
	4.2	4.2.1	Start-up support												
	4.2	4.2.2	Project monitoring	4.10											
	4.2	4.2.3	Final evaluations												
	4.3	4.3.1	Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level				4.11					4.14			
	4.3	4.3.2	Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs												
	4.3	4.3.3	Scientific meetings to enhance integration												4.15
	4.4	4.4.1	Call for letters of intent												
WPS	5.1	5.1.1	Communication links with international stakeholders												
	5.1	5.1.2	Communication links with national stakeholders												
	5.2	5.2.1	Platform for interaction												
	5.2	5.2.2	Systematic screening												
	5.2	5.2.3	Consolidation of results												
	5.3	5.3.1	Capacity map												
	5.3	5.3.2	Scientific support to enhance exploitation of results												
	5.4	5.4.1	Dissemination strategy												
	5.4	5.4.2	Targeted communication												5.7
	5.4	5.4.3	Stakeholder conference												
WPe	6.1		Short term missions												6.7
	6.2		Workshop programme												6.4
	6.3		One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates												6.5
	6.4		Doctoral training programme												
	6.5		One-Health CPD Module												6.6
	6.6		Communications workshop and media training												6.3
WP7	7.1		Collection of end user Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations.												
	7.2		Definition of the One Health SRIA 2021-2030												
	7.3		Development of governance model and related financial plan												
	7.4		Definiton of the road map for institutionalisation of One Health across the EJP												

2.1.3 Detailed work description

2.1.3.1 Annual work plan activities

2.1.3.1.1 WP1-Coordination and Management

Set of activity	WP1-Coordination and Management						Lead Beneficiary			P01-Anses	
							Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P04-Sciensano	
Start month	M13						End month			Month 24	
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M	35		6								
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M											
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI	
P.M											
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M											
Objectives											
T1.1: To carry out the EC contractual obligations regarding legal, financial and administrative management and coordination of the EJP.											
T1.2: To ensure efficient project management											
T1.3: To organize EJP management meetings of all the governance and management bodies of the EJP:											
T1.4: To set up and put in place and manage efficient communication tools											
T1.5: To manage ethical review											

Description of programmed activities

T1.1: The Coordination team will supervise the preparation and submission of the deliverables due from M13 to M24 to the European Commission (EC). At the beginning of the period the CT will carry out the annual technical and financial reporting. Also, the CT will coordinate the preparation, compilation and submission to the EC of the Summary Progress Report (SPR) for year 2 and the Annual Work Plan (AWP) for Year 3.

T1.2: The Coordination team members will exchange on a weekly basis via teleconferences to ensure that administrative, financial and contractual requirements are met. The Coordination team and the PMT will have monthly teleconference to ensure a smooth management and coordination of the WP activities. The CT will regularly liaise with the REA project officers and report any issue that may arise. The manual of procedures and the corresponding templates will be updated whenever relevant.

T1.3: The Support Team (ST) will ensure the organisation of all the project governance bodies meetings in regards to the identified planning. There will be 2 SSB, 3 PMT, 1 POC and 1 PMC meetings organised.

T1.4: The website and social media accounts will be regularly updated and fed according to the One Health EJP internal communication guidelines. Internal and external newsletters will be produced and compiled within an annual report. Also the annual report of first year will be adapted to the wider public and will be disseminated to the stakeholders.

T1.5: In year 2 the project leaders will indicate for the first time how they have complied with the recommendations drafted by the Ethics Advisors at the launch of the research and integrative projects. Based on these ethics reports plus the 12-months scientific reports, the Ethics Advisors will be able to evaluate all ethics aspects.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D1.4	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the first year	M13
D1.5	Complete version of annual report for stakeholders	M13
D1.6	Summary progress report year 2	M21
D1.7	Annual work plan for the third year	M21

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS3	SSB Meeting n°2	M14
MS4	SSB Meeting n°3	M20
MS13	PMC/POC/ESAB & SC Annual meeting n°2	M21

2.1.3.1.2 WP2-Strategic Research Agenda

Set of Activity	WP2–Strategic Research Agenda										Lead Beneficiary	P30-RIVM
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary	P17-UCM
Start month	Month 13						End month			Month 24		
Partici pant	1 Anses	2 Ages	4 Sciensan o	6 NDRVMI	7 SZU	8 VRI	9 BfR	10 FLI	11 RKI	12 DTU		
P.M	0.19		0.13				0.13				0.19	
Partici pant	13 SSI	14 UT	15 VFL	16 INIA	17 UCM	18 MVNA	19 INRA	20 IP	21 APHA	22 PHE		
P.M					2.44							
Partici pant	23 UoS	24 OKI	25 NUIG	26 TEAGASC	27 ISS	28 IZSAM	29 IZSLER	30 RIVM	31 WbVR	32 FHI		
P.M	0.32				0.32			2.25			0.19	
Partici pant	33 NVI	34 PIWET	35 INI/AV	36 INSA	37 IISPV	38 IC	39 SLV	40 FOHMI	41 SVA			
P.M	0.19	0.19								0.26		
Objectives												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To monitor relevant scientific developments, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations To regularly update the web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives 												

Description of programmed activities

Task 2.1: Development of the SRA

Task Leader: RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: UCM

Participants: all partner organisations

The SRA developed in year 1 will provide the basis for development of joint research and integrative projects in the second round of the OHEJP. Activities will also be undertaken to disseminate the SRA among OHEJP partners, stakeholders and other EU projects. Furthermore, relevant scientific developments will be monitored, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations. The results of this subtask will provide the basis for development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7.

Task 2.2: Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

Task Leader: UCM

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Participants: Anses, CODA-CERVA, BfR, SVA

The database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives, which is available to all OHEJP partners through the password-protected area of the One Health EJP website, will be updated three times a year.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
	n/a	

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
	n/a	

2.1.3.1.3 WP3-Joint Research Projects management

Set of Activity	WP3-Joint Research Projects management						Lead Beneficiary		P04-Sciensano	
							Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P31-WR	
Start month		Month 13				End month		Month 24		
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agas	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M			20.4							
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M										
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M			1	0.5					1.6	
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M										
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To draw up guidelines for the submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals To supervise the JRP in the first round of projects (KPI, deliverables, and milestones) and evaluate their outcome To organize the selection of JRP for the second round based on priorities identified in the updated strategic research agenda (WP2) To report to SSB and PMT on the external evaluations of JRP and JIP reports To organize annual scientific meetings to disseminate the results of JRP 										

Description of programmed activities**Task 3.1: Drawing up of guidelines for submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals as well as request of extension of accepted JRPs. Task with input from WP4 (Joint Integrative Projects) and with WP6 (Education and Training)**

The updating of the guidelines for evaluation of JRP proposals and selection of the projects starts in the autumn of 2018 and will be based on the existing procedure that was drafted in 2016. This procedure will be delivered in Y2 (2019, Deliverable 3.6) Also the procedure for the evaluation of the final reports (Deliverable 3.9), which is needed in Y3, will be finalised in Y2.

Task 3.2: Supervision of the JRP in the first round of projects**Subtask 3.2.1 Periodic follow up of activities in the JRP consortia**

As in Y1, WP3 L and DL want to have a close formal and informal contact with project leaders. For instance, they may want to participate in videoconferences or consortium meetings towards the end of the project. This subtask will help in creating constructive collaborations among partners and thus facilitate integration.

Subtask 3.2.2 Follow-up of recently started projects

N/A (This is a task in Y1 and Y3.)

Subtask 3.2.3: Mid- and end-term evaluations

Project leaders are requested to submit reports at 9 and 12 month of Y2, following templates that are available. The 9 month reports (of JRP that started in Y1 and Y2) will serve as an input for a large portion of the WP3 part of the EJP Summary Progress Report of Y2. Similarly, the consolidated 12 month reports of projects that started in Y1 will be used to feed into the annual EJP report of Y2. However, this 12 month reports will also help to draft the WP3 and the Ethics reports of Y2. These reports will consequently be discussed in the SSB and validated by the Programme Managers Committee in the autumn of Y2.

Project leaders may want to submit a request to extent their project in time (max 6 month), without additional budget.

Subtask 3.2.4: End-term evaluations of the final JRP reports by external experts

N/A (In Y2 there will not be any final JRP report available).

Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision**Subtask 3.3.1 Letters of intention & full proposals**

In Y2, candidate project coordinators that have identified themselves in Y1 through the submission of a letter of intention, will be invited to submit a full proposal of their project.

Subtask 3.3.2 Evaluations of proposals by external experts; selection of JRP

Subsequently, WP3 will contact external experts for the evaluation of the full proposals, will supervise the evaluation process and will report to the PMT of the outcome. In the autumn of Y2, SBB will select the JRP for funding.

Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM) where results from JRP are presented**Subtask 3.4.2: Organisation of ASM, scientific part**

The scientific meeting in Y2 will be organised in Dublin (22 to 24 May 2019). Most of the practical issues will be arranged in Y2.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3.6	Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects (JRP&JIP)	M13
D3.7	1st periodic report on ongoing JRP	M13

D3.8	Abstract book for 1st Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)	M16
D3.9	Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports	M18
D3.10	Second call for projects: Evaluation reports of full proposals	M19
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
MS30	External experts contacted for proposal evaluation, 2nd call	M13
MS31	First Annual Scientific Meeting	M16
MS32	External experts contacted for final report evaluation (#1)	M21
MS33	Proj Coord. contacted for submission of periodic and end-term report	M23

2.1.3.1.4 WP4–Joint Integrative Projects

Set of Activity	WP4–Joint Integrative Projects										Lead Beneficiary	P41-SVA
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary	P36-INSAs
Start month	Month 13					End month				Month 24		
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	P.M	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
			1.25									
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	P.M	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	P.M	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVr	FHI		
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	P.M		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSAs	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA			
	1			3.9					9.42			

Objectives

- To prepare for the final reporting of the first round of Joint Integrative Projects.
- To follow the implementation of the two JIPs - ORION and COHESIVE.
- To support the alignment of EJP activities with two external EU initiatives/projects, and to support internal integration through the arrangement of exchange visits, twinning and thematic meetings.
- To arrange the evaluation and selection of 2nd round proposals for JIPs
- To provide support and follow the implementation of the Data Management Plan (DMP)

Description of programmed activities

Task 4.1 Development of procedures and guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals, and for reporting and evaluation.

Subtask 4.1.1 Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals : WP4 will assist in the updating of guidelines for evaluation of JRP and JIP proposals, led by WP3 and starting in the autumn

of 2018. The update will be based on the existing document from 2016. The procedure will be delivered in Y2 (2019, Deliverable 3.6).

Subtask 4.1.2 Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of JIP progress: Instructions for final reporting of Joint Integrative Projects (D4.12) will be developed in Y2 (M18, to be used in Y3). They will be based on a similar document for JRPs (WP3, D3.5), which will first be trialled in Y2. Experiences from WP3 will inform the development of D4.12.

Subtask 4.1.3 Guidelines for evaluation of JIPs: N/A (This is a task scheduled for Y3)

Task 4.2 Supervision of JIPs

Subtask 4.2.1 Start-up support: N/A (This is a task in Y1 and Y3.)

Subtask 4.2.2 Project monitoring: As in Y1, WP4 will aim to have a close formal as well as informal contact with project leaders and/or deputy leaders. Mechanisms for this is the participation in regular teleconferences and in project consortium meetings. The consolidated 12 month reports of projects that started in Y1 will be used to feed into the first periodic report on ongoing JIPs (D4.10, M13), which in turn will feed the annual OHEJP report of Y2 (M13). The 12 month report will also help to follow up the implementation of the DMP. As in Y1, project leaders are requested to submit reports at 9 and 12 month of Y2, following templates that are available. The 9 month reports will serve as an input for a large portion of the WP4 part of the EJP Summary Progress Report of Y2. These reports will consequently be discussed in the SSB and validated by the Programme Managers Committee in the autumn of Y2.

Subtask 4.2.3 Final evaluations: N/A (This is a task scheduled for Y3 and Y5)

Task 4.3 Integrative support

Subtask 4.3.1 Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level: During Y2, two more cogwheel workshops (CW) (#3 and 4) will be arranged (D4.11 and D4.14), in order to align OHEJP activities with external strategic initiatives. The target initiative for CW #3 will be identified by the end of Y1 (M10), and the target for CWs #4 and 5 will be identified in Y2 (M16 and M22).

Subtask 4.3.2 Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs: A call for integrative missions aimed at facilitating internal integration between COHESIVE and ORION partners and OHEJP partners not participating in the JIP:s will be launched by the end of Y1, based on suggestions by JIP partners. The first round of proposals will be selected by M13, and WP4 will oversee the implementation. Reporting from integrative missions will be included in the annual reports of WP4.

Subtask 4.3.3 Scientific meetings to enhance and leverage integration: WP4 will contribute to the arrangement of the 1st scientific meeting of the OHEJP, which will take place in Y2 and be organised in Dublin (22 to 24 May 2019). A thematic meeting related to the OHEJP theme Host-microbe interaction (tentatively, unless other thematic needs emerge) will be arranged, based on methodological priorities identified by relevant thematic experts within the consortium (D4.15).

Task 4.4 Organisation of call for additional JIPs for the period Y3-Y5

Subtask 4.4.1 Call for letters of intent: In Y2, candidate project coordinators that have identified themselves in Y1 through the submission of a letter of intent, will be invited to submit a full proposal of their project in M12, with the deadline in M14 (Y2). Subsequently, WP4 will assist WP3 in identifying external experts for the evaluation of the full proposals, and will supervise the evaluation process together with WP3.

Subtask 4.4.2 Prepare output from external peer review for project selection: In the autumn of Y2, WP4 will prepare documentation summarising the outcome of the external peer review of JIP proposals (D4.13). The documentation will be sent to the SBB prior to the October meeting. WP3 and 4 will present the material at the SSB meeting, where the SSB will select the JIPs and JRPs to be funded.

Task 4.5 Open data management

Subtask 4.5.1 Development of the Data Management Plan: In Y1, all JIPs and JRPs will produce the first version of their project specific data management plans (DMP). As part of the annual reporting (M12), they will also be asked to provide information about the status of implementation of the project specific DMP. This information will form the basis for the first update of the overarching DMP in Y2.

Subtask 4.5.2 Guidance and support for the implementation of the DMP: In Y2, training will be offered to ensure partners have the capacity to adhere to the OHEJP DMP. Also, the tasks related to the implementation of the DMP, listed in the action list in the overarching DMP (D4.4), will be successively executed.

Subtask 4.5.3 Open data access point: N/A (scheduled for Y1)

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D4.10	1st periodic report on ongoing JIPs	M13
D4.11	Report from 3rd cogwheel workshop	M16
D4.12	Instructions for final reporting of JIPs	M18
D4.13	Reports on evaluation of JIP proposals, 2nd call	M19
D4.14	Report from 4th cogwheel workshop	M22
D4.15	Report from thematic meeting II	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS51	External reviewers for JIP proposals recruited	M13
MS52	Draft instructions for final reporting of JIPs presented to SSB	M14
MS53	All projects from 1st call have started implementing the DMP	M17
MS54	Eight IM visits conducted	M18
MS55	Fifteen STIMs conducted	M20

2.1.3.1.5 WP5-Science to policy translation

Set of Activity	WP5-Science to policy translation						Lead Beneficiary		P09-BfR	
							Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P13-SSI	
Start month		Month 13				End month			Month 24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI
P.M							13.33			
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	JP	APHA	PHE
P.M	13									
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M										
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M										
Objectives :										
<p>T5.1: To consolidate procedures for a good information flow and interaction between the OHEJP projects and European stakeholders to support complementarity and synergy of activities and exploitation of results</p> <p>T5.2: To regularly update research and integrative needs of stakeholders identified in policy processes and the interaction with the OHEJP consortium</p> <p>T5.3: To regularly integrate available science and activities and support alignment for closure of knowledge gaps of international stakeholders</p> <p>T5.4: To foster dissemination of results from activities within the OHEJP following the targeted dissemination policy initiatives addressing the protection of consumers health</p>										
Description of programmed activities :										
<p>Task 5.1: Identification of the stakeholders and establishment of communication links</p> <p>Subtask 5.1.1 Establish communication links with EU and international stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consolidate interaction with identified contact points and broaden contact points of Key EU Stakeholders 										

- Regularly communicate with contact points of Key EU Stakeholders following the established communication procedures
- Establish communication links with international stakeholders (e.g. WHO, FAO)

Subtask 5.1.2 Establish communication links to national stakeholders

- Establish interaction with national stakeholders for drafting the capacity map and identification of potential synergies

Task 5.2: Identification of the research needs of EU stakeholders

Subtask 5.2.1 Platform for interaction

- Consolidate the technical platform for interaction with the stakeholders to ensure efficient collaboration for identification of data and knowledge gaps, needs and other requests for scientific support
- Develop procedures to support linkage of activities related to capacity map (access to available information and expertise; Task 5.3) with research and integrative needs of EU stakeholders

Subtask 5.2.2 Systematic screening

- Establish and regularly apply procedures for horizon scanning and identification of research needs
- Establish a procedure to identify potential overlap of ongoing or completed activities and needs addressed to support complementarity of activities

Subtask 5.2.3 Consolidation of results

- Discuss needs of stakeholders on the list (task 5.2.2) and potential overlap of activities with them and identify how specific issues can be addressed
- Bring forward agreed action
- Consolidate items for integration into the regularly updated Strategic Research Agenda

Task 5.3: Linking of the scientific capacity available in the EJP with the stakeholders' identified needs: closure of knowledge gaps

Subtask 5.3.1 Capacity map

- Finalise initial concept for the capacity map
- Implement a platform / platforms to display, fill, broaden and update the content of the capacity map (assisting access to available expertise and resources), including an overview on ongoing integrative activities and potential complementarity with Key EU Stakeholders
- Develop and apply indicators for research capacity and preparedness within the consortium
- Collate information on capacities and capabilities
- Compare content of capacity map with established capacities of stakeholders and identified research and integrative needs of Key EU Stakeholders
- Consolidate communication within the OHEJP to ensure timely identification of potential overlaps and synergies of OHEJP activities with activities of Key EU Stakeholders
- Develop and implement procedure to update the capacity map and to integrate information and available science
- Establish and maintain an inventory on similar activities (e.g. expert databases, capacity maps) and platforms outside the OHEJP consortium (including EU and international stakeholders)

Subtask 5.3.2: Scientific support to stakeholders

- Develop a procedure to provide scientific support to enhance exploitation of results and to contribute to their policies

Task 5.4: Dissemination of new knowledge, tools and materials

- Establish different formats for dissemination of science and integrative activities to stakeholders meeting their identified needs
- Disseminate actively new science, tools and materials to all stakeholders

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D5.7	Second annual report on dissemination activities to international stakeholders	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS69	New knowledge gaps and research needs identified n°1	M24
MS73	Scientific support provided n°1	M24

2.1.3.1.6 WP6-Training and Education

Set of Activity	WP6-Training and Education					Lead Beneficiary			P23-UoS	
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P31-WR	
Start month		Month 13				End month			Month 24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI
P.M										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	JP	APHA	PHE
P.M										
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M	14								1.5	
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M										
Objectives										
<p>To develop and deliver innovative training platforms and materials in the area of new and emerging zoonoses with a specific focus on 'one health'.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The 4 PhD grants selected to be funded in the first round will commence in 2019 • Organise the submission, selection and evaluation of PhD proposals from the second call to fund the remaining PhD grants • Organise and deliver the first One Health EJP summer school • Organise and deliver the first satellite workshop alongside the ASM • Organise and deliver the first One Health CPD module • Organise and administer 10 short term missions (STM) for EJP partners 										
Description of programmed activities										
Task 6.1: Short Term Missions										
<p>Calls for short term missions (STMs) will be managed according to the existing and successful protocol used by MVNA consortium. However, the documentation is in the process of being updated for us in the EJP. The annual call for Short Term Missions n°1 will be launched by M16 of the EJP in</p>										

alignment with MS78 at the first Annual Scientific Meeting in Ireland (confirmed 22nd – 24th May 2019). The WP6 team are currently developing the validation process for the STM applications. The specific types of missions that will be considered are as follows:

- One Health missions- Veterinary/Medical/Environmental researcher exchanges
- Skills development missions (genomics, bioinformatics, big data epidemiology)
- Researcher/policy maker/risk manager exchanges (Integrated with and complementing WP5, Science to policy translation)

Task 6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to ASM)

The first Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) has now been confirmed to take place on 22nd – 24th May 2019 in Ireland. The lead on the first ASM is Dr Geraldine Duffy at the TEGASC institute in Ireland. WP6 leader Roberto La Ragione has been in bi-weekly TC with WP3 deputy leader Hendrik-Jan Roest at WbvR. Monthly TC with Dr Geraldine Duffy will now follow to ensure that all the necessary planning is in place. Furthermore, the MVNA project manager will engage with the process to ensure documentation and learnings from the MVNA ASM’s can be utilised.

Each ASM will include a satellite workshop. The first satellite workshop will take place alongside the first ASM now confirmed to be in May 2019, and the process for selecting the priority theme for the first satellite workshop is currently being developed. Themes may include the following: New and emerging diseases, Rapid and innovative diagnostics, Harmonisation and validation of diagnostics, Antimicrobial resistance, Molecular surveillance, Digital Innovation

Task 6.3: One Health Summer School

A protocol for the call to host the summer school will be started by August 2018. An invitation to employees from partner institutes to organise a One Health Summer School will be issued to all partners by September 2018. In alignment with the G.A, applications will need to be submitted at least nine months (December 2018) before the scheduled starting date, and will be assessed by the Academic board. Notifications of successful applications will be made at least six months (Feb. 2019) prior to the course dates. The protocol for the selection of first summer school location and the theme is currently being developed. The documentation of how the week will be setup is under development. A flyer for the One Health Summer School is currently being drafted.

Task 6.4: Doctoral Training Programme

The first round of submission and selection of PhD grants has been completed. 4 PhD grants have been funded and will commence in 2019. Using the same procedure summarised in the Summary Year 1 report, a further 8 grants will be selected to be funded from the second PhD grant call. The second PhD call will be announced in September 2018.

Task 6.5: One Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

Preparation for the development of a two-week One Health CPD module is underway. The first CPD module will take place in the M24 of 2019 in alignment with D6.6. The date of the CPD module will be confirmed by early 2019. A call for participants will be issued 6 months prior to the course, and applicants will be informed at least 3 months before the module commences in alignment with the G.A. CPD has the potential to include state of the art techniques such as bioinformatics, where expertise exists within the partners.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D6.4	Report on one workshop per year associated with ASM (with WP1,3,4 and 5)	M24
D6.5	Report of the four, 4-week One health summer schools with a minimum of 12 delegates.	M24

D6.6	Two week CPD module in one health to 15 participants	M24
D6.7	Reports of the 10 short-term missions per year completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	M24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
MS78	Launching of annual call for Short Term Missions n°1	M16
MS83	Preparation and scheduling of annual training workshop programme associated with ASM n°2	M24
MS87	Preparation and launching of annual One-Health Summer Schools n°2	M24
MS91	Selection of PhD projects within the 2 first years (six to start in 2018 and another six to start in 2019)n°2	M24
MS93	Preparation of a One Health CPD module and launching of annual course n°2	M24
MS96	Preparation of a special communications workshop and media training for early career researchers - Run in 2020	M24

2.1.3.1.7 WP7-Sustainability

Set of Activity		WP7-Sustainability									Lead Beneficiary		P27-ISS
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P20-IP
Start month		Month 13					End month			Month 24			
		1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
Partici	1	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
part	2												
P.M													
Partici	13	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
part	14												
P.M									1.5				
Partici	23	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI		
part	24												
P.M						4.5							
Partici	33	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA			
part	34												
P.M										10			
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To assess drivers and constraints for institutionalization of a sustainable EJP; To identify the requirements of the stakeholders to continue the alignment and integration activities set up in the One Health EJP, also after the EJP will be finished; To explore the available options (instruments, resources) to preserve the project's achievements To ensure that the EJP main scientific outputs, protocols, databases, and other strategic integration activities will be sustainable beyond the lifetime of the project 													
<p>Description of programmed activities</p> <p>Task 7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations. Task leader: BFR / Participants: ISS, ANSES, RIVM, IP Once the stakeholders are mapped, their needs and expectations of a sustainable EJP will be explored via questionnaires or face to face meetings with them. The data collected will be analysed and benchmarked. This analysis will trigger the reflection on the different ways to make the EJP sustainable. This task will be conducted in close cooperation with WP5 tasks 5.1 and 5.2, and WP2 task 2.2.</p>													

Task 7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030 (SRIA 2021-2030).

Task leader: ISS / Participants: RIVM, ANSES, BfR, IP, CODA-CERVA, SVA UCM.

WP2 has produced an updated SRA, that will be complemented with the information from task 7.1. As a main focus, the EJP SRA agenda will be evaluated to consider its relevance in the mid- long term period and its alignment with the next EU and international calls (in particular FP9).

Task 7.3: Making the EJP sustainable through other funding and/or legal basis

Task leader: IP / Participants: all beneficiaries

The EJP mission and objectives will be evaluated considering the next EU and international calls, to attract other funding thanks to the EJP’s leverage effect. In particular, FP9 missions and other types of calls will be analysed and the common objectives will be described, to promote the EJP structure and governance continuity beyond H2020.

Task 7.4: Making the bridges between EJP’s beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable

Task Leader: SVA / Participants: all beneficiaries

A draft method to conduct an EU-wide analysis of currently established and implemented work processes and shared infrastructures across the animal health-public health interface, with identification of legal, financial, cultural and political barriers and drivers for their long-term maintenance will be produced, taking into account main reference documents and guidelines. This work will be conducted partly in the form of a PhD project in collaboration with Roskilde university, Department of Social Sciences and Business.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
	n/a	

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
	n/a	

2.1.3.1.8 JRP1-IMPART

Set of activity		JRP1/R1/AMR-1 Phenotypic methods								
Project title		Improving phenotypic testing of AMR by development of sensitive screening assays for emerging resistances and setting missing ECOFFs								
Project acronym		IMPART								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P31-WbVR			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P01-Anses		
Project Coordinator person name		Kees Veldman			Project Deputy Leader person name			Sophie Granier		
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month				M1			Project End month		M24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	8.24						7			3
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M	2.5								7.51	3.13
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
P.M								2.4	17.5	
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M	5.75	14.25								
<p>Objectives</p> <p><u>Work package 1:</u> Develop, improve and validate common methods to isolate, characterize and confirm resistance to colistin in relevant Gram negative bacteria.</p> <p><u>Work package 2:</u></p>										

To develop a sensitive and validated culturing method for the detection of relevant carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) in meat samples and caecal samples from animals.

Work package 3:

Development of epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) of antimicrobials for veterinary pathogens.

Work package 4:

To develop and standardize a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile* followed by testing of a large collection of *C. difficile* isolates resulting in inhibition zone diameter distributions of a relevant set of antimicrobials.

Work package 5:

To coordinate the four work packages and the knowledge dissemination within and beyond IMPART.

Description of work

WP1: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae

WP1 start month: M1

WP1 end month: M24

WP1 Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy WP1 Leader: (junior scientist to be hired at 1, Anses)

WP1 participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbVR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the WP:

Work package 1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The first description of a transferable colistin resistance mechanism (Liu *et al* 2015), urged antimicrobial resistance laboratories world-wide to quickly implement methods to confirm or reject the presence of transferable colistin resistance genes. Since then, variants of *mcr-1* and *mcr-2* genes have been described without enough knowledge of their epidemiological relevance. Due to the public health concerns about resistance to a last resort antimicrobial to treat life threatening human infections, each laboratory empirically set their own methods relying on recent literature.

The time has come to share, compare and evaluate, to “IMPART”, our experience and knowledge in order to evaluate and standardize methodologies to:

- Selectively isolate colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae
- Phenotypically characterize colistin resistance
- Confirm the presence of transferable colistin resistance mechanisms

IMPART-WP1 will ensure that all participants will implement the same harmonized method for detection and characterization of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae.

At the end of IMPART, the participants will have raised their expertise on colistin resistance identification in general. IMPART will raise us all to the same level in order to create a network of laboratories throughout Europe able to monitor this potential threat to public health, using similar harmonized methodologies.

Task 1.4: Preparation of samples for the final ring trial (WP1 and WP2)

Task start month: M12

Task end month: M17

Task Leader: Agnès Perrin-Guyomard (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leaders: Sophie Granier (1, Anses) as WP1 leader and Jannice Schau Slettemeås (33, NVI) as WP2 leader

Task Participants: Anses (1), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T1.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. As the samples to be prepared were listed during T1.3, the caecal and meat samples will be collected and the absence of the relevant resistant bacteria will be assessed (SPF animal samples will be preferred if possible). After the artificial contamination of the samples, stability tests will be performed continuously until the end of the ring trial. Samples ready to be shipped will be stored and transferred to the participants in frozen condition.

Task 1.5: Performing the final ring trial

Task start month: M17

Task end month: M17

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Jannice Schau Slettemeås (33, NVI) as WP2 leader

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T1.5 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. The final ring trial will be a joint ring trial for WP1 and WP2 as their objectives are very similar. To be cost effective, the joint ring trial will be composed of a maximum of 24 samples (meat or caecal samples), in order to detect, characterize and confirm the presence of either colistin-resistant (WP1) or carbapenemase producing (WP2) Enterobacteriaceae.

This ring trial will achieve two goals: First, assess the individual capacity of each partner to identify colistin resistance or carbapenemase production, and second, to certify that the established protocols are standardized.

Task 1.6: Analysis of the results and reporting

Task start month: M18

Task end month: M19

Task Leader: Agnès Perrin-Guyomard (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leaders: Sophie Granier (1, Anses) as WP1 leader and Jannice Schau Slettemeås (33, NVI) as WP2 leader

Task Participants: Anses (1), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T1.6 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. The WP1 will generate a publication containing a science-based advice for a reliable and standardized method to isolate, detect and confirm colistin resistance in relevant Enterobacteriaceae from meat or caecal samples.

Task 1.7: Publication in peer-reviewed journal

Task start month: M20

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T1.7 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. The WP1 will generate a publication, in an open access peer-reviewed journal, containing a science-based advice for a reliable and standardized method to isolate, detect and confirm colistin resistance in relevant Enterobacteriaceae from meat or caecal samples.

Task 1.8: Plan joint implementation

Task start month: M20

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T1.8 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. After the evaluation of the ring trial, when the methodology is established, an amount of available samples will be investigated for colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae at each lab. The final stage of IMPART-WP1 will be to plan the joint implementation of the harmonized surveillance and to write proposal(s) for future projects.

WP2: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae

WP2 start month: M1

WP2 end month: M24

WP2 Leader: Jannice Schau Slettemeås (33, NVI)

Deputy WP2 Leader: Marianne Sunde (33, NVI)

WP2 participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the WP:

Work package 2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The main goal for WP2 is the development and harmonization of a sensitive culturing method to detect and characterize carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) in caecal and meat samples from animals. WP1 and WP2 are of the same character, addressing the importance of establishing the most sensitive culturing method to detect colistin-resistant and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) in both human and veterinary laboratories. WP2 fits very well to the scope of the call description regarding AMR-1: Development and harmonizing phenotypic methods sharing data and/or bacterial strains of the participating veterinary and medical institutes. IMPART-WP2 will give the best methods to:

- Selectively isolate carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae
- Phenotypically characterize carbapenemase production
- Confirm the presence of transferable carbapenem resistance mechanisms

IMPART-WP2 will gather information on methods already available, perform a ring trial between the participants in the consortium and evaluate the results to give the best available method to be

used in both monitoring programs as well as in routine diagnostic labs in human and veterinary sector.

Task 2.4: Preparation of samples for the final ring trial (WP1 and WP2)

Task start month: M12

Task end month: M17

Task Leader: Agnès Perrin-Guyomard (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leaders: Sophie Granier (1, Anses) as WP1 leader and Jannice Schau Slette-meås (33, NVI) as WP2 leader

Task Participants: Anses (1), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T2.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The samples to be prepared are listed in T2.3. The caecal and meat samples will be collected and the absence of the relevant resistant bacteria will be confirmed (SPF animal samples will be preferred if possible). After the artificial contamination of the samples, stability tests will be performed continuously until the end of the ring trial. Samples ready to be shipped will be stored and transferred to the participants in frozen condition.

Task 2.5: Performing the final ring trial

Task start month: M17

Task end month: M17

Task Leader: Jannice Schau Slette-meås (33, NVI)

Deputy Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses) as WP1 leader

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T2.5 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. The final ring trial will be a joint ring trial for WP1 and WP2 as their objectives are very similar. To be cost effective, the joint ring trial will be composed of a maximum of 24 samples (meat or caecal samples), in order to detect, characterize and confirm the presence of either colistin-resistant (WP1) or carbapenemase-producing (WP2) Enterobacteriaceae.

This ring trial will achieve two goals: First, assess the individual capacity of each partner to identify colistin resistance or carbapenemase production in Enterobacteriaceae, and second, to certify that the established protocols are standardized.

Task 2.6: Analysis of the results and reporting

Task start month: M18

Task end month: M19

Task Leader: Agnès Perrin-Guyomard (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leaders: Sophie Granier (1, Anses) as WP1 leader, Jannice Schau Slette-meås (33, NVI) as WP2 leader, Solveig Sølverød Mo (33, NVI)

Task Participants: Anses (1), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T2.6 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. The WP1 will generate a publication containing a science-based advice for a reliable and standardized method to isolate, detect and confirm carbapenemase resistance in relevant Enterobacteriaceae from meat or caecal samples.

Task 2.7: Publication in peer-reviewed journal

Task start month: M18

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Jannice Schau Slette-meås (33, NVI)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T2.7 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. WP2 will generate a publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal, containing a science-based advice for the best method to isolate and detect carbapenemase-production in relevant Enterobacteriaceae from meat and caecal samples.

Task 2.8: Plan joint implementation

Task start month: M20

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T2.8 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. After the evaluation of the ring trial, when the methodology is established, an amount of available samples will be investigated for carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae at each lab. The final stage of IMPART–WP2 will be to plan the joint implementation of the harmonized surveillance and to write proposal(s) for future projects.

WP3: Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)

WP3 start month: M1

WP3 end month: M24

WP3 Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy WP3 Leader: Els Broens (31, WbvR)

WP3 participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the WP:

Work package 3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This work package will accelerate the development of epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for veterinary pathogens and thereby support the process defining animal-specific clinical breakpoints for veterinary antimicrobials, which is essential for the prudent use of antimicrobials in animals.

WP3 is aiming to set ECOFFs for a defined list of bacterial species-antimicrobial agent combinations by collecting a sufficient number of MIC distributions from different laboratories.

Task 3.2: Production of MIC data

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M18

Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy Task Leader: Els Broens (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T3.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Based on the priority list, batches of commercially produced microtiter plates with fixed panels of relevant antimicrobials will be ordered for each group of bacteria. Microtiter plates will be distributed by the WP leader. Subsequently, participants will produce MIC data with broth microdilution according to a predefined protocol using the distributed microtiter plates.

Task 3.3: Collection and quality control of MIC data

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M18

Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy Task Leader: Els Broens (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), SSI (13), APHA (21), PHE (22), WbvR (31), RIVM (30), NVI (33), PIWET (34), SVA (41), IZSLT (Ext 1)

Description of the task:

T3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. All available MIC values will be sent in fixed (EUCAST) Excel format to the WP leader. This includes MIC data already available in the national data bases, or MIC data produced with the commercial microtiter plates. The WP leader will upload the data in the central EUCAST data base. MIC distributions submitted for potential use in the estimation of ECOFFs are reviewed against defined criteria of acceptability according to the EUCAST subcommittee on MIC distributions and ECOFFs. The WP leader will perform the quality control of the data in close cooperation with EUCAST.

Task 3.4: Analysis of the data and publication of ECOFFs

Task start month: M13

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy Task Leader: Els Broens (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: WbvR (31)

Description of the task:

T3.4 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. Data will be analysed by the WP leader under supervision of the EUCAST subcommittee on MIC distributions and ECOFFs. Finally, defined ECOFFs will become available on the EUCAST antimicrobial wild type distribution website (<http://mic.eucast.org/Eucast2/>).

WP4: Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*

WP4 start month: M4

WP4 end month: M18

WP4 Leader: Sven Maurischat (9, BfR)

Deputy WP4 Leader: Mirjam Grobbel (9, BfR)

WP4 participants: ANSES (1), BfR (9), SSI (13), APHA (21), RIVM (30), PIWET (34), SVA (41)

Description of the WP:

Work package 4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This work package will develop and standardize a disk diffusion test for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) for *C. difficile*. This will improve the AST of this pathogen using the disk diffusion method. By collecting data on inhibition zone diameter distributions of relevant antibiotics from different classes analysing at least 500 *C. difficile* isolates from different origin (human, animal, food) and different European countries, we will be able to propose inhibition zone based cut-offs and thereby distinguish between wild type and resistant strains.

Finally, the aim of WP4 is to facilitate the usage of the disk diffusion method for a broad spectrum of antimicrobials and support its application for routine diagnostic purposes as alternative to the agar dilution and commercially available gradient strips for minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) testing of *C. difficile*.

Task 4.4: Producing inhibition zone diameter distributions and proposing cut-off values for *C. difficile*

Task start month: M11

Task end month: M22

Task Leader: Sven Maurischat (9, BfR)

Deputy Task Leader: Mirjam Grobbel (9, BfR)

Task Participants: BfR (9)

Description of the task:

T4.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Using the disk diffusion method established in task 4.1, inhibition zone diameter distributions are established analysing at least 500 *C. difficile* strains from task 4.2 towards clindamycin, clarithromycin, imipenem, metronidazole, moxifloxacin, rifampicin, tetracycline and vancomycin. Based on these distributions, cut-offs will be proposed by statistical analysis. For certain antimicrobials and a subset of the strain collection, the correlation of inhibition zone diameters and MICs produced by agar dilution or Etest will be determined in parallel to verify the classification by comparing the proposed cut-off values and the published MIC-based ECOFFs. Furthermore, the WP4 leader will publish the data in an open-access peer-reviewed scientific journal.

WP5: Coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination both internally within and externally beyond the IMPART consortium

WP5 start month: M1

WP5 end month: M24

WP5 Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy WP5 Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

WP5 participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), WbvR (31), NVI (33)

Description of the WP:

Work package 5 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task: T5.1: Organization of IMPART

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Deputy Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), WbvR (31), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T5.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Under the supervision of the project coordinator, each of the four WPs will run in parallel with the common goal on improving and standardizing phenotypic methodologies to survey antimicrobial resistance in various ecosystems. Work plans will be shared and interactions between WPs will be encouraged in order to be as cost effective as possible. Work package leaders and the project coordinator constitute the coordination team of IMPART through T5.1.

T5.2: Communication within IMPART

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), WbvR (31), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T5.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. IMPART's main goal is to improve the methodologies on phenotypic characterization of antimicrobial resistance. All partners have agreed on a list of priority issues from their daily lab practice that will be addressed together. All knowledge generated by the scientific WPs will be shared on a special web-based platform with controlled access, containing meeting notes, protocols, reports and Video tutorials (using Windows Movie Maker and Camtasia). Two meetings are planned, Kick-off and Final, in between Video conferences will be organised on regular basis.

T5.3: Communication beyond IMPART

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (1, Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Kees Veldman (31, WbvR)

Task Participants: Anses (1), BfR (9), WbvR (31), NVI (33)

Description of the task:

T5.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Outputs from IMPART will be shared with the scientific community beyond MedVet EJP. The improved or developed methods, and the results of the ring trials, will be presented at international conferences

and published in open-access peer-reviewed scientific journals. IMPART will also contribute to the MedVet EJP Website, on a regular basis, following the general MedVet EJP communication strategy.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP1-1.4	Protocol for the final ring trial	M15
D-JRP1-1.5	Notifications of shipment of the samples for the final ring trial	M16
D-JRP1-1.6	Evaluation of the final ring trial	M19
D-JRP1-1.7	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M24
D-JRP1-1.8	Proposal(s) for epidemiological study to monitor resistance to colistin	M24
D-JRP1-2.4	Protocol for the final ring trial	M15
D-JRP1-2.5	Notifications of shipment of the samples for the final ring trial	M16
D-JRP1-2.6	Evaluation of the final ring trial	M19
D-JRP1-2.7	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M24
D-JRP1-2.8	Proposal(s) for epidemiological study to monitor resistance to carbapenems	M24
D-JRP1-3.3	Publication of ECOFFs on EUCAST website	M24
D-JRP1-4.1	Collection of inhibition zone diameter distributions	M19
D-JRP1-4.2	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M22
D-JRP1-5.3	IMPART News online on MedVet EJP website	M12-24
D-JRP1-5.4	Protocols and video tutorials online on IMPART EXTRANET	M18
D-JRP1-5.5	Invitation to the final meeting sent to participants	M21
D-JRP1-5.6	Final meeting notes sent to participants	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP1-7	Mid-term video meeting to validate the protocol (WP1, WP2 and WP5)	M13
M-JRP1-8	Performing final ring trial (WP1 and WP2)	M17
M-JRP1-9	MIC data collection complete (WP3)	M18
M-JRP1-10	Proposal of cut-off values based on inhibition zone diameter distributions (WP4)	M18
M-JRP1-11	Final meeting (notes of the meeting)	M24

2.1.3.1.9 JRP2-ARDIG

Set of activity		JRP2/R1/AMR-2 Epidemiology AMR										
Project title		Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment										
Project acronym		ARDIG										
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P21-APHA			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P11-RKI				
Project Coordinator person name		Muna Anjum			Project Deputy Leader person name			Tim Eckmanns				
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2					
Project Start month				M1				Project End month			M36	
Partici part	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
P.M	3.47						12		13.5			
Partici part	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22		
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
P.M					28			6	37.45	3		
Partici part	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI		
P.M	6.04								3.06			
Partici part	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41			
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA			
P.M	11											
Objectives												
Work-Package 1												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To compare AMR prevalence and AB usage in six different European regions collected through national surveillance, including EU and other surveillance programmes, from humans, animals, food and the environment. To correlate resistance trends with antibiotic sales or usage (available through research project or industry data and by collecting primary data), ecological factors and management practices To provide recommendations for improved One Health surveillance 												

Work-Package 2

- Performing longitudinal studies to determine prevalence of ESBL/*AmpC*/carbapenemase producing or *mcr-1* and *mcr-2*/PMQR-carrying Enterobacteriaceae in pig, poultry, cattle farms or hospitals and their environments
- Comparing national AMR prevalence data by considering herd/hospital level prevalence
- To set up a database integrating data from WP1 and 2 and accessible to all partner of the project

Work-Package 3

- To characterise antimicrobial resistance mechanisms in isolates of human and animal origin, and the fitness of multidrug resistant isolates in different environment.
- To understand the flux of antimicrobial resistance determinants and platforms, especially of those genes associated with antimicrobials that are used as human and animal therapeutics.

Description of work

WP1: Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

WP start month: 1 (first annual period)

WP end month: 36 (third annual period)

WP Leader: Bernd-Alois Tenhagen (9, BfR, DE)

Deputy WP Leader: Marianne Sunde (33, NVI, NO)

WP participants:

APHA (21): Pablo Alarcon

BfR (9): Bernd-Alois Tenhagen

NVI (33): Marianne Sunde

WbvR (31): Michael Brouwer

ANSES (1): Jean-Yves Madec

UCM (17): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

PHE (22): Neil Woodford

RKI (11): Tim Eckmanns

IP (20): Philippe Glaser

UoS (23): Roberto La Ragione

Description of the WP1

WP1 will continue based upon achievements of the first annual period of the EJP and will also continue during the third year of the EJP. This WP will explore and use epidemiological data available from humans, animals (pig, poultry and cattle), food (including from retail sector), and the environment, and link data (geographically) to investigate emerging trends and possible associations between AMU and AMR, and with potential risk factors beyond usage. We will have a special focus on resistance to important antimicrobial agents such as extended spectrum cephalosporins, colistin and fluoroquinolones focusing on *E. coli*. However, as much as possible, data on other bacteria (e.g. *Salmonella* spp or *Campylobacter* spp.), will also be collected to validate results across bacterial species.

It is expected that this work package will also provide data supporting the selection of relevant farms/hospitals to be included in the longitudinal study in WP2 and samples/isolates to be included in WP3

Task 1.2: Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors

Task start month: 9 (first annual period)

Task end month: 30 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Pablo Alarcon (21, APHA)

Task Participants: BfR (9), NVI (33), APHA (21), RKI (11) and PHE (22)

Description of the task

This task will be conducted during the first year of the EJP through to the 3rd year and is composed of four sub-tasks. It is based on the data collection in Task 1.1 but can already start by discussion on methodology issues before task 1.1 is finished.

Using the dataset obtained in task 1.1, a description of trends for specified AMR prevalence/frequency (primarily at the phenotypic level, and genotypic level where data is available, see WP3) at population/country/regional level will be carried out. Spatial analysis will be performed to assess and compare the coverage of the available data between countries, and investigate possible regional clusters of AMR and AMU in animals and humans. The spatial analysis done will allow for the identification of specific regions where available data will help perform in depth analysis. These will then be used to assess potential associations between AMR and AMU in livestock and humans in regional populations. The geographical regions identified will be used to investigate for risk factors for AMR beyond usage. This will consider ecological aspects like population density, urbanization, livestock density (or livestock to human relation), geographical features, but also livestock management practices (outdoor/indoor farms, farm size and distance between farms, level of integration, waste management, etc.). Existing datasets with potential risk factors that can be linked to the AMR/AMU data will be explored. Multilevel regression analyses will be performed to account for country and time (year) correlation.

WP2: Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/*mcr-1* and *-2*/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals

WP2 start month 1 (first annual period)

WP2 end month 36 (third annual period)

WP Leader: Philippe Glaser (20, IP)

Deputy WP Leader: Michael Brouwer (31, WbvR)

WP participants:

BfR (9): Bernd-Alois Tenhagen

ANSES (1): Jean-Yves Madec

UCM (17): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

IP (20): Philippe Glaser

APHA (21): Francesca Martelli

PHE (22): Neil Woodford

UoS (23): Roberto La Ragione

WbvR (31): Michael Brouwer

NVI (33): Marianne Sunde

Description of the WP2

WP2 will continue based upon achievements during the first annual period of the EJP and will also continue during the third year of the EJP. This work-package will study the persistence of ESBL/*AmpC*/carbapenemase/*mcr-1*and-2/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae at individual farm/slaughterhouse and hospital levels by collecting data on management and antibiotic usage as well as consecutive samples of faeces/meat and environmental samples through time. Furthermore, data from previous longitudinal studies that meet these criteria are present in the collection from several partners and will be included for an international comparative analysis. Retrospective and prospective collections will include samples from human, pig, poultry and cattle and related environmental isolates from all countries represented in the consortium.

Data and samples collected are expected to follow the national trends as analysed in WP1 but longitudinal samples from the same farms/hospitals and in certain cases from the same animals/patients will provide a much higher resolution of the prevalence, spread, persistence and risk factors involved for resistant Enterobacteriaceae. An estimate of 100-1000 samples will be collected and analysed per project partner, taking into account variations between study designs. Prevalence of resistance over time in specific farms/hospitals will provide information on the seasonal trends, effects of age of the subjects and individual management practices such as cleaning or disinfection, in which sampling from environmental/waste water samples will be included in farm and hospital studies, where possible. Isolates from consecutive batches of animals will be collected in a selection of pig and poultry farms to investigate if the same clone/plasmid persists at the farms or if new strains are introduced with each batch/time point. In beef and dairy farms, as well as in hospitals, where no 'all in, all out' policy is present, persistence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae within the same cohort of animals/patients overtime will be investigated by longitudinal sampling of the same animals/patients.

While all samples collected will be analysed phenotypically for ESBL/*AmpC*/carbapenem/*mcr-1*/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae, a representative number of samples will also be selected for detailed genotypic characterisation of resistance genes and associated plasmids using molecular methods and WGS, as described in WP3. For this in-depth analysis, samples will be chosen to maximise variability and to include infrequent types like CPE and *mcr-1/2* encoding isolates to address specific questions on the genetic environment of these resistance genes and on possible specificities of the corresponding lineages.

Task 2.2: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 30 (third annual period)

Task leader: Michael Brouwer (31, WbvR)

Task Participants ANSES (1), UCM (17), APHA (21), WbvR (31) and NVI (33)

Description of the task

Task 2.2 will be performed in the first, second and third year of the EJP. Longitudinal sampling will be performed at broiler, turkey or cattle farms/slaughterhouses and will be performed by all listed participants for this task. Depending on individual study design, each site will be visited 2 to >10 times. Data on management and antibiotic usage over the period of the study will be recorded and faecal/meat swabs/samples will be analysed for the presence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Phenotypic data will be recorded by established methods such as disc diffusion or broth dilution to determine the MIC of the isolates for panels of antibiotics. Methods for genotypic characterisation of the isolates, as well as plasmid composition will include genetic determination of the resistance genes via WGS, PCR, microarray, as well as other molecular methods such as PBRT, S1-PFGE, RFLP and NGS, as described in WP3. All information related to isolates on their origin, genotype and

phenotype will be stored in a common database accessible through the internet to all member of the consortium.

Task 2.3: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 30 (third annual period)

Task leader Philippe Glaser (20, IP)

Task Participants UCM (17), IP (20), PHE (22) and UoS (23)

Description of the task

Task 2.3 will be performed in the first, second and third year of the EJP. Longitudinal sampling will be performed at hospitals and/or care facilities and will be performed by all listed participants for this task. Data on patients including gender, age, disease, treatment and antibiotic treatment, as well as data on management will be recorded and faecal samples/swabs will be analysed for the presence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Phenotypic data will be recorded by established methods such as disc diffusion or broth dilution to determine the MIC of the isolates for panels of antibiotics. Methods for genotypic characterisation of the isolates, as well as plasmid composition will include genetic determination of the resistance genes via WGS, PCR, microarray, as well as other molecular methods such as PBRT, S1-PFGE, RFLP and NGS, as described in WP3. All information related to isolates on their origin, genotype and phenotype will be stored in a common database accessible through the internet to all member of the consortium.

Informed consent will be requested following national regulation and all data on patient will be anonymised.

Task 2.4: Data analysis of collected resistant Enterobacteriaceae on national levels

Task start month 22 (first annual period)

Task end month 34 (third annual period)

Task leader Francesca Martelli (21, APHA)

Task Participants ANSES (1), BfR (9), RKI (11), UCM (17), IP (20), APHA (21), PHE (22), UoS (23), WbvR (31) and NVI (33)

Description of the task

Task 2.4 will be performed over the second and third years of the EJP. The phenotypic and genotypic data on prevalence, spread and persistence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae collected in Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 will be analysed per sample source by each of the listed participants for this task. Analysis will be performed according to predetermined criteria as determined in D-2.1 by all contributors to WP2 to ensure compatibility of the results.

A risk factor analysis on relation between management of farms/hospitals and presence/persistence of resistance will be performed. Next to the relative risk and standardised incidence ratio, a regression model will be used to determine significance of the results. Persistence of resistance will be compared for conditions of between batch and within batch persistence. Phenotypic data will be complemented with the genotypic characterisation performed in WP3. Trends will be analysed in prevalence of resistance genes and associated plasmids.

WP3: AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.

WP3 start month 6 (first annual period)

WP3 end month 36 (Third annual period)

WP3 Leader Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM)
Deputy WP3 Leader: Roberto LaRagione (23, UoS)

WP3 participants:

ANSES (1): Dr Jean-Yves Madec
UCM (17): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn
IP (20): Philippe Glaser
APHA (21): Muna Anjum
PHE (22): Neil Woodford
UoS (23): Roberto La Ragione
WbvR (31): Michael Brouwer
NVI (33): Marianne Sunde
BfR (9): Jens-Andre Hammerl

Description of the WP3

To understand the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria it is essential to understand the vertical and horizontal flux of antimicrobial resistance determinants, especially of those genes associated with antimicrobials that are used as human and animal therapeutics. This is particularly important as several different genes/alleles can encode for the same antibiotic resistance, but can be from varied sources and be associated with different mobile elements.

WP3 will continue based on achievements during the first annual period of the EJP and will also continue during the third year of the EJP. In WP3, in-depth molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in a subset of isolates collected in WP1 and WP2 will be performed using WGS to add details of the mechanism of resistance present in isolates collected national and longitudinal studies. The prevalent circulating clones and/or plasmids which may be present in data sets from different compartments will be determined from the WGS data and compared between animal, human and environmental isolates from the same region and across different regions to determine their distribution. Conjugation experiments will be performed in vitro in the laboratory under standard culture conditions; in-vitro pig and poultry gut models and in-vivo animal models to determine transmission. Fitness studies performed experimentally in the laboratory both in-vitro (in culture) and in-vivo (in mice) will help determine the likely spread and persistence of dominant clones over time, which can then be compared with the on farm/hospital longitudinal data and national surveillance data gathered from different years. Such studies will not only help improve isolate characterization, which can be incorporated into future strategies, but will ultimately help in the accurate prediction of emergence and transmission of existing and novel AMR determinants across human and animal populations. It will also help understand why certain clones may be more successful than others and why some plasmids remain largely stable in their structure while others are highly variable and constantly evolving.

Task 3.1: Detailed molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in human, animal, food and environment isolates from WP1 and WP2

Task start month 6 (first annual period)

Task end month 18 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM)

Task Participants: ANSES (1), UCM (17), IP (20), APHA (21), PHE (22), UoS (23), WbvR (31), BfR (9), NVI (33)

Description of the task

Task 3.1 will be performed in the first and second year of the EJP. Detailed molecular characterisation will be performed in ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase/mcr-1-2/PMQR-harbours

Enterobacteriaceae collected from WP1 and 2 by the consortium using Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) tools such as Illumina Technology, which will be combined for some partners with microarrays, PCR, S1-nuclease pulse field gel electrophoresis (S1-PFGE) and restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP). The data will be analysed with expertise available in the consortium, particularly for WGS data, which many partners are currently involved in. The AMR genotype of ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase/mcr-1-2/PMQR-harboursing Enterobacteriaceae will be compared to determine which AMR mechanisms are currently prevalent and circulating in varied ecological niches across different geographic regions. Phylogenetic reconstruction will be applied to assess genetic relatedness of isolates, and the genetic basis of the dissemination of AMR determinants will be assessed through the identification of SNPs and gene loss and acquisition. The prevalent plasmids or Hi Risk clones will be used for further *in vitro* and *in vivo* characterization.

Task 3.2: Characterisation of prevalent circulating plasmids and their transfer *in vitro*

Task start month 10 (second annual period)

Task end month 24 (second annual period)

Task Leader: Philippe Glaser (20, IP)

Task Participants: UCM (17), IP (20), APHA (21), PHE (22), UoS (23), WbvR (31), NVI (33), ANSES (1), BfR (9)

Description of the task

Characterisation of the **prevalent circulating plasmids** from different epidemiological units at varying time points will be performed combining Illumina technology with long reads from PacBio / MinION technologies to help identify plasmid diversity and evolution as a result of adaptation to different environments/niches. Other molecular techniques such as plasmid profiling, plasmid multilocus sequence typing (pMLST), plasmid-based replicon typing (PBRT), will also be included. Conservation of plasmid genomes in different epidemiological units such as animals, foods, humans and the environment will help provide evidence of plasmid dissemination in zoonotic bacteria along the food chain. Transmission dynamics of plasmids in isolates showing the most conserved and diverse AMR profiles across different regions will be compared by performing plasmid conjugation experiments *in-vitro* using different bacterial receptor-hosts. Transfer experiments will be performed in different conditions, transfer rates assessed, and WGS used to identify plasmid changes that occur after transmission. By studying conjugation *in vitro* the impact of the elements for spreading of antimicrobial resistances will be assessed. Horizontal gene transfer will be quantified within *E. coli* and in other genera of the Enterobacteriaceae (i.e. *Salmonella*), including biofilm-producing hosts.

Task 3.3: Fitness cost of AMR and stability of plasmids in different host strain backgrounds

Task start month 18 (second annual period)

Task end month 30 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Jean Yves Madec (1, ANSES)

Task Participants: ANSES (1), UCM (17), APHA (21), PHE (22), UoS (23), WbvR (31), NVI (33), IP (20), BfR (9)

Description of the task

Fitness and survival of isolates harboring plasmids with both high and low AMR transfer rates will be compared under different conditions, to determine the contribution they make in host survival and AMR dissemination. Combination of these experiments with WGS will identify the plasmid and host chromosome factors that determine plasmid stability, spread, and adaptation to new bacterial

hosts and conditions. Bioinformatic analyses will provide an overview on the genome composition (i.e. genemaps, synteny plots) and the gene content of mobile genetic elements (transfer and mob-genes, resistances, stability factors). Studying plasmid stability and plasmid host adaptation in presence of subinhibitory concentrations of antibiotics / biocides, will determine the conditions that elicit emergence of High Risk clones or plasmids, that ultimately spread successfully between humans, animals and the environment.

WP4: Project coordination and management

WP4 start month 1 (first annual period)

WP4 end month 36 (third annual period)

WP4 Leader: Muna Anjum (21, APHA)

WP4 Participants: All

Description of the WP4

In WP4 the aim will be for the steering committee, with at least one member from each Institute, to ensure timely delivery of the Project. They will meet at least every 3 months to assess progress of the Project, whether virtually by videoconference or physically, by each partner involved in the Project. Any problems or concerns that Partners or Scientists may have will be communicated to, and discussed by, the steering committee at the earliest opportunity. A kick-off and annual meetings of consortium members will be arranged in different countries. All publications and communications concerning the Project will be approved by members of the steering committee to ensure awareness and fair representation of all facts.

Task 4.1: Steering committee quarterly meeting

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 36 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (21, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (21), BfR (9), NVI (33), WbvR (31), ANSES (1), PHE (22), RKI (11), IP (20), UoS (23), UCM (17)

Description of the task

To meet at least every 3 months, between month 1 to month 36 of the project, to assess progress of the Project by each partner involved in the Project and discuss and address possible problems, risks, technical issues, project communication and publications.

Task 4.2: Consortium members annual meeting

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 36 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (21, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (21), BfR (9), NVI (33), WbvR (31), ANSES (1), PHE (22), RKI (11), IP (20), UoS (23), UCM (17)

Description of the task

This Task will comprise of four annual meetings for the consortium partners and include a kick off meeting (Month 1); two progress meetings (Months 12 and 24); and a concluding meeting of the program (Month 36). The meetings will be organized in different countries and will include representatives from all partners.

Task 4.3: Reporting and communication

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 36 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (21, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (21), BfR (9), NVI (33), WbvR (31), ANSES (1), PHE (22), RKI (11), IP (20), UoS (23), UCM (17)

Description of the task

A summary annual communication from each WP for distribution to relevant organisations or stakeholders such as national governments, EU, international agencies and relevant industry/health partners. It is expected that members will also publish scientific papers and other communications from the results obtained in this study.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP2-1.2	Description of the specified AMR prevalence/frequency and AMU at population/country/regional level.	24
D-JRP2-1.3	A list of the regions identified for in-depth analysis, and a report including the assessments of parallel trends and estimates of potential associations between AMR and AMU.	24
D-JRP2-2.3	A project isolates database accessible to all member of the consortium	24
D-JRP2-3.1	Prevalent AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria from humans, animals, food and environment.	24
D-JRP2-3.2.	Circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24
D-JRP2-4.2	Annual communication to stakeholders	24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP2-6	Assessment of AMR prevalence/frequency and AMU at population/country/regional level.	24
M-JRP2-4	Identification of MDR isolates circulating in humans, animals, food and environment	24
M-JRP2-5	Assessment of AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria collected from humans, animals, food and environment.	18
M-JRP2-7	Identification of circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24

2.1.3.1.10 JRP3-RaDAR

Set of activity		JRP3/R1/AMR-3 Risk assessment AMR									
Project title		Risk and Disease burden of Antimicrobial Resistance									
Project acronym		RaDAR									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P30-RIVM			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)				P12-DTU		
Project Coordinator person name		Eelco Franz			Project Deputy Leader person name				Tine Hald		
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:								2			
Project Start month				M1				Project End month		M24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M	29.15						33			10	
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M									6.69		
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI	
P.M					7.5			26.49	4.2		
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M	12										
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Systematic integration of top-down epidemiological and bottom-up risk assessment information from diverse modalities to obtain best estimates for attribution, risk factors and health effects. Determining the most effective strategies for controlling transmission and to mitigate risks 											
Description of work											
WPO: Coordination and communication											
WPO takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP											
WP start month 01											

WP end month 24

WP Leader 30-RIVM

Deputy WP Leader 12-DTU

WP participants ALL

Description of the WP

This WP takes responsibility for and effective project coordination. This will be facilitated by conducting conference calls with WP leaders every 2 months. We will organize 3 consortium meetings (a M1 kick-off meeting, a M12 mid-term meeting and a M24 final meeting) to promote synchronized decision-making and development within the project as well as exchange of knowledge. This WP also makes keeps track of timely provisioning of partner's deliverables. Further, it will manage the creation of yearly project reports.

Task 0.1: Coordination and project management

Task start month 01

Task end month 024

Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: 12-DTU

Task Participants: ALL

Description of the task

A Project Management Team will be formed including the Coordinator, the deputy coordinator, and the WP leaders. Throughout the project, the group will have regular meetings (quarterly or more often, if needed) to communicate across WPs and ensure that the work flow within and between WP proceed as expected. This task will monitor the progress of the project (i.e. milestones and deliverables) as a whole by organizing regular teleconferences / Webex-meetings.

Task 0.2: Consortium meetings

Task start month 1

Task end month 24

Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: 12-DTU Task Participants: ALL

Description of the task

This tasks will organize 3 consortium meetings aimed at establishing corporation, common direction, and critical issues. These meetings will take place at M 1, 12 and 24. Minutes of meeting reports will be produced for all these 3 meetings.

Sub-Task 0.2.1: Final meeting

Sub-Task start month: 22

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: 12-DTU

Sub-Task Participants: ALL

Task 0.3: Annual reports

Task start month 01

Task end month 024

Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: 12-DTU

Task Participants: ALL

Description of the task

This tasks will produce two annual reports (for each annual period one report) summarizing the project progress as a whole.

Sub-Task 0.3.2: Second annual report

Sub-Task start month: 22

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: 12-DTU

Sub-Task Participants: ALL

WP1: New genomic information to feed AMR transmission models

WP1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month 1

WP end month 24

WP Leader Michel-Yves Mistou (Anses)

Deputy WP Leader Camilla Sekse (NVI)

WP participants Anses, NVI, DTU, RIVM, ISS

Description of the WP

Theoretically, access to the whole genomic information makes it possible to identify genetic mechanism of AMR and predict the resistance phenotype of isolates without culturing. However, the move from theory to practice requires additional biological knowledge. WP1 is about the development of new bioinformatics tool to retrieve information from genomic data relevant for modelling AMR risk and transmission. It focuses on plasmid content and mutations associated with AMR and on the impact they have on the phenotype. Genomic data in combination with phenotypic information will be linked with epidemiological data and integrated into appropriate transmission models to have full impact on public health. WP1 will collaborate closely with WP6 where new ways to combine information different by nature are developed. Extensive exchange of data with the modelling tasks of WP3 and WP5 will be promoted. In this WP, Anses will develop bioinformatics tools to analyse (meta-)genomic data and retrieve information relevant for AMR and its transmission. The other partners will be involved in biological interpretation of data and integration of the new information into transmission models.

Task 1.1 Build collections of high throughput sequencing (HTS) data needed for bioinformatics developments and knowledge advancement

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 15

Task Leader: Sophie Granier (Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Camilla Sekse (NVI) Task Participants: Anses, DTU, NVI

Sub-Task 1.1.1

WP1 addresses questions related to the exploitation of genomic data with a particular attention to plasmids. For benchmarking the new assembly pipeline (T1.2) two kind of data will be used: First,

from well annotated complete plasmid + chromosomal dataset available in public DB synthetic raw reads will be generated with dedicated program (like ART). This dataset will be used to set up and define parameters related to the different situations which could occur (e.g. number of plasmids, sizes, copy number). In a second step experimental raw reads from well-studied bacterial species with reference genomes and annotated plasmids will be gathered for pipeline validation.

Sub-Task 1.1.2

Field HTS data relevant to various AMR challenges will be collected and organised in subprojects on pilot species (e.g. Salmonella, E. coli), antimicrobials (e.g. cepheems, carbapenems, colistin and fluoroquinolones) and origins (human, animal-food sectors, environment). The field data will also include metagenomics datasets.

Examples of available WGS datasets:

- Salmonella surveillance network (2000-2016) from all food, animal and environmental sectors, a particular focus will be on colistin resistance and on the plasmidome in relation with certain serovar (*S. infantis*). (Salmonella network Anses Maisons-Alfort/Ploufragan)
- French E. coli surveillance plan in livestock focusing on colistin resistance during the last 5 years (Collection from the AMR NRL's and WGS data available at the AMR EURL-AR (DTU)

French national surveillance plan of E. coli BLSE in meat (300 strains) (2015-2016)

- QREC (quinolone resistant E. coli) from animals (poultry, pigs, cattle) in Norway
- Cephalosporin resistant E.coli (containing blaCMY-2) from poultry in Norway
- Metagenomics data of faecal, food and environmental samples

The curated collection of HTS data associated to AMR metadata will be organised in a dedicated DB accessible to partners. The DB data will be used in T1.2, T1.3 and T1.4 for testing and validating the methods.

Task 1.2 Develop an innovative automated bioinformatic pipeline integrating de novo plasmid reconstruction and generation of chromosome scaffolds

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 18

Task Leader: Nicolas Radomski (Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: Arnaud Felten (Anses) Task Participants: Anses, NVI

Sub-Task 1.2.1

An automated assembly pipeline will be developed (Python 2.7) that will incorporate a novel plasmid assembly algorithm. The accessory genome is usually not reconstructed correctly from fragmented sequencing information. The pipeline will include programs focusing on plasmid assembly (ex.: PlasmidSPAdes) which take advantage of the features of plasmid-borne DNA molecules: smaller size, circularity and copy numbers. The outputs of the pipeline will be designed for handling by microbiologists and modellers to facilitate biological interpretation (T1.3) and integration into transmission models (WP6).

Sub-Task 1.2.2

The pipeline will be tested and parameterised for analysis of metagenomics data.

Figure 1: Schematised assembly pipeline that will be developed in WP1.

Task 1.3 Plasmidome: Biological annotation and risk assessment

Task start month: 12

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: S. Granier (Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: C. Sekse (NVI)

Task Participants: Anses, NVI, DTU, RIVM, ISS

Sub-Task 1.3.1

HTS data gathered from T1.1 will be run through the in silico validated pipeline(T1.2). Outputs will be examined and curated by microbiological experts and phenotypic characteristics such as MIC values will be used for verifying the genomic findings. The knowledge will be used to predict risk factors associated to different plasmids/plasmid genes /AMR profiles and to inform the exposure assessment modelling of (WP3 T3.3), as well as the evidence-based synthesis attribution in WP5.

Task 1-4 Methods to identify genetic traits associated to AMR

Task start month: 12

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: Laurent Guillier (Anses)

Deputy Task Leader: C. Sekse (NVI)

Task Participants: Anses, NVI, DTU, RIVM, ISS

Sub-Task 1.4.1

Whole-genome association studies (WGAS to identify SNP's and Indels statistically associated to AMR traits whether plasmid-borne or not) will be performed on sets of HTS data issued of epidemiologically comparable population (with tools like Clonal Frame and linear mixed modelling).

Sub-Task 1.4.2

A second approach will be through regression model that will focus on the presence/absence of gene belonging to the accessory genomes (chromosomal and plasmid-borne, Sub- Task 1.2.2). Variations in traits important for survival (e.g. secretome, heat tolerance) and infection (virulence factors) are considered useful in WGS-based risk assessment models, where the "conventional" predictive modelling is not applicable. Genome wide association tests will be performed using a recently described statistical tool for determining the SNPs or kmer that influence bacterial phenotypes of interest (AMR resistance). Population structure and genome-wide linkage disequilibrium will be controlled with linear mixed model. The Bonferroni method will be implemented to consider multiple testing and Manhattan plots will be used to summarize results.

T1.4.3 The results of the analysis performed in Sub-Tasks 1.3.1, 1.4.1 and T1.4.2 will be used to

predict risk factors associated to different genetic markers linked to plasmids and/or AMR profile and to inform the exposure assessment modelling of WP3.3, as well as the evidence-based synthesis attribution in WP5.

WP2: Pharmacodynamics and transmission models

WP start month: 01

WP end month: 24

WP Leader Robin Simons (APHA)

Deputy WP Leader Antonios Zagaris (Wbvr)

WP participants ANSES, BfR, DTU, ISS, RIVM

Description of the WP

Resistance clone and/or gene dissemination (spread) is a multi-factorial phenomenon influenced by a variety of processes, with antimicrobial usage (AMU) in livestock production being a driving factor for antimicrobial resistance selection. The relative importance and dependence of these processes on e.g. production practices, national policies and consumption patterns is unknown. Additionally, transmission between distinct animal/human populations, underpinned by these processes, remains poorly quantified. All of this hinders effective control, with WP2 responding to this call to action.

Task 2.1: On-farm transmission models

Task start month: 01

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: Robin Simons

Deputy Task Leader: Pascal Sanders

Task Participants: APHA, ANSES

Description of the task

Using selected case studies and existing data from primarily pigs, we will develop models to explore the association between AMU and AMR at the herd level, assess the relative importance of AMU and clonal dissemination for resistance occurrence and simulate the within-farm transmission dynamics of AMR. Previous research has applied pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic modelling (PK/PD) - the relationship between drug concentration and effect - to the veterinary field to predict drug resistance and drug optimisation (dosing regimen, green antibiotics, etc...) as well as in vitro activity of antibiotics against pathogens. We will explore the use of this methodology here. Few PK/PD models describe the drug distribution in the body, in the gut and in excreta for pigs or poultry. The potency of the drug against veterinary pathogens and commensals could be described, but a fit between data and prediction requires some experimental results of good quality to set the parameter values and then an approval of datasets used for modelling will be necessary. Coupled with a population pharmacokinetic approach, PK/PD models can be used to estimate the range of effects for different levels of susceptibility of bacteria and so define the antimicrobial resistance selective window and compartment. Few theoretical models simulate the adaptation process in bacterial populations leading to resistance. During the project, a set of models will be reviewed and applied to available data sets produced by other WPs (after their release) and/or previous data obtained via avenues such as a literature search of peer reviewed publications. The analysis will be performed to identify the data gaps for the parameter value settings. We will then develop a strategy to implement future experimental studies able to fill the gaps (1. methodology for acquisition of the data and release of data sets intended for modelling) and derive a generic

modelling approach to cover different scenarios (2. Harmonized methodology for PK/PD modelling). We will also develop an on-farm model for transmission of AMR bacteria in the pig livestock sector and parameterise it for at least one type of AMR bacteria (e.g. ESBL E. coli). While a number of transmission models have previously been developed for bacteria such as Salmonella, there has been little development regarding AMR transmission and AMU usage, a gap we propose to address with this model. The model will also be designed to be able to assess the effectiveness of control measures with regards to reducing the prevalence and/or level of AMR bacteria in slaughter age pigs.

Sub-Task 2.1.1: PK/PD model to assess relationship between animal exposure and change in antimicrobial resistance

Sub-Task start month: 01

Sub-Task end month: 20

Sub-Task Leader: Jerome Henri

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES, APHA

There are both experimental and clinical evidence to support that dosing schedule may influence resistance development and that dosing regimen may be optimized by proper use of PK/PD. The investigations made by Eagle et. al. were the first demonstration that minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is not enough to describe bacterial activity and that the pharmacokinetics of the antibiotics need to be taken into account to have a better understanding of the antibiotics activity and to define precise targets. Vogelmann et al. and Craig investigated the PK/PD relationship of antibiotics and defined three PK/PD indices based on a measure of the drug exposure and the MIC of the bacteria. The terminology of these PK/PD indices have been standardized into fAUC/MIC, fC_{max}/MIC and fT_{>MIC}. PK/PD indices are summary endpoints based on the MIC, which do not provide any information on the time course of antimicrobial activity. Therefore a lot of information is lost in the process of generating these endpoints, such as the regrowth of bacteria that can be observed after an initial decay although the antibiotic concentration is kept constant, and suggesting a changing effect with time. These complexities can be analyzed by a modelling approach that allows description of the full time course of antimicrobial activity. A review of these PK/PD structural models describing the time course of resistance levels in the gut/excreta of the host (animal) will be necessary during the project to develop a generic PK/PD model. This PK/PD model will be developed according to a population approach (nonlinear mixed effect model) in order to associate the inter-animal variability to the structural model and then to get PK/PD relationship for each host (individual values) of the entire herd (population values). The identifiability of the model's parameters will be assessed according to collected datasets after their qualification. The model will allow testing of methodologies for (a) acquisition and qualification of data intended for PK/PD modelling purposes and (b) implementation, calibration and validation a generic PK/PD model of AMR in a herd for a couple AMD/bacteria.

Sub-Task 2.1.2: Assess relative importance of AMU and clonal dissemination for resistance occurrence

Sub-Task start month: 01

Sub-Task end month: 20

Sub-Task Leader: Michel Laurentie

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES, APHA

Once the variability is defined at the host level in the trio AMD/bacteria/host, simulations will be made in order to integrate variability factors relating to (i) the AMD and (ii) the bacteria.

(i) AMU's variability will be studied according to "Green AMDs", a concept recently developed by Toutain et al. and then simulations of the population PK/PD model (with the same structure) will be realized for the same AMDs but with different pharmacokinetic properties (different parameters' mean values and standard deviations) due to changes of formulations (long-acting formulations, i.e. a short elimination half-life with a limited volume of distribution and an appropriate plasma clearance AND eco-friendly properties, i.e. a clearance by hepatic metabolism is ideal, provided the metabolites are inactive but a high renal clearance is acceptable provided the eliminated active AMD is rapidly degraded in the environment or immobilized by physical sorption) in order "to make them greener" and to see the positive impact on AMR levels in the gut of the animals.

(ii) Clonal dissemination depends on resistance mechanism. In this part we will study if the variability of these processes can be simulated in changing values of the PD parameters of the PK/PD model or if structural adaptations of the generic model are necessary depending on the studied bacterial species. This will allow us to identify data gaps in order to experimentally check the simulations and modelling hypotheses done in this sub-task. The connection between the PK/PD model and the transmission model will also be elaborated in collaboration with sub-task 2.1.3 participants

Sub-Task 2.1.3: Development of on-farm transmission model

Sub-Task start month: 01

Sub-Task end month: 20

Sub-Task Leader: Robin Simons

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES

The on-farm model will use Monte-Carlo simulation techniques to allow incorporation of variability about model parameters and follow individual pigs on a farm over a period of time (e.g. one year); both with regards to susceptible and resistant bacteria status, using a modified Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) approach, and pig production factors such as moving pens while transitioning between production stages (i.e. from grower to weaner to finisher). The model will consider the risk posed from environmental contamination (e.g. from ingestion of faeces in the pig pen) and incorporate the effect of farm management factors such as cleaning of pens between batches. AMU on farm will be a primary consideration; The model will simulate when pigs are given antibiotics and the incorporation of equations to model the pharmacodynamics will enable simulating the effect of antimicrobials on the numbers of resistant gut bacteria. It is anticipated that the PK/PD models developed in this task (sub tasks 2.1.1 & 2.1.2) will inform this and we will investigate the feasibility of directly integrating them into the on-farm model. The model will simulate the levels of resistant and susceptible bacteria and antimicrobials consumed by the pigs and the resulting levels present in the faeces of infected pigs. The model will be designed to allow for relatively simple re-parameterisation for other (resistant and susceptible) bacteria in the future.

Sub-Task 2.1.4: Scenario analysis to assess hypothetical on-farm intervention measures.

Sub-Task start month: 06

Sub-Task end month: 20

Sub-Task Leader: Robin Simons

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES

The on-farm model will be designed to help assess the impact of on-farm interventions in controlling prevalence and spread of AMR bacteria. Discussion with policy colleagues in the first year of the

project will identify potential intervention measures that can be incorporated into the on-farm model. Potential control measures to consider include reducing antimicrobial usage. It is anticipated that in the future data will be available to parameterise the model for specific interventions, e.g. from the AMR-2 EJP project, but are unlikely to be available during the timeframe of this task. As such, here we will conduct scenario analyses to assess the effect of hypothetical interventions to demonstrate the proof of principle for when real world data are available and inform as to the level of effectiveness necessary for an intervention to have a meaningful impact. The scenario analyses will also be used to investigate the impact of uncertainty about the model parameters on the results.

Sub-Task 2.1.5: Communication of results

Sub-Task start month: 18

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: Robin Simons

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Pascal Sanders

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES

In addition to being reported inside the project, results will be communicated through appropriate standard scientific outlets (e.g. peer-reviewed publications, scientific meetings).

Task 2.2: Models for transmission between livestock and human populations

Task start month: 01

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: Antonios Zagaris (WbvR)

Deputy Task Leader: Martin Bootsma (RIVM)

Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, RIVM

T2.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. Its aim is to understand better large-scale transmission between populations, assess infection risk and set the stage for designing intervention measures and assessing them in silico. This modelling study will first use a massive sample library available within the consortium and counting 30,000 samples from human and animal populations and the environment. The study will be adapted using project-generated data as these become available. Models developed in T2.1 and expert knowledge from WP3 will play significant roles in intervention assessment.

Sub-Task 2.2.1: Development of mathematical models for source-attribution

Sub-Task start month: 01

Sub-Task end month: 22

Sub-Task Leader: Martin Bootsma (RIVM)

Sub-Task Participants: WbvR, RIVM

T2.2.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. Its scope is to model transmission of resistance mechanistically and, in this manner, understand the relative importance of human, animal and environmental transmission routes. The focal point will be ESBL's, because of relevance and genetic data availability, but the methods developed here will be more widely applied. Prior dynamical models left these routes underexplored by focusing on within-host AMR dynamics. Recent statistical studies, on the other hand, clustered human and animal populations into epidemiological units using the relative prevalence of AMR-encoding plasmids. Here, we will

use these analyses to fit data to several transmission models - compartmental models (CM), next generation matrices (NGM), system dynamics (SD) - and to assess goodness of fit. This will allow estimation of AMR dissemination levels between human/animal reservoirs, food and the environment, thus directing efficient intervention design in T2.2.2. It will also pinpoint important transmission routes insufficiently resolved due to data gaps, thus aiding the design of further data collection. Two significant data sources will feed into this task: longitudinal data on AMR prevalence in different reservoirs and strain data from them. We will explore and integrate multiple modeling approaches due to problem complexity, starting with a limited number of reservoirs afforded high-quality data (e.g., hospitals and extramural community, as well as farm animals and farmers) and gradually incorporating more reservoirs, in one overall model, as we test and refine our methodology.

Sub-Task 2.2.2: Assessment of intervention measures

Sub-Task start month: 13

Sub-Task end month: 22

Sub-Task Leader: Jeroen van Leuken (RIVM)

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, RIVM

T2.2.2 will be underpinned by model building from T2.1.3 - T2.2.1 and expert input from WP3. It will focus on investigating systematically how strain prevalence relates to transmission, so as to quantify changes in prevalence brought about by transmission-attenuating measures. An additional point of interest will be the (lack of) robustness of the transmission network to disruptive attacks, so that high- impact interventions can be designed. Interventions targeting single transmission routes will impact all reservoir prevalences nonlinearly, necessitating a systematized approach. A first step will be a univariate sensitivity analysis quantifying relative importance of AMR transmission pathways. We will follow up by computing the basic reproduction number R_0 between reservoirs under various intervention scenarios, to reveal intervention opportunities within the current operational model. This part of the work will employ simplified model representations using the next generation matrix (NGM) methodology (validated against the full dynamical model). Combining interventions should substantially reduce the effective reproduction number and significantly limit transfer of resistance traits between key reservoirs. Input from T2.1 and WP3 will be critical in obtaining realistic estimates for the magnitude of interventions. An analysis of the transmission network characteristics will provide additional guidance, utilizing recent advances on understanding robustness/vulnerability of various types of dynamic networks.

Sub-Task 2.2.3: Communication of results

Sub-Task start month: 18

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: Antonios Zagaris (WbvR)

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, RIVM

This work will form part of a Ph.D. project within NCOH and will thus extend past the two-year project duration. In addition to reporting in the project, we will communicate results through the resulting Ph.D. thesis and standard scientific outlets (peer-reviewed publications, scientific meetings).

WP3: Transmission through the food chain

WP start month: 1

WP end month: 24

WP Leader: BfR

Deputy WP Leader: WbvR

WP participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, NVI, RIVM

Description of the WP

This workpackage will aim on reviewing available methods to model the change of prevalence and concentration of bacteria with phenotypic resistance or specific resistance determinants along the food chain for exposure assessments. This will increase accessibility and exchangeability of these models. Building on that and in collaboration with WP2, generic models will be developed and implemented where different exposure pathways as well as different food chains can be evaluated and compared with respect to risk. These models will be translated into a standardised format according to the recently (at BfR) developed/proposed Food Safety Knowledge (FSK) Framework which aims at facilitating access and exchange of models. This should support rapid assessments when new patterns arise or specific measures needs to be assessed. The work will contribute to progress beyond the present state of art and enable rapid exchange of models and information between researchers, countries and public & animal health institutes in the future.

Hence, the objectives of the WP are:

- To create an inventory of available exposure assessment models and to translate them into a standardised format according to the Food Safety Knowledge Framework
- To establish generic exposure assessment models for the chicken, pork and mussels production chain
- To establish a generic exposure assessment model based on WCS/metagenomics data

This WP is closely linked with WP2, where specific on farm models are developed and with WP6, where overarching analysis will take place. The close linkage with these two WPs is guaranteed in staffing, since the team of deputy WP 3 leader is also actively involved in WP2, and the team of the WP3 leader is actively involved in WP6.

BfR will lead WP3 and task 3.1, focusing on an inventory of models following FSK Standard and contribute to task 3.2. by developing a generic exposure assessment model for the chicken production chain.

CVI will assist leading WP3, and contribute to interaction and integration of results which link WP2 and WP3. As such, they will participate as consultant/advisor in each subtask.

RIVM will lead task 3.2 and contribute to task 3.2 by improving the exposure assessment model for the pork production chain (subtask 3.2.2).

NVI will lead task 3.2.3 and contribute to this task by developing a generic model for the mussels production chain.

DTU will lead task 3.3 and contribute to tasks 3.1, 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.

Task 3.1: Inventory of available exposure assessment models and related data and transfer to FSK Standard

Task start month: 01

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: BfR

Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, NVI, RIVM

Description of the task

An inventory will be made on the models/ elements for exposure assessment which are available among partners. Details on bacterial species, phenotypic and resistance traits, animal species and

production stages, processing steps, transmission pathways (foodborne, direct contact), spread (horizontal vs. vertical) as well as risk factors (AMU, biosecurity, trade, other factors) considered will be collected and summarised. Relevant data on regional/ local patterns for food processing and consumption habits linked to or relevant for the models will be collected.

Sub-Task 3.1.2: Transfer of available exposure assessment models developed in R (or matlab) to FSK Standard for at least one type of AMR bacteria and at least one animal (chicken, pig or mussels)

Sub-Task start month: 10

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: BfR

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, NVI, RIVM

Task 3.2: Exposure assessment models for different production chains

Task start month: 01

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: RIVM

Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, NVI, RIVM

Description of the task

Exposure assessment calculations for selected AMR determinants (e.g. ESBL E. coli, Colistin resistance gene *mcr-1*) will be performed for broiler, pig and mussels. Task 3.1 will provide an inventory of available models. Based on this, possibly further improvement of the available farm-to-fork models will be necessary for the calculations in Task 3.2. A close link to WP2 where transmission models within farms will be addressed is envisaged. It is expected that the main part of the model parameters will be micro-organism-specific and reusable for specific AMR (e.g. ESBL E. coli) calculations. As for the AMR specific (e.g. ESBL E. coli) parameters, the main challenge will be to obtain data the concentrations along the food chain. For parameter values in general, data made available by partners or collected in collaborating consortia (e.g. FBZ-2, FBZ-3, FBZ-4, AMR-2) will be useful. Possibly assumptions, expert estimates or scenario studies will have to fill remaining data gaps. Given the large variation in farming systems, slaughter processes and consumption habits across the EU, it will be necessary to select one or a limited number of countries or cluster(s) of similar countries to come to a realistic amount of work. For comparative exposure assessment used for attribution (e.g. between food animals, farming systems, specific food products within food animals, etc.) relatively simple exposure models can be applied. As a next step, the ambition is to create the ability to calculate the impact of intervention measures, but possibly scenarios studies will prove to be the highest achievable.

Sub-Task 3.2.1: Exposure assessment model for the chicken production chain

Sub-Task start month: 13

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: BfR

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, DTU

BfR will improve a model for the chicken production chain with a main focus on the spread of newly emerging resistance determinants, e.g. *mcr-1* and/or specific plasmidic ESBL-genes and impact of intervention at different processing steps. Implementation will following the FSK- standard and will

aim to develop a generic model. In this workpackage we will work close together with WP2 which focuses on farm transmission. Variability about model parameters will be integrated. Where real-world data are missing, different scenarios will be assessed to feed in future research needs and decisions towards preliminary risk management decisions.

Sub-Task 3.2.2: Exposure assessment model for the pork production chain

Sub-Task start month: 13

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: RIVM

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, RIVM

Work conducted in this workpackage will be built on previous work related to modelling Salmonella in the farm-to-fork pork chain. These approaches will be modified to allow assessment of exposure by emerging resistance determinants and the impact of different processing steps as well as intervention measures. In this workpackage we will work close together with WP2 which focuses on farm transmission.

Sub-Task 3.2.3: Exposure assessment model for the mussel production chain

Sub-Task start month: 01

Sub-Task end month: 24

Sub-Task Leader: NVI

Sub-Task Participants: BfR, NVI

This workpackage will first assess different cooking procedures of mussels and their effect on the load on emerging resistance determinants of the indicator bacteria E.coli. An exposure assessment model will be developed which will thereby use data regarding resistance frequencies from surveillance of mussels and data from the experiments to assess the probability of consumption of emerging resistance determinants from mussels.

Task 3.3: Generic comparative exposure assessment model

Task start month: 13

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: DTU

Task Participants: BfR, WbvR, DTU, NVI, RIVM

Description of the task:

In interaction with WP2 we will determine the potential for deriving or creating generic methods for exposure assessments for different production types, different bacteria, plasmids, and genes. These generic methods may be more crude, but will allow for combining the risks in the different (sub-)categories, which is otherwise never totally acceptable and correct. Thus we expect them to create a more complete picture of the AMR problems throughout.

WP4: Machine learning methods for quantification of risk and health effects

WP start month 01

WP end month 24

WP Leader Thomas Selhorst (BfR)

Deputy WP Leader Madelaine Norström (NVI)
WP participants NVI, RIVM

The development of antibiotic resistance is a complex process influenced by a multitude of risk factors, and this process is still not understood in all parts. It is undoubted that the occurrence of multiple resistance patterns is a key feature of antibiotic resistance and the aim of risk factor analysis should be the disclosure of resistance patterns and potential risk factors. Perhaps, we might not have understood the process of antimicrobial resistance, because we have not used the appropriate statistical methods for the analysis of our observation. In order to contribute to the understanding of antimicrobial resistance, a repository of state of the art statistical methods collectively referred to as 'machine learning' methods will be compiled. The aim of this WP is the systematic identification and recording of the known methods and their comparison. In particular, a comparison with the classical methods (e.g. logistic regression) of data analysis is employed. The logistic regression model will be taken as the baseline comparator, because it is the de facto standard model for the analysis of relations of a binary (and also multinomial) outcomes and observed influential factors. Its popularity is based on its availability in statistical software programs and its adaptability to specific tasks (Dasgupta et al.; 2014). But, good predictions and effect size estimation from a logistic model requires to guess the true data generating model, i.e. guessing the predictors (risk factors) and their interactions. If the model is mis-specified, both predictions and effect size estimates may be more than slightly in error (Dasgupta et al.; 2014).

All documentation and program code will be produced with the help of R and especially knitR with is used today for the creation of reproducible scientific documents. Additionally, we will use github for versioning.

WP is subdivided into 4 tasks:

Task4.2: Methods for testing model -validity, -sensitivity and –robustness

Task start M13

Task end M21

Task Leader BfR, Thomas Selhorst:

Deputy Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Description of the task

in this task we will analyze model validity, model sensitivity, model robustness, the influence of test and training data selection, and the influence of correlated, biased, blurred, missing influential variables on model predictions. Comparison to the baseline comparator will be performed. This task can be performed only in the presence of data. A preliminary investigation has revealed that records on antimicrobial resistance were freely available in the past (for example Ludwig et al, 2013), and it can be expected that the situation has and will improve in the future. The use of these records ensures the implementation of Task 4.2. Nevertheless, WP 4 will be happy to use records that are generated as part of AMR-3 or have been generated by the project partners in the past.

Task 4.2 is subdivided in 3 subtasks:

Sub-Tasks T4.2.1: Selection of test data set(s) to be used (at least one taken from the internet will be provided) includes literature review and description of data sets provided by partners of project AMR- 3. A list of possible datasources will be compiled.

Sub-Task start month: 13

Sub-Task end month: 14

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Tasks T4.2.2: will define a work bench for assessing model validity, model sensitivity, model robustness, the influence of test and training data selection, and the influence of correlated, biased, blurred, missing influential variables on model predictions.

Sub-Task start month: 15

Sub-Task end month: 17

Sub-Task Leader: BfR Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madeleine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Tasks T4.2.3: will conduct analysis on model validity, model sensitivity, model robustness, the influence of test and training data selection, and the influence of correlated, biased, blurred, missing influential variables on model predictions using example data sets. A comparison with the baseline comparator is conducted.

Sub-Task start month: 18

Sub-Task end month: 21

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Task4.3: Methods for the quantification of effect sizes and calculation of population attributable fractions (PAFs)

Task start 22

Task end 27

Task Leader BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Description of the task:

we will analyze and develop methods for the quantification of effect sizes. This is an important issue because ML methods do not necessarily provide estimates for the effect size. But, quantified effect sizes are essential for the calculation of risks and PAFs (population attributable fractions) and are related to burden of disease calculations. Thus quantified effect sizes are necessary condition for further calculations. The baseline comparator, i.e. logistic regression models, naturally provide quantified effect sizes and alternative methods are compared with the baseline comparator.

Task 4.3 is sub-divided into three subtasks.

Sub-Task 4.3.1: Literature review of methodologies and compilation of the selected methods

Sub-Task start month 22

Sub-Task end month 24

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Task 4.3.2: Programming of the selected methods, inclusion in the collection of methods and creation of methods Description.

Sub-Task start month 24

Sub-Task end month 26

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Task 4.3.3: Application of selected methods to the available data, comparison of the results including comparison with baseline comparator and creating recommendations.

Sub-Task start month 26

Sub-Task end month 27

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madeleine Norstrom (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Task 4.4: ML and causality. Does it fit together?

Task start 28

Task end 36

Task Leader BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Description of the task

Causality is a fundamental prerequisite for the calculation of source attribution, risk factor profiling, health impact assessment of antimicrobial resistance, and finally for decision making, and control. But, often it is assumed that machine learning and causality preclude each other.

Despite this assumption, advances were made in machine learning for tackling problems in causality (e.g. distinguish cause from effects, infer the effect of interventions). Modern machine learning methodologies provided efficient methods for causal structure learning and powerful tools for conditional independence test, which is a key component in traditional constraint-based causal discovery. This task will review the literature, setup a repository of methods and finally apply these methods to available data sets.

Sub-Task 4.4.1 Literature review of methodologies and setup of a repository for the selected methods

Sub-Task start month 28

Sub-Task end month 30

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Task 4.4.2: Implementation of methods in R, including a description and a sample application

Sub-Task start month 30

Sub-Task end month 33

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

Sub-Task 4.3.3 Application of selected methods to the available data, comparison of the results including comparison with baseline comparator and creating recommendations.

Sub-Task start month 33

Sub-Task end month 36

Sub-Task Leader: BfR, Thomas Selhorst:

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Madelaine Norström (NVI)

Sub-Task Participants: NVI, RIVM

WP5: The burden of disease caused by AMR exposure

WP start month 1

WP end month 24

WP Leader Tine Hald (DTU)

Deputy WP Leader Marie-Josée Mangen (RIVM)

WP participants DTU, RIVM

Description of the WP

In December 2015, WHO published the first estimates of the global burden of foodborne diseases including 12 bacterial infections (1,2). These estimates, however, did not address AMR, and the overall contribution of AMR to the human disease burden and specifically the proportion attributable to livestock and food remains unknown. The overall objective of this WP is to conduct a structured expert judgement (SEJ) to fill data gaps that need to be addressed in order to estimate the human disease burden associated with AMR exposure through different exposure pathways. We will use integrative modelling combining existing data and approaches with new data collected through SEJ in an attempt to quantify the burden of AMR due to human exposure through livestock and food. SEJ has previously been used with success to estimate the proportion of infections caused by specific pathogens caused by exposure through food, direct contact animals and other transmission routes (3,4). The findings of the SEJ study will be combined with estimates of exposure to AMR through different transmission routes (as estimated by other WPs in this project and culminating in WP6) to estimate the incidence of each health outcome in the population, as well as the burden of this disease in terms of Disability Adjusted Life years, DALYs (WP6).

T-5.3. Identifying, enrolling and interviewing the experts

Task start month:4

Task end month:17

Task Leader: Tine Hald (DTU)

Deputy Task Leader: Marie-Josée Mangen (RIVM)

Task Participants: DTU, RIVM

Description of the task

Depending on the nature of the final set of target questions, it may be necessary to recruit experts with very different backgrounds, and therefore it may be beneficial to distribute the targets

questions into two or more expert panels. An iterative peer nomination process based on a professional network sampling technique, sometimes called 'snowball sampling' will be used to identify a pool of potential experts. Since the purpose of this process is to identify an adequately large pool of appropriate experts, rather than to identify the entire expert network, the process of referral will be continued until an adequate size pool is identified to fill panels of 8 to 12 experts per panel.

T-5.4. Analysing the data to obtain aggregated responses to the target questions

Task start month:18

Task end month: 21

Task Leader: Tine Hald (DTU)

Deputy Task Leader: Marie-Josée Mangen (RIVM)

Task Participants: DTU, RIVM

Description of the task

Based on the responses to the seed questions, experts are scored with regard to statistical accuracy (calibration score) and informativeness (information score). The calculated calibration and information scores are used to aggregate experts' judgments on target variables. Data will be analysed using the software EXCALIBUR (<http://www.lighttwist.net/wp/excalibur>) that also allows for a direct comparison of the results that would be obtained from unweighted aggregation of expert judgments with those produced using performance weights. The final choice of weight will be decided by an assessment of the statistical accuracy and informativeness of the expert responses. The weights will be used for constructing joint probability distributions for the target variables, which will serve as input for the disease burden model developed in WP6.

WP6: Integration of information by Bayesian Evidence Synthesis

WP start month

WP end month

WP Leader Eelco Franz (RIVM)

Deputy WP Leader: Thomas Sellhorst (BfR)

WP participants BfR, DTU, NVI

Description of the WP

To estimate the public health impact caused by AMR, data from various origins must be combined. These include occurrence of resistance (genetic factors, or carrier species) in environmental compartments (including food and water), transmission of resistant microbes in and between animal and human populations, and the relation between exposure to resistant microbes and health effects. Combining these sources of information not only requires dealing with different sources of varying accuracy, but also different modalities. Occurrence of a resistance gene in a food ingredient cannot be directly translated into human exposure to a resistant pathogen, or to an associated health risk. As an analogy, the fraction of the reported incidence of urinary tract (UT) infections caused by resistant strains may not be simply proportional to the carriage of these strains in the general population. In work packages 1 - 5 such relations are described by means of mathematical models. Integration of the information contributed by these work packages must not only consist of combining model outputs, but should also include metrics of the model performance, to allow information to be weighted by accuracy. This approach is similar to meta-analysis, but it is more general, in that information from different modalities is translated into a common metric (de Angelis et al. 2014; Spiegelhalter 2003). A highly simplified example is shown in Figure 1: resistant bacteria

may be enumerated in samples from surface swabs. The sampling distribution (Poisson, or some compound distribution to model microbial aggregation) may be used to characterize the concentration of these bacteria, and an exposure model may be employed to predict human exposure, for instance, the transmission of infectious bacteria via the hand to cause urinary tract infection. A dose response model is needed to translate exposure into UT infection, or another relevant health endpoint as may be observed in hospital studies. Thus, the two bottom rectangles represent observed data: the occurrence of (AB resistant) bacteria on surfaces, and incident cases of UT infections. The connection between these observations are described by the model framework, possibly informed by other data sources (not shown here). The Bayesian evidence synthesis framework allows a joint analysis of the relationships between parameters and data sources in an information network of the type shown in Figure 1 to be conducted, and thus aids in providing consensus estimates (in this case, of the dose response parameters α and β , and/or parameters of the exposure model). This framework also ensures that uncertainty associated with all parameters is correctly propagated to the parameters for which inference is desired. Absence of convergence indicates inconsistencies, allowing identification of potentially incorrect (model) assumptions and/or possibly biased data sources. Thus, the integrative model may help in finding conflicting evidence, and thus provides a means for correcting the analysis.

Task 6.3: Update evidence network for information developed in the other work packages

Task start month 12

Task end month 18

Task Leader: RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Task Participants: BfR, NVI, DTU

Description of the task

Continuous, iterative work, use project meetings (to be organized by the project lead and WP leaders) to keep up to date with WP results, and select results that can be used to improve the Bayesian evidence synthesis model. If possible, early versions of the evidence synthesis models may guide selection of problem areas: identify critical variables that are poorly known, or conversely, variables that exert little influence, e.g. on health burden estimates. This may help prioritizing data acquisition and identify critical data gaps.

Task 6.4: Define endpoint for the current project and report results for the evidence synthesis model in its endpoint state.

Task start month 18

Task end month 24

Task Leader: RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Task Participants: BfR, NVI, DTU

Description of the task

Deliverables

D-JRP3-0.2	Second annual report	24
D-JRP3-1.2	Establishment of a database of field (meta-)genomic data	15
D-JRP3-1.4	Test and parameterization of the assembly pipeline for metagenomics data	18
D-JRP3-1.5	Biological annotations of plasmid identified in the pipeline	

D-JRP3-1.6	WGAS-based method for genomic data analysis	18
D-JRP3-1.7	Development of regression model for genomic data analysis	18
D-JRP3-1.8	Integration of genetic traits associated to AMR and plasmid content information into models (WP6)	24
D-JRP3-2.1	Report/draft paper on generic PK/PD model	M24
D-JRP3-2.2	Report/draft paper on on-farm model	M24
D-JRP3-2.3	Report/draft paper on transmission model	M24
D-JRP3-2.4	Report/draft paper on intervention strategies	M24
D-JRP3-3.1	Inventory with models and related data in FSK standard	24
D-JRP3-3.2	Scientific report on a generic model for the chicken production chain	24
D-JRP3-3.3	Scientific report on an adapted model for the pork production chain developed	24
D-JRP3-3.4	Scientific report on an model for the exposure assessment of AMR through mussels	24
D-JRP3-3.5	Scientific report on a generic comparative exposure assessment model	24
D-JRP3-4.2	Recommended methods for risk profiling in investigations on antibiotic resistance	24
D-JRP3-5.1	Report on structured expert judgement	17
D-JRP3-6.1	Publication on final evidence network	18
D-JRP3-6.2	Policy-targeted report	24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP3-12	Formulate CM/NGM (CVI, NCOH) and SD (RIVM) transmission models	13
M-JRP3-13	Produce case study (collected datasets) baseline results for PK/PD (ANSES)	15
M-JRP3-14	Test and validation of assembly pipeline on synthetic and reference genomic data	15
M-JRP3-15	Establish connection between the PK/PD model and the on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	16
M-JRP3-16	Establish connection between the PK/PD model and the on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	16
M-JRP3-17	Calibrate models using data library (CVI)	17
M-JRP3-18	Performed interviews	17
M-JRP3-19	Develop model frameworks for PK/PD and on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	18
M-JRP3-20	Simulations of the PK/PD model for green AMDs (ANSES)	18
M-JRP3-21	Concept for a improved model for the chicken production chain developed	18
M-JRP3-22	Concept for an adapted model for the pork production chain developed	18
M-JRP3-23	Concept for an model for the exposure assessment of AMR through mussels	18
M-JRP3-24	Analysis of HTS field data with assembly pipeline	18
M-JRP3-25	Analysis of field genomic data with WGAS-based method	18
M-JRP3-26	Analysis of field genomic data with regression model	18

M-JRP3-27	Produce case study baseline model results for on-farm model (APHA)	20
M-JRP3-28	Formulate/investigate interventions (RIVM, NCOH, CVI, BfR43)	21
M-JRP3-29	Structural adaptations of the PK/PD model according to AMR mechanisms (ANSES)	21
M-JRP3-30	Concept on a generic comparative exposure assessment model	21
M-JRP3-31	Model development and model assessment completed	21
M-JRP3-32	Assimilate project-generated data (NCOH)	22
M-JRP3-33	Assess hypothetical intervention measures using on-farm model (APHA)	22
M-JRP3-34	Final meeting and report	24
M-JRP3-35	Make recommendations to fill data gaps (RIVM, NCOH, CVI)	24
M-JRP3-36	Data gaps in PK/PD modelling and propositions of experimental studies with a defined methodology (ANSES)	24

2.1.3.1.11 JRP4-MAD-VIR

Set of activity	JRP4/R1/ET-1 Non-NGS-based methods									
Project title	Metagenomic Array Detection of Emerging Virus in EU									
Project acronym	MAD-VIR									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)	P13-SSI			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)				P13-SSI		
Project Coordinator person name	Anders Fomsgaard			Project Deputy Leader person name				Maiken W Rosenstjerne		
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month	M1					Project End month			M24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	2.03					0.4				
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M	16.8			5.2					2.15	
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVr	FHI
P.M	1.2	0.4				0.4	0.4			
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M		0.8								
Objectives										
The overall objective is to validate and implement the microarray technology as a harmonized methodology for detection of new and emerging virus threats through testing of human, animal and vector samples from EU participants										
Description of work										
WP1: Coordination and management										

WP start month: M13

WP end month: M24

WP Leader: Anders Fomsgaard, SSI

Deputy WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

WP participants: All

Description of the WP1: WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

WP1 contain the coordination and management of the project. Some of the main tasks of the WP is to;

- 1) Overall project management
- 2) Coordinate sharing of collected samples between the many participating labs and the 4 method microarray laboratories.
- 3) Coordinate regular telecoms between the many participating laboratories.
- 4) Organize the annual meeting.

WP2: Sample collection

WP start month: M13

WP end month: M24

WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy WP Leader: Francisco Llorente, INIA

WP participants: All

Description of the WP2

WP2: continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

WP2 is the WP for sample collection. The different participating laboratories will during the entire project collect clinical samples (e.g. blood, urine, biopsies) from unusual infectious cases and surveillance samples from human and animals. In addition samples from vector born animals such as (e.g. mosquitoes, ticks, birds and rodents) will be collected and analysed. Some of the laboratories already have huge sample collections in the freezer. These samples have not been analyses by metagenomic methods and the samples will also be used in the project.

WP3: Diagnostic and surveillance

WP start month: M13

WP end month: M24

WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne

Deputy WP Leader: Sylvie Lecollinet, ANSES

WP participants: All

Description of the WP3

WP3: continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. WP3 is the WP for Diagnostics and surveillance. The collected samples will be tested for viruses using the MAD-Vir microarray and for comparison also tested by other diagnostic tools such as real-time PCR, different Microfluidic PCRs, Nanostring technology and sequencing.

Task 3.2: Analysis of samples

Task start month: 1st September 2018

Task end month: 31st August 2019

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne , SSI
Deputy Task Leader: Jovita Fernandez-Pinero, INIA
Task Participants: SSI, PIWET, INIA, APHA

Description of the task T3.2

T3.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. T3.2 is the WP for Diagnostics and surveillance. The collected samples will be tested for viruses using the MAD-Vir microarray and for comparison tested other diagnostic tools such as real-time PCR, different Microfluidic PCRs, Nanostring technology and sequencing.

WP4: Data Sharing

WP start month: 1st September 2018
 WP end month: 31st August 2019

WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI
Deputy WP Leader: Anders Fomsgaard, SSI
WP participants: All

Description of the WP4

WP4: continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. WP4 is the WP for data sharing. The EJP Webpage (www.onehealthjep.eu) will be used for data sharing between the participating laboratories. The Webpage will contain information regarding all collected samples, methods used, SOPs and results.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP4-1.2	Second annual meeting for the participating Institutes	24
D-JRP4-2.1	Collection of samples (maximum 1500 samples in total from year 2017 to 2019)	18
D-JRP4-3.4	MAD-VIR microarray analysis of all collected samples (max. 1500)	24
D-JRP4-4.2	Fully updated Website	24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
	n/a	

2.1.3.1.12 JRP5-Tox-Detect

Priority Topic reference		JRP5/R1/ET1									
Project title		Development and harmonization of innovative methods for comprehensive analysis of food-borne toxigenic bacteria, ie. Staphylococci, Bacillus cereus and Clostridium perfringens									
Project acronym		TOX-Detect									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym) ⁱⁱ		1 Anses				Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)					
Project Coordinator person name		JA Hennekinne				Project Deputy Leader person name				Y NIA	
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2 nd period				
Project Start month				M1			Project End month ⁱⁱⁱ			M36	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensan	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M	27.41		11				13				
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M							51.5	6.95			
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UOS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI	
P.M											
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M	1.5										
Objectives											
Description of work											
WP0. Coordination, management and communication											
WP0 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. WP start month: M0											

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne (P1) Deputy WP Leader: Frédéric Auvray (P1)

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P19

Description of the WP:

General management strategy

The overall purpose of the management structures is to ensure the timely implementation of the tasks and the smooth running of the project as a whole. Its primary goal is to identify arising opportunities and detect the occurrence of obstacles as early as possible, hence maximise the outcome of the project while preventing delays in its implementation. This will ensure that all tasks and research objectives are realised effectively and at a high quality level within time and budget. Due to the structure of the work packages and the relatively low number of partners, a very lean, thus flexible management structure and a clear decision-making process was chosen to avoid creating an unduly hierarchical system or an unnecessary administrative burden.

The project management will be subdivided into several sub-domains as follows:

Administrative and scientific management: Administrative management is the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (PC) who will delegate tasks directly to project partners. The scientific management of each of the work packages is the responsibility of the relevant WPL who reports to the PC.

Financial and legal management: Overall, the financial management of the budget will also be the responsibility of the PC, who will, should the need arise, formulate any required redistribution of the overall budget in cooperation with the WPL. Financial management of the individually allocated parts of the budget and all required reporting will be the sole responsibility of the individual institution. Overall legal management will be coordinated by the PC. Management of intellectual property rights (IPR) is the primary responsibility of the data or intellectual property creator.

Although direct communication between all consortium members is preferred and strongly encouraged, project-internal communication will be ensured through the establishment of clear communication channels and reporting structures within each WP by the WPL and between all project partners by the PC. All information materials like flyers, leaflets etc. as well as scientific publications like posters, presentations or journal articles will be made available to partners for approval. Each partner has also the right to veto its name being mentioned on any publication.

Management structures

Project coordinator (PC)

The PC is named in the contract with the EJP and acts as the intermediary between the contractors and the EJP. The main responsibilities of the Coordinator are the following:

- General coordination of the project
- Submit reports and deliverables to the EJP, in particular periodic scientific and management reports
- Participate in and be responsible for coordination of meetings
- Ensure the timely interaction and communication between the WPs
- Ensure the necessary information and document flow between the partners
- Ensure that all necessary legal and ethical responsibilities and obligations are known to the consortium institutions and that they are acted upon
- Overall responsibility for financial management, including budgeting, resource allocation and distribution and financial controls
- Ensure external communication, information and dissemination of knowledge.

Work Package Leader (WPL)

Each WP has one WPL. Deputy WPL can be nominated. In case any replacement should become necessary, a new WPL will be appointed by partners. The main responsibilities of the WPLs are the

following:

- Ensure the timely implementation of their WP
- Attain all deliverables
- Communicate whenever milestones are reached or delayed
- Suggest solutions on how delays can be avoided or their effects minimised
- Issue a detailed project work plan.

Meetings and reports

Although electronic communication will be used extensively for the implementation of the WPs and the management of the project, face-to-face meetings are nevertheless an essential part of research and the running of any project. They further team building, help to develop mutual respect as well as confidence and, in many situations, provide the most effective mechanism for trouble-shooting of arising difficulties.

Consortium meetings with partners will take place at the beginning (kick-off meeting, meeting 0), after 18 months (meeting 1), after 24 months (meeting 2) and at the end of the project (wrap-up meeting, meeting 3).

Minutes and reports on all formal meetings and decisions will be distributed to all partners. Great importance will be attached to regular reporting during the whole project period. Where appropriate work package leaders will provide internal reports to the PC twice yearly. These will contain

information on work completed during the period, work planned for the next period and work behind schedule.

Although the coordinator has overall responsibility for the preparation of the financial reports, it is the sole responsibility of each participating institution to ensure proper accounting and timely reporting to the PC and the EJP. As link between the project contractors and the EJP, the coordinator will be responsible for scientific reporting to the EJP.

Risk management

Changes necessary in order to deliver milestones on time as well as delays and problems in achieving the milestones will be reported in advance of partner meetings by the WPL, including a suggestion for alternative strategies. Modifications to the project made possible by newly available materials and techniques will be discussed, evaluated and, if considered appropriate, implemented in a coordinated manner, as will possible changes in emphasis based on developments in perceived threats and newly published work appearing in the literature.

Task 0.1: General coordination and management of the project (administrative and financial)

T0.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task 0.2 and 0.3: Organisation of 1 meeting fac-to-face with all partners.

T0.3 Meeting 1: follow up of technical WPs (WP2, WP3 and WP4)

T0.3 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP.

T0.4 Meeting 2: results of technical WP2 and WP3

T0.4 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP.

Task 0.6: mandatory reports on network activities: interim activity report, final report

T0.6 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

WP2. Characterization of toxins/virulence factors

WP2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M30

WP Leader: Nalini Rama-Rao (P18)

Deputy WP Leader: Valérie Fessard (P1) WP participants: P1, P18, P19

Description of the WP:

Background and objectives

Although the main causes of pathogenicity for toxin-producing bacteria such as *Bacillus cereus* and *Clostridium perfringens* are well known today, the mechanisms responsible for the expression of this virulence need, however, more investigations. For *B. cereus*, because there was a tendency in the past to consider all *B. cereus* strains as potentially pathogen, food microbiological diagnostics were focused on species determination using conventional culture-based methods. However the pathological potential of the strains ranges from neutral to highly virulent. Therefore, in order to characterize pathogenic stains isolated from food poisoning outbreaks, methods have been developed to detect toxin genes using PCR-based diagnostic tools for the three main enterotoxins (Nhe, Hbl and CytK) as well as for the emetic toxin (cereulide). However, only the emetic strains (which carry the *ces* gene) and rare diarrheal strains harboring the *cytK1* gene could be assigned as clearly pathogenic while the other factors contributing to *B. cereus*-induced gastroenteritis remain unknown. Similarly for *C. perfringens*, even if 17 different toxins have been described, this bacterial pathogen is currently classified in five toxic types (A to E) only based on the production of 4 major toxins (alpha, beta, epsilon and iota). The *C. perfringens* type A that produces CPE toxin is a major cause of food-borne gastroenteritis (FBGE) whereas the role of other virulence factors remains poorly investigated. Several data also indicate that, for these two pathogens, the level of toxin production could play a major role in determining the pathogenic potential of a particular strain, while the presence of specific toxin genes appears to be less discriminating. In addition, although cytotoxicity assays have already been used for classifying bacterial strains according to their toxic potency, further investigation on the toxicity mechanisms involved has been rarely carried out.

Approach

For toxigenic bacteria such as *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* whose pathogenic potential remains to be further defined, two complementary approaches will be used in parallel. On one hand, candidate toxins and/or virulence factors will be characterized using automated fluorescence microscopy and in vitro and cellular tests. In order to correlate the results with a “true” toxicity of the different strains at the intestinal level, toxicity testing will be conducted on a human intestinal cell line for viability measurement as well as for identification of the molecular mechanisms of toxicity (apoptosis, DNA damage, pro-inflammatory effects, oxidative stress and mitochondrial membrane potential) using High Content Analysis. This method is based on automated image acquisition and analysis, thereby rapidly generating large amounts of quantitative biological data from cellular imaging. On the other hand, reverse-transcriptase (RT)-PCR and general transcriptomic assays will also be used to assess virulence and toxin gene expression, from bacteria grown as pure cultures. The expression patterns of bacterial toxins/virulence factors will then be correlated to the identification of specific toxicity profiles, which could provide a toolbox for the prediction of the toxicity of the bacterial strains.

Task 2.1. Characterization of candidate toxin and/or virulence genes using toxicity tests

T2.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Valérie Fessard (P1)

Deputy Task Leader: Nalini Rama-Rao (P18) Task Participants: P1, P18, P19

Description of the task:

The cytotoxicity of the strains of *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* will be tested following 2h and 24h treatments of intestinal Caco2 cells using classical toxicity tests including the neutral red uptake assay. Cellular imaging-based High Content Analysis approaches will be developed and used to characterize the mechanisms of toxicity of a subset of specific strains in detail. Various markers of cellular toxicity will be evaluated. These markers will include apoptosis (active Caspase-3, annexin V), genotoxicity (γ H2AX, phospho-ATM, phospho-p53), the pro-inflammatory response (nuclear translocation of NF- κ B), oxidative stress (DCFDA, Heme oxygenase-1), mitochondrial membrane potential (TMRE) and cell cycle (Ki67, phospho-H3).

Task 2.2. Assessment of virulence and toxin gene expression using RT-PCR and transcriptomic assays

T2.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Nalini Rama-Rao (P18)

Deputy Task Leader: Olivier Firmesse (P1) Task Participants: P1, P18, P19

Description of the task:

The aim of this task is to select genes over or highly expressed in pathogenic strains compared to nonpathogenic ones within a panel of candidate genes suspected to play a role during *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* pathogenesis. Regarding *B. cereus*, differentially expressed genes will be compared between pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains, and presence and expression of *nheA*, *nheB*, *hblL2*, *hblB*, *cytK1*, *cytK2*, *hlyII* and *ces* will be monitored by qPCR and RT-qPCR, respectively, in the strains selected in WP1. For *C. perfringens*, differentially expressed genes will be compared between pathogenic strains from clinical and food origins. The obtained results will make it possible to find correlations and to build a better characterization scheme for strains of *C. perfringens* causing food poisoning. The presence and expression of 17 virulence factors will be monitored by qPCR and RT-qPCR, respectively, in the strains selected in WP1. To gain a general knowledge on gene expression and evaluate the potential of new virulence genes, a whole transcriptomic assay will be performed (RNAseq technology) in various growth conditions, mimicking the intestinal environment and allowing toxins expression. These conditions will be optimized as a preliminary step.

Sub-Task sT2.2.2. development of RT-PCR assays and transcriptomic analysis

sT2.2.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M10

Sub-Task end month: M24

Sub-Task Leader: Nalini Rama-Rao (P18)

Sub-Task Participants: P1, P18, P19

WP3. Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors

WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M30

WP Leader: Mirjana Andjelkovic (P4)

WP participants: P1, P4, P18, P19

Description of the WP:

Background and objectives

The aim of this WP is to ensure the development and/or optimisation of LC-MS/MS methods for detection of bacterial toxins. The main objective is to deliver dedicated methods using different proteomic approaches (bottom-up, top down and targeted quantification) for the detection of toxins of interest. To accept the results in food control purposes it will be necessary to work on the harmonization of the quality criteria. These criteria are well defined in the legal frameworks describing the monitoring and controlling of the food safety. The new proteomic approaches do not have either specific guidelines or standards about the acceptable quality criteria enabling the food safety authorities to make decisions. The outcome of the WP3 should be adoption of the acceptance criteria as decided on the basis of the results obtained from the developed and tested methods. Another aspect that will be elaborated in the WP3 is the sample preparation techniques and optimization of all steps of the workflow (protein extraction, LC separation including column length, type and gradient, MS method). This may be detrimental for the analyses of the toxins in highly different and sometimes highly protein content food matrices.

In particular different mass-spectrometry based proteomics approaches will be used to target Detection of toxins including:

- currently undetectable enterotoxins produced by *S aureus*,
- known toxins from *B cereus* (cereulide),
- known toxins from *C. perfringens* (CPE)

Detection of virulence factors of *B. cereus* in order to distinguish between pathogenic and nonpathogenic strains

Approach

In this WP, two different mass-spectrometry based proteomics approaches will be used to identify and quantify toxins and virulence factors of *S. aureus*, *B. cereus*, and *C. perfringens* and separate pathogenic vs non-pathogenic strains.

- Targeted approach (bottom-up LC-MS/MS) will be undertaken in discovery mode. The objective here is to achieve a comprehensive analysis of the different bacterial proteomes and assess the presence of toxins, virulence factors, as well as protein biomarkers differentiating pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains. The analyses will be performed on state-of-art equipment. The bottom-up approach relies on the analysis of proteins after enzymatic digestion (usually trypsin). Shotgun LC-MS/MS experiments on bacterial samples can lead to the confident identification, in routine, of thousands of proteins.

- Non targeted approach (top-down proteomics) will be used in discovery mode. Top-down proteomics is an emerging technology based on the analysis of intact proteins using high- resolution mass spectrometry. A great advantage of top-down proteomics is its ability to address protein variations and characterize proteoforms arising from alternative splicing, allelic variation, or post-translational modification (PTM). Top-down proteomics provides a bird's eye view of all proteoforms and thus information closely connected to complex disease phenotypes. By studying intact proteins rather than peptides, top-down proteomics also neatly sidesteps the so-called "inference problem" that is inherent in the bottom-up workflow (the same peptide can be shared by several proteins which can lead to ambiguous identification). Recent results obtained by partner P19 (IP MS lab) have shown that top-down proteomics can be used for the discrimination of very closely related species and specific bioinformatics tools have been set-up for data analysis.

Task T3.1: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins from *S. aureus*

T3.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M27

Task Leader: Mirjana Andjelkovic (P4)

Task Participants: P1, P4

Description of the task:

To date, more than 20 *S. aureus* enterotoxins (SEs) or enterotoxin-like proteins (SEIs) have been identified. However, recognised detection methods are available for only a few of them (SEA to SEE), and are limited to ELISA based techniques or confirmation by PCR analyses. Direct link between the toxin concentration present in a sample and its toxic potential is thus interrupted. Therefore, task T3.1 will provide a strategy platform for detection of other enterotoxins and offer possibility to estimate the toxic dose using bottom-up proteomics. Three enterotoxins (SEM, SEN, SEO) were selected according to their estimated high prevalence in staphylococcal food poisoning outbreaks. The major output of the task T3-1 will be the optimisation and assessment of the analytical method for SEM, SEN and SEO enterotoxins for which no commercial tests are yet available.

Task T3.2: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *B. cereus*

T3.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M27

Task Leader: Julia Chamot-Rooke (P19)

Task Participants: P1, P4, P19

Description of the task:

The approach that will be used for detection of *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors will be searched using a combination of bottom-up and top-down proteomics approaches. In this task, the current LC- MS and MALDI-ToF MS methods will be evaluated together with available reference materials and standards, as well as their applicability in the detection purposes. The major answers to be given with the results is how to distinct the pathogenic from non-pathogenic strains in various sample types from *B. cereus* related food intoxications; and at which level these toxins may be detected in the sample. Specific targets starting from our current experience will be the emetic toxin (cereulide) and any possible analogues that would arise from the discovery analyses. We will also try to assess the presence of other toxins such as the major enterotoxins HBL, NHE and T.

Task T3.3: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *C. perfringens*

T3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M27

Task Leader: Michel Hebraud (P18)

Task Participants: P1, P18, P19

Description of the task:

A bottom-up proteomic approach will be performed on state-of-art equipment installed in partner P18). Shotgun LC-MS/MS experiments on bacterial samples can lead to the confident identification, in routine, of thousands of proteins. Specific focus will be done on the *C. perfringens* enterotoxin (CPE) responsible for causing the gastrointestinal symptoms of several nonfood-borne human gastrointestinal diseases.

Task T3.4. Transfer of LC-MS/MS methods

T3.4 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M24

Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Mirjana Andjelkovic (P4)

Task Participants: P1, P4, P18, P19

Description of the task:

C. perfringens food- and The new LC-MS/MS methods developed will be in-house validated. For each analytical method a detailed analytical protocol and validation report will be written. These protocols will include all QA criteria which have to be fulfilled for a sensitive and reliable analysis. Among others, these QA parameters are scope definition, analytical range, chromatographic separation/selectivity, sensitivity - Control of LOD and LOQ, control of the calibration standards and exchange of standard solutions, recovery of the isotopically labelled internal standards (if available), matrix additions experiments at regular intervals, duplo analysis at regular intervals, control of the blank concentrations/ blank samples, quality control during analyses. Once validated the methods will be transferred to the partners of the WP3 in order to test applicability of the methods before further implementation in WP5. As an important step towards harmonisation of technical approaches, performance criteria for those developed analytical techniques will be defined. This will be requirement set up for WP5 participants.

WP4. Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence determinants

WP4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M33

WP Leader: Alexandra Fetsch (P9)

Deputy WP Leader : Michel Gohar (P18)

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P33 Description of the WP:

Background and objectives

The available immune-enzymatic methods do not cover the entire spectrum of SEs as only five SE serotypes (namely SEA, SEB, SEC, SED, and SEE) out of 23 SE types are currently detectable. Moreover, epidemiological data indicate that there is an increase of human cases caused by emerging *S. aureus* strains producing other types of toxins such as SEG, SEH, and SEI. On the other hand, also a variety of *B. cereus* specific toxins currently lack appropriate detection methods hampering valid characterization of the pathogenicity, in particular of diarrheal strains. Therefore, the aim of this WP is to facilitate the investigation of foodborne outbreaks and toxigenic *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* strains by enlarging the scope of already available diagnostic tests.

Approach

We plan to develop (quantitative) immunoassays fit for purpose to detect staphylococcal and *B. cereus* specific virulence factors. More precisely, these assays will cover targets allowing for the detection of at least two SE-types other than SEA-SEE, e.g. SEG, SEH, SEI, SEM, SEN and/or SEO, and for at least three *B. cereus* specific toxins, e.g. Hbl (HblL1, HblL2, HblB), Nhe (NheA, NheB, NheC), CytK2, the phospholipases (PlcA, PlcB, Smase), and/or any new virulence factor or toxin variant specific to diarrheal strains. For *B. cereus*, these assays will be different from the assays commercially available today for Hbl, Nhe and CytK, which do not all allow for their quantification.

Our approach foresees the cloning of the various targeted toxins of interest in expression vectors, their overproduction in *Escherichia coli* and subsequent purification. Polyclonal, and/or (preferably) monoclonal antibodies raised against these toxins will then be selected for their affinity, specificity and compatibility with different food matrices (e.g. milk/milk products, meat/meat products). Moreover, for the development of immunoassays to detect SE we plan to run a 'cell-free' approach in comparison to the 'classical' approach as described before at least for one of the chosen SE types, resp. In this procedure, the constituents of the cell are used to produce a certain target protein. The basic principle of the cell-free reaction is the same. Crude extracts are generated from cultured cells and depleted of endogenous DNA and mRNA, and the lysate is subsequently supplemented with energy components and free amino acids. The translational process is initiated by the addition of a suitable template (linear or circular DNA or mRNA), and carried out at an appropriate temperature for the chosen system. WP4 will operate in close collaboration with WP2 dedicated to the characterization of (i) known virulence factors (e.g. Nhe, Hbl, CytK, SEG, SEH and SEI) and (ii) new virulence determinants highlighted using cytotoxic assays coupled to qRT-PCR and transcriptomic approaches (see WP2). Moreover, the feasibility of the developed assays will be tested in a ring trial between the project partners (see WP5) using artificially and naturally contaminated food or culture supernatants allowing for the immediate set-up in routine analyses.

Task T4.1. Development of quantitative immunoassays for five known *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors

T4.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M32

Task Leader: Alexandra Fetsch (P9)

Deputy Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Task Participants: P9, P18

Description of the task:

2 SE-encoding genes from CPS (e.g. SEG, SEI, she, SEM, SEN and/or SEO) and 3 toxin-encoding genes from *B. cereus* (e.g. Hbl, Nhe, CytK2) will be selected and genetic tools allowing protein overexpression will be constructed. Production of proteins will be performed using (i) a classical approach for chosen SEs from CPS and 3 toxins from *B. cereus*, and (ii) a 'cell-free' approach for 1 SE from CPS. Polyclonal or monoclonal antibodies will be produced and immuno-enzymatic assays will be designed. The results obtained with antibodies derived from classical and cell-free approaches will be compared.

Sub-Task sT4.1.2. Proteins production

sT4.1.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M8

Sub-Task end month: M18

Sub-Task Leader: Alexandra Fetsch (P9)

Sub-Deputy Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Sub-Task Participants: P9, P18

Sub-Task sT4.1.3. Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

sT4.1.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M12

Sub-Task end month: M24

Sub-Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Alexandra Fetsch (P9)

Sub-Task Participants: P9, P18

Sub-Task sT4.1.4. Design of immunoenzymatic assays

Sub-Task sT4.1.4. takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M17

Sub-Task end month: M32

Sub-Task Leader: Alexandra Fetsch (P9)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Task Participants: P9, P18

Task T4.2. Development of a quantitative immunoassay on a new B cereus toxin or virulence factor

Task T4.2. takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP, depending on the outcome of WP2.

Task start month: M18

Task end month: M32

Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Task Participants: P18

Description of the task:

Further to the identification and characterization of new B. cereus candidate virulence factors in WP2 and to NGS in WP1, one of these candidate factors will be selected for the development of a dedicated immuno-enzymatic assay.

Sub-Task sT4.2.1 Construction of a genetic tool for protein overexpression

Sub-Task sT4.2.1. takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M18

Sub-Task end month: M26

Sub-Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Sub-Task Participants: P18

Sub-Task sT4.2.2. Protein production

Sub-Task sT4.2.2. takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task start month: M24

Sub-Task end month: M27

Sub-Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Sub-Task Participants: P18

WP6. Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results

WP6 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M0

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne (P1)

Deputy WP Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P19, P33

Description of the WP:

As described in WP0, the partners will set up a committee, composed of at least one representative from each partner, which will be in charge of evaluating the results, and suggesting appropriate means of protection and valorization of the results. For results concerning fundamental research or

public health, the results are meant to be freely published through both oral presentations and publications in open access journals. If some of the results may constitute an invention which can be protected by a patent application, publication will be delayed until the proper protection is sought. If results might be commercially exploited, the committee will be in charge of suggesting plans for their exploitation (choice of a party in charge of valorization, actions for finding one or several commercial exploitation partners). Exploitation, ruled by a commercial exploitation license, will include a fair financial return for the (co)owners. If an application is predicted, the patents service of the institutions hosting the research teams associated to the discovery will also be consulted, to obtain help with the administrative tasks linked to filing a patent. A consortium agreement will also be prepared by the partners that will detail the rules concerning intellectual property rights, classification of results stemming from the project and their valorization. Partners, through their respective valorization departments, will take appropriate decisions to protect results and to file a patent regarding the developed assays. The scientific and technico-economic outcome of these findings will be assessed by realizing a technico-economic study of the trade environment, of the technological and legal constraints, and of the market expectations. An analysis of the freedom to operate will be performed, in which the filed patent dependence upon patents held by third parties will be examined. Partners will also search for industrial partners, by elaborating and distributing technological offers to targeted private firms. Terms and conditions of the technology transfer (license or license option according to development stage of the invention) will be negotiated with industrial partners. A support group will be organized to follow up the administrative and financial issues of the contractant, and to keep the invention on the forefront of the technology. Results not directly involved in the patent filing will be published in open access peer-reviewed journals and presented in international meetings.

Task T6.1: dissemination of information within the partners.

T6.1. continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M0

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne (P1)

Deputy Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P19)

Task Participants: all participants involved

Description of the task:

Based on the developed methods, an exchange of standard operating procedures and tools will be initiated, wherever possible.

Task T6.2: dissemination of information to the outside.

T6.2. continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M0

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne (P1)

Deputy Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P19)

Task Participants: all participants involved

Description of the task:

Presentation of network activities at international conferences (talks, posters, flyer) and to respective national and international decision makers in different networks and institutions
Publication of results in open access peer-reviewed journals

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D0.2	Intermediate report	M18
D0.3	Report of the meeting 1	M19
D2.1	Report on results from toxicity assays (classical toxicity tests and High Content Analysis)	M24
D2.2	Report on TR-PCR and RNAseq data analysis	M24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
MS2.3	High content analysis methods developed	M18
MS2.4	RNAseq data analysed	M24
MS3.2	Methods developed and assessed	24

2.1.3.1.13 JRP6-NOVA

Set of activity		JRP6/R1/FBZ-1 Improved Surveillance								
Project title		Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain								
Project acronym		NOVA								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P38-SVA			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P13-SSI		
Project Coordinator person name		Jenny Frössling			Project Deputy Leader person name			Steen Ethelberg		
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month				M1			Project End month			M24
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	18.52		16.9						36	16
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M	19			19	19				3.79	2.14
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI
P.M					7	2.5		6		19.7
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M	2.5							2.5	18.5	
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrative research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Evaluation of the effect of different surveillance programs in the food production on human health through mathematical modelling ○ Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses. ○ Developing models to answer questions of cost-efficiency and prioritisation of surveillance ○ Common framework of terms describing foodborne zoonosis surveillance across sectors ○ Descriptive mapping of unused potential food-chain surveillance resources across countries and of impediments towards their use 										

- Use of electronic food purchase data for surveillance
 - Description by member state of food purchase data sources and their availability
 - Structured review of the field of the use of food purchase data for outbreak investigation.
 - Manual of how to use food purchase data for outbreak investigations.
 - Case control studies of food risk factors for sporadic infections of important pathogens using electronic datasets of food purchase data.
 - Analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals in relation to hospitals outbreaks of foodborne zoonotic diseases.
 - Tool for food risk mapping and trace-back as a computer software
- Syndromic surveillance tools
 - Inventory of data availability, quality and suitability
 - Evaluation of statistical syndromic surveillance approaches to detect foodborne diseases outbreaks
 - Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance methods for foodborne diseases surveillance
- Spatial analysis tools
 - Maps of livestock prevalence and geographical patterns of Salmonella transmission in in areas of varying infection intensity
 - Analyses of the spatio-temporal associations with human salmonella cases
 - Geographically aided evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.
 - Assessment of the potential effect of relevant interventions
 - Cartographic map of hot spot areas for Salmonella transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.
 - Potential new environmental surveillance indicators identified.

Description of Work

WPO: Coordination and project management

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy WP Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

WP participants: SVA, SSI, and all other partners

Description of the WP:

WPO continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This WP will be responsible for all reporting to Med-Vet-European joint programme coordinating body and will coordinate 3 annual assemblies during the 3-year project. Because of the large number of partners in the consortium and the need for interaction between WPs, this coordinating WP will play an important role in ensuring that milestones and final deliverables of the consortium are successfully completed and communicated.

The Coordinator at SVA and a deputy project leader at SSI will collaborate in keeping continuous contact between the WPs and secure dissemination of results.

A Project Management Team will be formed including the Coordinator and WP leaders. The project will also have a Steering Committee with one representative per partner. Within NOVA, there will be three annual assemblies, where the Committee will meet.

In addition to these groups, an Advisory Board is planned to include relevant stakeholders, i.e. authorities and institutes (1 representative from CDC, and 1 from EFSA) and the food industry (1 representative). Members for the Advisory Board will be recruited at the start of the project. The

Board will meet with the coordinators through Skype-meetings and will be asked for advice on project directions three times in the project period.

T-0.1 Project management

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Task Participants: SVA, SSI, SCIENSANO, ANSES, INIA, DTU

Description of the task:

T-0.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This task will include communication to all partners about project progress, upcoming deadlines, follow-up of deliverable completion, and reporting of deliverables to the EJP.

A Project Management Team will be formed including the Coordinator and WP leaders. Throughout the project, the group will have regular meetings (quarterly or more often, if needed) to communicate across WPs and ensure that the work flow within and between WP proceed as expected. Staff for administrative support, including financials, will also be included. A common platform will be set up to facilitate sharing of information and documents.

T-0.2 Organise annual assemblies

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M34

Task Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI, and the partner institutes that will host the meetings

Task Participants: SVA, SSI, and hosting partner institute

Description of the task:

T-0.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. During the course of the 36-month project three physical assemblies will be held. The first in Month 2 (October 2017), the second in Month 19 (March 2019), and the third in Month 34 (June 2020). These meetings will be held at 3 different partner institutes that are to be identified prior to the project start. The purpose of these meetings will be to introduce the consortium participants to one another, to discuss how to achieve the defined milestones in the work packages most efficiently, and to present results to the group. In connection to these assemblies, smaller meetings with discussions and planning within WPs will also take place.

T-0.3 Economic reporting and financial management

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Anna Nordenfelt, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Task Participants: All partners

Description of the task:

T-0.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. SVA will coordinate the financial reporting for the project, as well as support the partners in the project with any financial questions or questions regarding procurement of goods and services. This task includes communicating requirements for reporting of person time and ensuring material is correct and sent on to EJP.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month

D-0.2	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M20
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-FBZ1.NOVA.13	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M19
<p>WP1: Food chain surveillance mapping WP start month: M1 WP end month: M36 WP Leader: Maria Eleni Filippitzi, Sciensano Deputy WP Leader: Solveig Jore, NIPH WP participants: SVA, SSI, DTU, ANSES, INIA, NVI, NIPH, RIVM, APHA, BfR, UCM, RKI, FLI, SpFrance, ISS, IZS, PHAS, PHE</p> <p>Description of the WP: WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Effective and cost-efficient surveillance demands an integrated approach across the food chain, harmonised practices and communication among the different stakeholders. For the surveillance of foodborne zoonoses, a common understanding of the surveillance systems in place, their potential gaps, and alternative approaches, is needed. In this context, a common language is one important baseline for surveillance communication; i.e. terminology with Med-Vet joint definitions of phrases used to describe, analyse, and evaluate surveillance. Various methods and tools for collecting information about foodborne pathogens and human health exist or are being developed at national and regional levels. Different stakeholders at different levels of the food chain process reveal different perceptions, needs and priorities. Development and implementation of traditional and new surveillance tools relies on effective communication among the parts involved, an issue particularly important when communication cross-domains is needed. Objective: This WP aims at aligning perceptions and needs along the food chain, and across the Med-Vet domains, in two main ways: by providing a common language for discussion, and by performing a full mapping of the surveillance opportunities and hurdles along these dimensions. The tasks outlined below aim at analysing the different levels of the food chain in order to obtain a comprehensive overview of the different stakeholders involved as well as their terminology perception, needs and priorities. In addition, this WP aims at identifying stakeholders' perceptions on critical gaps and hurdles reducing the cost effectiveness of surveillance (i.e. legal, ethical and technical barriers to data communication). This, in turn, will enable a comprehensive approach to foodborne zoonosis surveillance optimisation. The study may use one specific pathogen as a proof-of-concept for other foodborne pathogens. Parts of the feed-to-fork data chain analysis may be focused in a specific sector (such as poultry, or pork). The pathogen and sectors will be defined in the start of the task, among partners. This WP will mainly be descriptive and will involve all partners. This WP can be partly linked to and will have continuous contact with the other WPs in this project, as well as WPs in some other EJP projects.</p> <p>T-1.1 Definition of a joint food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology Task start month: M1 Task end month: M24 Task Leader: Solveig Jore, NIPH Deputy Task Leader: Estelle Ågren, SVA Task Participants: ALL</p> <p>Description: T-1.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Previous projects within veterinary medicine such as RISKSUR and ICAHS workshops have found important differences between countries in how fundamental surveillance terms are defined. In order to</p>		

communicate, exchange data, and improve surveillance across the entire field of veterinary and human medicine a common language is essential. This task would bring experts from different countries and across the Med-Vet domains together to discuss terminology and definitions. The construction of such a terminology needs to be informed by the surveillance opportunities and needs within partner countries, therefore this WP will also carry out a mapping of activities that can support foodborne surveillance in a framework that aligns med-vet activities. Collaboration with the integrative area projects will be sought to avoid duplication of the work, and maximise resources.

Objective: To provide a common understanding and agreed-upon definition of surveillance terms used within food borne zoonosis surveillance throughout the food chain, i.e. across Med-Vet sectors and countries.

Method: **Terminology** output from the RISKSUR project and ICAHS workshops will be used as the starting point for the animal surveillance part and ECDC terminology used as starting point for the human side, complemented by a broad literature search. These foundations will be built upon through discussions among OH EJP partners in meetings and expert consultations. A smaller group of experts, including both Med and Vet sides, will circulate and agree on the **final list of definitions**, if possible involving also a small group representing similar tasks from other funded EJP projects, in particular those in the integrative topics. Given the work on a Med-Vet glossary of the participants of ORION project WP2 Integration in which members of NOVA project WP1 also participate in the first year, the deliverable of this WP will also be based on the work conducted within the framework of ORION. After collaboration with participants of NOVA WP2-5, any additional terms will be added and defined (e.g. food purchase data).

Outcome: Provide a common glossary of defined terms used in food borne surveillance.

T-1.2 Mapping of surveillance: data, regulatory framework, key stakeholders, opportunities and barriers

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Maria Eleni Filippitzi, Sciensano

Deputy Task Leader: Solveig Jore, NIPH

Task Participants: ALL

Description:

T-1.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Within this task the participating partners will make a detailed overview of available surveillance information sources in the different MS, including both databases and other type of sources. Traditional surveillance data, but also all kind of other potential usable data sources such as registers, surveys, and reports, will be included. Understanding the context and drivers to surveillance is critical for designing successful interventions actions and that these intervention actions will only be effective if key players in the system accept them. In this task, the different surveillance strategies implemented in each MS, and the involved stakeholders, will also be described. This will provide input and support to the other WPs, in particular the simulation of alternative surveillance strategies in WP5. This task will be performed in close collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5

Objective: To find and describe all currently used and unused sources that potentially could be used for improving surveillance, and to investigate stakeholders' perceptions on the obstacles and opportunities for foodborne integrated surveillance associated with these sources.

Method: Again, the work of previous European funded projects will be used as starting point, but here the focus will be on the **potential for synergy** between med and vet with the aim of foodborne surveillance. Group discussions about this topic will be held and documented, some in connection to assemblies where experts are already participating. After **identification of stakeholders** across Member States through an overall **mapping exercise** on selected zoonotic foodborne pathogens (i.e. *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*), potential novel data sources or surveillance gaps will be further

investigated by targeted surveys and/or interviews. Following the overall mapping exercise, each MS will choose a stakeholder to focus on (e.g. herd veterinarian, general practitioner, etc.) and will identify and describe the **surveillance activities** they are involved in. **Questionnaires** addressed to these different stakeholders will be prepared, in order to collect information and identify perceived and documented **opportunities and barriers** for systematic use of each new data source. This will cover availability, cost, technical, legal, economic, socio-political, educational and ethical issues for each involved Member State. When relevant, motivators or incitements for supplying data i.e. feedback information of interest for the data supplier will be examined. Participatory methods will be used to evaluate the functionality and acceptability of surveillance strategies and to determine the main drivers and hurdles for effective surveillance.

Outcome: A comprehensive map describing important components and stakeholders across the food chain representing potential sources for improved surveillance; and an increased knowledge about differences in Member States regarding implementation and execution of surveillance programs concerning food borne zoonoses. A description of identified opportunities and obstacles of each of these sources.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-1.1	Glossary of terms based on a common food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP6-15	Glossary of surveillance terminology for foodborne surveillance is disseminated.	M24

WP2: Analysis of food purchase data

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Deputy WP Leader: Katja Alt, BfR

WP participants: SSI, RKI, BfR, ISS, SpFrance (InVS), PHE, RIVM, SCIENSANO, PHAS, NIPH, NVI, IZS.

Description of the WP

WP2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. In order to understand the transmission of foodborne diseases it's important to understand food exposures. This is done by applying questionnaires for patients and non-ill control subjects, asking them to report food histories. Often, however, such data are heavily biased or incomplete and their collection costly and difficult to obtain in a timely manner. Therefore, ways to obtain data on everything a patient or household consumes during an outbreak period have been pursued for some years, progressing from manual collection of receipts to capture of electronic purchasing data. Also, purchase data from restaurants or caterers for hospitals or other institutions for vulnerable populations can be tracked. Additionally, information obtained from food sales data (big data covering affected regions) and tracing analyses potentially enhance evidence during outbreak investigations. This WP aims to use food consumption patterns as a new digital surveillance tool to aid our understanding of both outbreaks as well as determinants for sporadic foodborne illness.

Objective: This WP will perform research into how surveillance of food consumption patterns can be used to better understand foodborne zoonoses: to aid surveillance, to explore risk factors and for outbreak investigations.

Structure: The WP is divided into five separate, partly interdependent tasks, each containing subtasks.

T-2.1 Data availability and barriers

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M14

Task Leader: Ingrid Friesema, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: Luigi Iannetti, IZS

Task Participants: All partner institutes.

Description of the task:

T-2.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Digitalisation is progressing rapidly, though at different speeds across Europe, and consumer patterns and habits differ between member countries. Some EU countries have several years of experience with use of consumer purchase data for outbreak investigations, whereas others have never used it. Likewise, legal systems and other structures varies across EU member states.

Objective: Subtask 1: Map prior experience, identify purchase data sources and potential coverage, map actors. Subtask 2: Describe major impediments including legal, political, economical, practical and technical obstacles.

Methods: Structured process in which all institutes perform national analyses. Data collection via web-survey questionnaire on data availability and barriers in different countries.

Outcome. Provide basic data availability information. The data obtained will guide other subtasks. Identified impediments & barriers should be used to plan how such can be overcome in the future.

T-2.2 Food purchase data for outbreak investigations

Task start month: M2

Task end month: M34

Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI.

Deputy Task Leader: Uffe Braae, SSI.

Task Participants: SSI, ISS, SpFrance, PHE, BfR, RIVM, SCIENSANO, PHAS, NIPH

Description of the task

T-2.2 continues based upon what was achieved in the first annual period of the EJP, during which published papers making use of consumer purchase data (CPD) used for outbreak investigations was reviewed. This review formed Deliverable D-2.2.1 and was also published in Eurosurveillance. The review showed the method to be quite powerful. It had, however, not been widely used and when so, mostly in an ad hoc manner and the methods not been standardised. We believe a more general use of the method could be obtained if its benefits and limitations be better described and brought forward to OH-EJP partner institutes and epidemiological researchers in the EU. The work will therefore focus on describing a common methodology, which should pave the way for increased use of this potentially powerful tool.

Objective: Subtask 1: Further, identify existing use of CPD for outbreak investigations, including through a survey of EU public health institutes, conducted in cooperation with T-2-1. Subtask 2: Develop Best Practice descriptions for such studies. Subtask 3: Describe potential for use as an analytical tool (rather than simply a hypothesis-generating tool).

T-2.3 Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M34

Task Leader: Frederik Trier Møller, SSI.

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI.

Task Participants: SSI, PHAS, PHE, RIVM, NIPH.

Description of the task:

T-2.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The level of electronic payment of purchases in Denmark is high with more than 80% of transaction being

digital. In Denmark, also experience with epidemiological use of consumer purchase data (CPD) exists and we have therefore chosen Denmark as the scene to further study how CPD may be used for epidemiological studies of foodborne diseases. We wish to make a structured comparison between known cases and non-ill persons for whom we can assess electronic CPD either using large-scale datasets from supermarkets or even prospectively collected case/control CPD. Work done in the first annual period has among others focused on mapping and approaching various private actors within the field and further building a module that can administer invitations and consent-forms for participation in studies.

Objective: Subtask 1: Achieve supermarket CPD to study the ways to structure data on foods and run simulation studies for the risk of outbreak/sporadic foodborne infections. Subtask 2: Build a research infrastructure to achieve consent from sporadic cases of salmonella and campylobacter and healthy controls to use CPD to conduct analytical studies of foods posing a risk for sporadic salmonella and/or campylobacter infections (year 3 included).

Perspective: Depending on results from Denmark, studies can be extended to other countries. Sweden and Norway, where the data accessibility is also maturing rapidly, are good candidates. Also, other pathogens and other study objectives can be envisioned and may be included in this phase.

T-2.4 Food distribution data for hospital outbreaks

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Hendrik Wilking, RKI.

Deputy Task Leader: Sebastian Haller, RKI.

Task Participants: RKI, IZS, ISS.

Description of the task:

T-2.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Hospitalised patients are particularly vulnerable to foodborne infections and timely identification of foodborne outbreak sources is crucial. In Germany, a national surveillance of healthcare associated outbreaks is implemented and several healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks (ha-FBO) were recently reported; caused by agents such as *Salmonella*, *Listeria* and *Klebsiella*, some agents being multidrug resistant. Investigation requires analyses of dozens of menus/items for hundreds of patient and thousands of hospital-patient-days. A better solution lies in quick analyses of electronic data of the hospital in-house catering in hospital information systems. Unfortunately, there are barriers which hinder comprehensive and quick analyses of these data in outbreak settings. There is a need for research – which need to be interdisciplinarily organised.

Objective/Outcome: We aim to develop a systematic approach for ha-FBO analysis of associations with patient meals. Subtask 1: Epidemiological analysis of existing surveillance data regarding ha-FBO. Review of the literature and description of the proportion of ha-FBO on all healthcare associated outbreaks. Subtask 2: Evaluation of the feasibility of investigation via electronic data. If feasible prospective calculation of disease association measures (OR or RR) from data of food consumption histories from food supply data from hospital information system databases in one or more outbreak settings (proof-of-principle). Alternatively retrospective outbreak analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals and evaluation of most likely disease pattern of ha-FBOs. Proposal for an early warning system for ha-FBO inside hospitals. Subtask 3: Discussion with other public health / veterinary health agencies inside NOVA regarding generalization of methods and concepts in other settings and countries to proof external validity. Thereby we will analyse and better understand potential barriers in the field.

T-2.5 Trace back and food risk mapping

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Katja Alt, BfR.
 Deputy Task Leader: Madelaine Norström, NVI.
 Task Participants: BfR, NVI, NIPH, ISS.

Description of the task:

T-2.5 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Published likelihood-based tools have previously been developed at partner institutes (BfR, NVI) that potentially could accelerate the identification of contaminated food products using spatio-temporal distribution of food sales (food risk mapping). We suggest further development of the methods to include time and Global Trade Identification Number (GTIN) in the analysis, to evaluate various aggregation levels before analysis, and to increase robustness in case of inaccurate or missing information. Furthermore, these results will subsequently be integrated into the state of the art tracing tool FoodChain-Lab.

Objective: Subtask 1: Investigate the availability and usefulness of data from WP2, tasks 1-3. If new real data should not be available for the project, the partners will work on data provided for previous studies. Subtask 2: Develop the likelihood method so that it handles data on time together with GTIN. Work out guidance for selection of unit for aggregation of data before analysis, and decide on ways to handle inaccurate and missing information on case purchase patterns and distribution patterns, and others. Subtask 3: Import of available food sales and eventually food purchase data structures into FoodChain-Lab. Implementation of the likelihood method as cloud service, and integration of the results of the likelihood method into the analysis of FoodChain-Lab.

Outcome: Integration of improved tools for food risk mapping into the state-of-the-art tracing tool FoodChain-Lab will allow for open access, cloud based use in the scientific community. Additionally, the structure of the collected sales data will be evaluated for tracing purposes (in alignment with EFSA working group report) and subsequently integrated as import routine into FoodChain-Lab.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-2.1.2	Description by member state of barriers for use: legal, political, economic, practical and technical obstacles.	M22
D-2.4.3	Studies using the German results extended to the partner institutes.	M24

Milestones

M-JRP6-8	Best practice description.	M16
M-JRP6-9	Development of method to handle time and GTIN.	M17
M-JRP6-10	Prospectively calculation of disease association measures and retrospective analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals.	M24

WP3. Syndromic surveillance

WP start month: M1
 WP end month: M36
 WP Leader: Adeline Huneau, ANSES
 Deputy WP Leader: Fernanda Dórea, SVA
 WP participants: ANSES, NIPH, SVA, NVI, SCIENSANO

Description of the WP

WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Syndromic surveillance (SyS) is a relatively recent approach of surveillance used since early 2000s in human health and more recently in animal health (<http://www.syndromicsurveillance.eu/>). It consists in the real-time collection, analysis, interpretation and diffusion of non-specific indicators in order to early detect any change in human or animal health. SyS systems, usually used in complement of traditional public health surveillance systems, are expected to be earlier and more cost effective

than ongoing systems. Nevertheless, due to the use of nonspecific indicators, there is still doubt about the efficiency of the approach and performances of syndromic surveillance have to be evaluated for the monitoring of FBD.

Objective: Assess whether SyS in animal and food sectors could be a valuable add-on to the current or future surveillance of FBD in humans. The expected impacts are a better understanding of the interplay between animal and human health and an improvement of the prediction of human FBD outbreaks.

Structure: The WP has three tasks, where T-3.2 and T-3.3 are dependent from T-3.1.

Task 3.2. Univariate syndromic surveillance development for FBD (and AMR)

Task start month: M11

Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Carole Sala, ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: Petter Hopp, NVI

Task Participants: ANSES, NIPH, SVA, NVI, SCIENSANO

Description:

T-3.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Objective: evaluate statistical approaches and potential of the data sources identified in Task 1 to detect FBD outbreaks using data.

Method: A set of modules/components, representing different statistical methods will be implementing and applied to the relevant data sources identified in Task 1. SyS data will be analysed with a panel of commonly used time series models (GLM, GAM, ARIMA, Holt-Winters...) combined with algorithms for signal detection (use of CI, control charts...). Simulated dataset will be used to complete data sources when needed and, particularly to mimic various outbreak patterns helping in the evaluation of the performance of the SyS in terms of sensitivity, specificity and timeliness. The scoring approach proposed by Dórea *and coll* (2013) on univariate SS data source will be implemented to assess the improvement of the SS performances by combining methods. This will lead to the identification of the relative timeliness/sensitivity/specificity of each of the methods, and whether some methods are more suited for certain outbreak types i.e. large vs small, spatially diffuse versus localised. Human outbreak data will be used to valid results and performances of the approach.

Result: Evaluation of the potential interest of the development of SS for FBD based on real examples

Task 3.3. Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance for FBD

Task start month: M11

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Gry Marysol Grøneng, NIPH

Deputy Task Leader: Fernanda Dórea, SVA

Task Participants: NIPH, SVA, NVI, ANSES, SCIENSANO

Description:

T-3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

Objective: Assess whether the combination of surveillance results from different SyS components could lead to an improvement of the surveillance system for the selected FDB cases study. That is, to investigate how results from different components, developed in Task 2, can support the evidence from the others, and lead to improved decision making. Integration across components is understood here as integration along the disease transmission chain for specific pathogens within humans, within animals, and across the med-vet domains.

Method: Considering the data sharing barrier, the goal will be to combine the evidence from results of independent monitoring of different epidemiological sources of data, with the overall goal of public health protection. By combining the evidence gathered through these punctual monitoring

along the food production chain, we can monitor FBD risk from farm to fork, accumulating evidence at every step. A possible example of case study is the use of the results from veterinary and food monitoring system such as *Campylobacter* detection in broilers and meat, to support results from the human syndromic surveillance system based on primary health consultations for gastrointestinal diseases (Sykdomspulsen) in Norway.

Result: Identify possible methods to improve the global surveillance by integrating and consolidating results from different sources across the med-vet domains. Barriers to achieving this goal will be identified and prioritised.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-3.3	Description of the SS components implemented and guidelines for their use	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP6-14	SS components developed and tested	M22

WP4: Spatial risk mapping

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Ana de la Torre, INIA

Deputy WP Leader: Stefan Widgren, SVA

WP participants: INIA, RIVM, UCM-VISAVET, SSI, SVA, FLI, CODA

Description of the WP:

WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This WP deals with the development of modelling tools for spatial analysis of FBZ and the identification and assessment of new surveillance indicators/risk factors. Spatial epidemiological tools are increasingly being applied for the study of emerging zoonoses, partly because of improving analytical methods and technologies for data capture and management, and partly because the demand for more objective ways of allocating limited resources in the face of the emerging threat posed by these diseases is growing.

Objective: This WP will perform research into how spatial analysis can improve the knowledge on disease behaviour (spatio-temporal patterns) and identify risk factors/indicators for designing efficient risk-based surveillance strategies and favour timely interventions. Following the recommendation of the Special report on eradication, control and monitoring programmes to contain animal diseases (EU, 2016), new indicators related to the environment, including wildlife, will be explored to optimize the effectiveness of surveillance programs.

Scope: The practical approach of this WP will be done using *Salmonella* infection in swine as a proof of concept. *Salmonella* has been selected as example of FBD as it is one of the most common public health problems, causing significant human morbidity and even mortality and consequently high economic losses in both developing and developed countries. Foods of animal origin are still one of the major sources of infection for the general public, with eggs, broiler chickens and pigs being consistently identified among the top attributed food sources. Whereas control programmes for *Salmonella* in poultry have been applied in the whole UE with high success, only few European countries have implemented eradication or control programmes of *Salmonella* in swine, beef, or dairy production. Results from efforts made in Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Norway, Ireland, Germany, Great Britain and Holland, are somewhat inconsistent. So far, there are no national control programmes established in any Mediterranean country, where >40% of the pig farms were positive to *Salmonella* (EFSA baseline study, 2009). In consequence, further efforts to implement control programs for reduction of the prevalence of *Salmonella* infection in swine in the near future

are envisioned. Prerequisites to the implementation of such an approach; scientific efforts directed to improve our preparedness and develop an effective risk-based surveillance system should be carried out. Results from this WP would also be relevant for surveillance of many other FBZ diseases, as the explored risk mapping techniques and developed tools will be generic.

Structure: The WP is divided into 3 tasks. Task 4.1 deals with disease behaviour to identify spatial relationships and patterns in *Salmonella* prevalence in livestock, slaughterhouses and its association with human cases; Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 deals with the identification of new risk factors, namely animal feed (Task 4.2) and wildlife and the environment (Task 4.3).

Links with other WP: The current *Salmonella* surveillance programmes compiled under WP1 will be reviewed to identify the main requirements for applying risk mapping techniques. Data on *Salmonella* prevalence in livestock and human will be explored through the source data explored in WP3. Usefulness of the risk mapping tools developed and new risk factors identified will be evaluated in close collaboration with WP5, where alternative surveillance approaches will be tested. Results applicability: The spatio-temporal patterns of disease occurrence in livestock and human would allow finding an optimized strategy for each epidemiological scenario, e.g. by identifying high risk administrative areas to focus resources for prevention and control of diseases. The identification of new surveillance indicators will allow designing more cost-effective surveillance and control strategies as recommended in the special report on eradication, control and monitoring programmes to contain animal diseases (EU, 2016). Finally, the cartographic map of hot spot areas for *Salmonella* will improve disease awareness in pig producers and hunters, and development of contingency plans and control strategies in EU member states with low biosecurity farms.

All the information generated will be available at the Internet as interactive high resolutions maps, graphs and visual information. As such it will improve the technology transference of on-going research effort and help educators, veterinarians, technicians and policy makers to better understand, evaluate and fight FBD.

T-4.1. Identification of spatial relationships and patterns in *Salmonella* prevalence

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: SVA

Deputy Task Leader: INIA

Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET, SSI, SVA, SCIENSANO

Description of the task:

T-4.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The aim of this task is to understand the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in livestock and slaughterhouses and its association with human cases to optimize sampling strategies and the implementation of risk based surveillance strategies. It will be investigated under two different conditions: low prevalence regions (Subtask 1), medium prevalence regions (Subtask 2) and high prevalence regions (Subtask 3).

Objective: Identify the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution and map their incidence at the administrative level to reduce the prevalence or to detect introduction and changes in prevalence.

Since large differences in the epidemiological determinants of *Salmonella* infection may be expected depending on the setting, two scenarios (high and low prevalence) will be analysed. Spain will be selected as a working example of high prevalence regions as this Mediterranean country is one of the EU's biggest pig producers (ranking first in 2015) and recorded the highest *Salmonella* prevalence in this host (64% of the farms) within the EU according to EFSA (2009). Sweden will be

selected as a working example of low prevalence regions in cattle (prevalence of 1.8%, EFSA, 2009). Denmark will be used for human association studies.

Methods: Sub-Task 4.1.1: Intensive pig farm location, industry surveys (slaughterhouse and feed co-operatives) and human cases will be investigated in conjunction with routinely recorded surveillance information using spatial techniques (e.g. smoothing technique, cluster analyses) [M1-M12]. Geographical areas (broad spatial trend and local spatial correlation) and periods with higher probability of detection of infection will be identified by temporal and spatial autocorrelation analyses, which will allow reallocating efforts on sampling strategies. In addition, temporal trends on serotype distribution and antimicrobial resistance profiles in isolates from clinical human cases and those found in swine will be compared [M13-M24]. Sub-Task 4.1.2: A detailed model of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics will be applied based on data-driven simulations incorporating the complete population demographic, the time-varying contact animal network and the local spread among proximal holdings (Bauer 2016, Widgren 2016a, Widgren 2016b). The model parameters will be calibrated against observed data from historical and ongoing monitoring [M1-M12]. Optimal surveillance strategies will be explored to detect introduction and an increasing prevalence [M13-M24]. For the study of direct risks for human salmonellosis, Danish data will be used. Denmark has a high number of pig holdings and unique geographical registers. Thus x-y-coordinates will be available for the addresses of pig farms, human salmonellosis patients and, in fact, the entire Danish human population. Therefore, the risk of geographical distance of living near farms can be directly analysed using geographical modelling.

Sub-Task 4.1.1: Surveillance in high prevalence regions to detect introduction and changes in prevalence.

Sub-Task start month: M1

Sub-Task end month: M24

Sub-Task Leader: UCM-VISAVET

Sub-Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET.

Sub-Task 4.1.2: Surveillance in low prevalence regions to reduce prevalence.

Sub-Task start month: M1

Sub-Task end month: M24

Sub-Task Leader: SVA

Sub-Task Participants: SVA, SSI

Outcome: Identify geographical pattern in *Salmonella* incidence in cattle farms and slaughterhouses by choroplethic maps and evidences for an association between the temporal pattern of human cases with trends observed in the cattle reservoir.

Task 4.2. Risk of introduction of *Salmonella* in pig farms through animal feed.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: UCM-VISAVET

Deputy Task Leader: INIA

Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET, SCIENSANO

Description of the task

T-4.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. *Salmonella* present in animal feed is a significant source of infection in pigs. In order to develop systems for its inclusion in risk assessment/mapping, feeding flows for some of the largest swine systems in high prevalence regions will be described and mapped.

Objective: The aim of this task is to assess the risk of *Salmonella* introduction in pig farms through contaminated animal feed.

Methods: The spatial network structure (feed plants-swine farms) will be explored by spatial analysis techniques (e.g. spatial modelling, network analyses) [M1-M12]. Data on prevalence of *Salmonella* infection, and serotypes and antimicrobial resistance patterns in intensively managed pig farms will be explored in combination with information on animal feed data to analyse the importance of unsterilized animal feed in the introduction of *Salmonella* in the farms and to improve zoonotic hazard management in the pork food chain [M13-M24]. Using this model, the potential effect of changes in feed management (such as the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments, the most common alternatives to provide an effective antimicrobial control and whose use is controversial due to its risk for workers) will be explicitly considered and evaluated [M25-M36].

Outcome: Characterize the feeding flows for large swine systems in a high prevalence regions using sociograms. Assess the potential effect of changes in feed conservation treatments (i.e., withdrawal of formaldehyde-based feed treatments).

Task 4.3. Role of the environment in the occurrence and maintenance of *Salmonella* infection in extensive farming.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: INIA

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET, RIVM, FLI, SCIENSANO

Description of the task

T-4.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Wildlife often serves as a reservoir for (re-)emerging zoonoses. Infection of wildlife or vectors is frequently linked to environmental and climatic conditions, which largely take place outside the field of view of medical and veterinary experts and affect transmission in a complex manner. This lack of insight in the mechanisms that drive the occurrence and spread of wildlife zoonoses hinders appropriate risk assessment and the development of interventions to reduce public health risks, particularly in a changing environment.

Objective: The aim of this task is to investigate the overlap between habitats of suitable wildlife, e.g. wild boar, with primary production and other environmental variables, which may influence transmission of pathogens from wildlife to livestock farming. *Salmonella* transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems such as extensive farming-oriented systems or backyard farms will be selected as a working example. It will be studied in selected Mediterranean countries, e.g. Spain, where this type of non-controlled housing is present and there is a high prevalence of infection in livestock.

Methods: First, available data on infection and serotype prevalence in extensively managed pig farms (WP3) will be mapped and analysed to characterize its spatial distribution and identify patterns, processes, and relationships (e.g. smoothing technique, cluster analyses) [M1-M12]. Second, hot spot areas with higher potential for *Salmonella* transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems will be identified by overlapping wild boar distribution maps (Bosch et al., 2016), extensive farming systems geodata and known serotype spatial distribution (spatial autocorrelation analyses) [M13-M24]. Finally, state-of-the art machine learning algorithms will be

employed to correlate infection data with environmental drivers. They will be spatially explored and analysed through Bayesian classical and stochastic modelling approaches (correlating covariates, expert opinion, mapping techniques....) to assess their availability/competence as surveillance indicators [M25-M36]. Reliable data of paramount importance will be gathered from free sources such as 'worldclim' (climate), 'CORINE' (land-use) and 'MODIS' (satellite imagery). The model will be an extension of a previously developed model, which was successfully used for tick presence forecasting.

Outcome: A high-quality cartographic map of hot spot areas will be developed that would help to understand and visualize risk scenarios to make decisions based on the best available information. This tool could also be potentially used for implementing the surveillance systems of other FBZ diseases shared between wild boar and domestic pigs, as trichinellosis. Identification of potential new surveillance indicators will be shared with WP5, where alternative surveillance approaches will be tested.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-4.2.	Identification of periods with higher probability of detection of infection identified in high prevalence regions and temporal evidences for an association with human cases	M24
D-JRP6-4.4.	Evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.	M24
D-JRP6-4.5.	Characterization of the spatial network structure of the pig industry in a Mediterranean scenario and <i>Salmonella</i> data mapped and analysed.	M24
D-JRP6-4.8.	Cartographic map of hot spot areas for <i>Salmonella</i> transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP6-16	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in high prevalence regions and evidences for an association between them.	M24
M-JRP6-17	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in low prevalence regions and evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.	M24
M-JRP6-18	Result reporting on hot spot areas for <i>Salmonella</i> transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.	M24

WP5: Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Håkan Vigre, DTU

Deputy WP-leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

WP Participants: DTU, SVA, APHA, RIVM, ANSES, SCIENSANO, FLI

Description of the WP

WP5 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP.

To support the identification and prioritization of control measures in food production, mathematical models have become an important tool as they help a risk manager to predict the effect of different intervention strategies. Thus far, different mathematical frameworks have been

developed for i) estimating the occurrence of pathogens in the food chain e.g QMRA), ii) develop probability theorems around sampling and detection of pathogens, iii) estimate the importance of different sources for human disease (source attribution) and iv) estimate the consequence of different diseases (burden of disease).

The overall objective of this WP is to develop modelling approaches to predict the impact of surveillance programs applied in the food production chain on human exposure and public health. Initially, all models will be developed using case-studies focusing on specific pathogen-food combinations that are of primary importance to the public health within the EU. Each case study will utilise nation and region specific data within the farm to fork approach (e.g. population structure in animal production systems, prevalence and concentration of pathogens in animals or specific food products, consumption patterns and food handling by consumers). These will then be used to develop a framework that can be applied to other pathogens and food items. The output will be a modelling-tool that will form the scientific basis for the design of surveillance programs across Europe, which will enhance the comparability of surveillance data between countries.

The novelty in this WP is that it will combine and further develop currently segregated mathematical frameworks to model the efficiency of different surveillance programs in a human health and cost efficiency context. This approach will advance the focus on human health impact when developing surveillance programs in food production, thereby optimizing decisions about how to distribute limited capacity for surveillance.

T-5.1: Adapt infectious disease models for assessing the effect of surveillance programs in primary animal production on consumer exposure to foodborne pathogens.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Mark Arnold APHA

Deputy Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal, SVA

Task Participants: APHA, DTU, SVA, SCIENSANO

Description of the task

T-5.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. In this task we will adapt existing risk assessment models for foodborne zoonotic pathogens to include modules for simulating the effect of surveillance programs (detection and control) in the food-chain on human exposure to zoonotic pathogens.

sT-5.1.1

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Arnold, APHA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, SVA, DTU

For several foodborne zoonoses, the difficulty of detection is compounded by the lack of clinical signs in the animals. Therefore, improved surveillance measures are required to detect infected animals, and thus limit the exposure of humans to contaminated products by prevention of further spread in the animal population, and/or withdrawal of products from the market. The objective of this task will be to adapt existing models for the transmission of Salmonella in pigs in GB (APHA), in cattle in SWE (SVA) and in eggs in DK (DTU) to (i) take into account the effect surveillance activities on consumer exposure to Salmonella and (ii) if applicable, adapt the models to represent additional pathogens.

sT-5.1.2

Sub-Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal, SVA

Sub-Task Participants: SVA, SCIENSANO.

The surveillance layer of existing models describing spread of a food-borne zoonosis in an animal population will be adapted to generate different global metrics of performance. These will include: time to detection, extent of an outbreak, spread at the time of detection and animal population strata affected. Other surveillance metrics will also be explored to find those that are most

descriptive in situations of endemic disease, freedom from disease and low prevalence disease states. These metrics will be used to assess different surveillance strategies and their capacity to minimize the exposure of foodborne pathogens among the citizens in a country or region in case of an outbreak or change in prevalence of disease in the animal population.

T-5.2 Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses.

Task start month: M7

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Håkan Vigre DTU

Deputy Task Leader: Ofosuhene Okofrobour Apenteng, DTU

Task Participants: DTU

Description

T-5.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Today, emerge of emerging zoonoses is often detected by human cases (public health surveillance data). Genome sequencing provides the potential to generate the “full” information of known and unknown pathogens within samples in surveillance programs (metagenomics). The use of metagenomics at initial stages in the farm-to-consumer chain might improve the likelihood (sensitivity) to detect an emerging pathogen before detection of human cases. In this task, we will further expand existing models describing spread of emerging zoonoses in immunological naïve animal population into two parts: one part to estimate the performance of metagenomics to detect emerging pathogens in the food-chain, and the other part to estimate the performance of detecting human cases. The structure of the model will allow for assessment and comparison of the performance of very different surveillance strategies, and estimation of the necessary “size” of surveillance early in the food-chain compared to surveillance based on human cases.

A mathematical model that can simulate the public health effects of very different surveillance strategies used in the same population.

A model structure that allows for assessment and comparison of the performance of very different surveillance strategies to improve the public in a population, and estimation of the necessary “size” of surveillance early in the food-chain compared to surveillance based on human cases.

T-5.3 Modelling the effect of surveillance programs in the food production on human health.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M36

Task Leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: DBD

Task Participants: RIVM, APHA, DTU, SVA, SCIENSANO, FLI, ANSES

Description of the task

T-5.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. We will broaden the assessment of surveillance from one specific pathogen-food combination at a specific stage in the food chain to surveillance of different pathogens in several food production chains simultaneously up until the moment of consumption. Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) will be used as a consistent measure for the subsequent public health risk. Accounting for mortality, severity and duration of a disease in a single method is a powerful tool to compare the actual health impact of a given intervention in the surveillance of different zoonoses.

sT-5.3.1.

Sub-Task Leader: Håkan Vigre, DTU

Sub-Task Participants: DTU, ANSES, RIVM, FLI

In this subtask we will develop a model consisting of parallel parts for surveillance of a pathogen in several sources based on the cases studies in sT-5.1.1 (Salmonella in egg, pork, poultry and beef).

The objective is to combine the effect on human health based on individual surveillance programs

into an overall effect on human health when different programs are combined. Connecting surveillance in several sources allows the simulation of changing the distribution of surveillance capacity across sources. This modelling approach will consider countries having several sources for a zoonotic infection (e.g. *Salmonella* in pork from Denmark is one source and *Salmonella* in pork from France is another source, and so on). By parameterising each country-specific model by country-specific data and weighting the contribution from each country by import/export data, this approach can support the prioritisation of surveillance across European countries.

sT-5.3.2

Sub-Task Leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

Sub-Task Participants: RIVM, DTU, SVA, FLI, ANSES, SCIENSANO, APHA

In this subtask we will develop a modelling approach for optimizing the distribution of sampling capacity of different food safety authorities in the EU over products in retail according to their contribution to the microbiological public health risk in a most cost-efficient way. DALYs will be used as a consistent measure for the public health risk of different food pathogens over Europe. Exposure assessment (including consumption data and food preparation at home) from St-5.3.1 will be combined with DALYs and a monitoring budget to define an optimising criteria for risk based sampling. The method has already been implemented in The Netherlands for *Campylobacter* in pork and poultry, *Salmonella* and *Toxoplasma gondii* in pork, Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* and ESBL *E. coli* in beef. In this subtask we will improve the current methodology through the contribution of other data sources as identified in this project (e.g. retail purchase data following the EFSA zoonoses report) and other methods for surveillance.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-5.3	An assessment of the public health effects of very different surveillance strategies to detect emerging foodborne infections in a MS or at European level.	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP6-11	complete specification of the infectious disease models	M24
M-JRP6-12	Submodels to be integrated in the model framework identified	M24
M-JRP6-19	The model parts to detect emerging pathogens in the food-chain and detecting human cases, respectively implemented in the model.	M24
M-JRP6-20	Interim report for a practical risk based sampling approach that combines exposure to zoonoses with disease burden and costs for sampling at a European level.	M24

2.1.3.1.14 JRP7-LISTADAPT

Set of activity		JRP7/R1/FBZ-2 NGS-based methods								
Project title		Adaptive traits of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> to its diverse ecological niches								
Project acronym		LISTADAPT								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P01-ANSES			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P33-NVI		
Project Coordinator person name		L. Guillier			Project Deputy Leader person name			T. Skjerdal		
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month				01/18			Project End month			12/2019
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agès	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	51.58	6.5				8.0				12.5
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	JP	APHA	PHE
P.M							27.0			
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M						20.0				
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
P.M	10								0.5	
Objectives										
<p>WPO (coordination), WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 are involved in year 2 of LISTADAPT project. The objectives related to each of these WPs are described here.</p> <p>WP2 aims to :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purify DNA from 2000 <i>Lm</i> strains including (i) strains already available within the consortium (WP1 T1.1) and (ii) strains collected by external partners and on field (WP1 T1.2) (Task 2.1). • Sequence the 2000 strains (Task 2.2). • Assembly and annotate the 2000 genomes obtained (Task 2.3). 										

WP3 aims to :

- Screened and phenotypically characterize this panel:
 - Test effects of biocides on *Lm* strains adaptation (T3.2)
 - Investigate bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of *Lm* strains (T3.3)
 - Investigate survival and persistence of *Lm* strains in different ecological niches (T3.4)

WP 4 aims to:

- Analyze the distribution / prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs for all the strains available (T4.1)
- Conduct a literature search for genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for adaptation, survival and virulence (T4.2)
- Conduct biostatistics analysis of 4000 genomes: 2000 obtained in this project compared with additionally 2000 genomes presently available from food, food processing plants, and clinical cases (T4.3).
- Uncover new genes or new mechanisms related to virulence of clinical human and animal strains (T4.3).
- Determine which genes or lack of genes involved in the strain ecophysiology that results in some clonal complexes being successful in a given environment i.e. humans, food matrixes, storage and unsuccessful in another in terms of adaptation (T4.3, T4.4).
- Compare genotypical data with phenotypical data to identify new determinants or genetic markers needed for improving surveillance for prevention and control (T4.4).

WP5 aims to :

- Share information and knowledge between “Listdapat” partners on methodologies and tools developed and implemented in the project (T5.1)
- Train “Listdapat” partners to use WGS according to harmonized protocols, workflows and analytical tools (T5.2)
- Set up appropriate quality standards and WGS Proficiency Testing Trials, in close collaboration with Compare (WP 2) and the Global Microbial Identifier (GMI) (T5.3)
- Communicate and inform the scientific community about “Listadapt” progress and results obtained (T5.4).

Description of work

WP 0 : Coordination

WPO takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. WPO continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month : M1

WP end month : M24

WP Leader : ANSES (L Guillier)

WP participants: All : DTU, ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the WP :

The coordinator will invest a large amount of time in the Listadapt project. He will maintain regular contacts between the 8 different partners and will be responsible for the efficient progress of the project. He will make sure that all deliverables and milestones are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project. He will organize interactions between groups, and meetings every six months (one face-to face meeting and one telephonic conference) to continuously monitor progress of the objectives and to discuss scientific advances and problems. The coordinator will take advantage of the venue of 6 NRLs involved in “Listadapt” at the annual EURL /NRL workshops

dedicated to *Listeria* and located at ANSES Maisons-Alfort to organize the annual face-to face “Listadapt” meetings.

Each partner will provide the coordinator with scientific and financial statements, from which the coordinator will prepare the reports (cost details, research results and technical advancements). Any problem related to the financial management of the project will be discussed.

WP 2: Whole genome sequencing of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

WP2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. WP2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month : M2

WP end month : M16

WP Leader: IZSAM (Cesare Camma)

Deputy WP Leader: ANSES (Yannick Blanchard)

WP participants: DTU, ANSES, AGES, IZSAM

Description of the WP:

AGES, DTU, ANSES and IZSAM have access to high-through-put next generation sequencing platforms. Given the high number of isolates in this project, however, it will be more cost-effective to outsource the sequencing to Oxford (Wellcome Trust, UK). The facilities, however at the partners of the consortium will be used if convenient for sequencing a minor subset of isolates and of routine sequencing of *Lm* in relation to national surveillance systems.

ANSES (NGS platform) will purify the DNA of the 2000 *Lm* strains selected in WP1 and centralized at ANSES (Maisons-Alfort) (T1.3). The consortium partners, AGES, DTU and IZSAM, will purify the DNA of *Lm* from national surveillance systems to be included in the overall collection of the 2000 *Lm*. (T.2.1.2). Subsequently, the whole genome sequencing of the purified DNA from ANSES will be outsourced due to cost-effectiveness by to Oxford (Wellcome Trust, UK) (T2. 2.1) whereas consortium partners, AGES, DTU and IZS, will sequence a minor subset of routine surveillance strains intended for also this project to be sequenced in real time on in house sequencing platforms (T.2.2.2). In task T.2.3, the genomes produced will be assembled and annotated using bioinformatics tools and software decided at a later stage.

WP2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP.

Sub-Task T2.1.2 Second batch Purification of DNA from additional Lm strains

Sub-Task start month: M13

Sub-Task end month: M14

Sub-Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: IZSAM

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES

Sub task 2.1.2: the *Lm* strains identified in deliverable D1.3 of WP1 will be collected for automated DNA extractions by ANSES genomic platform to prepare the second batch of sequencing.

Task T-2.2: Whole Genome Sequencing

Task start month: M3

Task end month: M14

Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: DTU

Task Participants: ANSES, IZS, DTU, AGES

Description of the task:

The whole genome sequencing of the purified DNA of 2000 strains will be outsourced due to cost-effectiveness to Oxford (Wellcome Trust, UK) (T2.2.1). A minor subset of the strains originate from consortium partner surveillance systems and will be sequenced by partners in real time using in house sequencing platforms (T2.2.2).

Sub-Task T 2.2.2. Second batch Whole genome sequencing for additional Lm stains

Sub-Task start month: M13

Sub-Task end month: M14

Sub-Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Sub-Task Leader:

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES

The number of sequenced *Lm* strain will be completed by a second batch of sequencing for the additional *Lm* strain collected during Task 1.2. 2 of the project

Sub-Task T2.2.3 Ad hoc Whole genome sequencing

Sub-Task start month: M3

Sub-Task end month: M14

Sub-Task Leader: IZSAM

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: DTU

Sub-Task Participants: IZSAM, DTU, AGES

Collection of sequenced *Lm* strains will be completed by the task participants in case the total amount of sequenced strain available at the end of the task T2.2.2 did not reach the number of *Lm* genomes expected for the project.

Task 2.3 Genome Assembling and Annotation

Task start month: M5

Task end month: M16

Task Leader: IZSAM

Deputy Task Leader: ANSES

Task Participants: ANSES, IZS, DTU, AGES

Description of the task:

The objective of T2.3 is to do:

- Assembly of raw data from WGS obtained from the first and the second batch of strains
- Annotation of the assembled genomes of the first batch (D-2.2) and the second batch (D-2.3) *Lm* using bioinformatics tools used by the partners
- Annotation of the assembled genomes produced with Ad hoc WGS (D-2.4).

The reads obtained by WGS will be submitted to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and a shared pipeline for quality control and trimming of raw data (from different platforms) will be established among partners, together with a shared assembly pipeline mainly based on best performing software in use by them (most suitable candidate could be SPADES followed by scaffolding and finishing tools). Similarly, for the annotation pipeline, one or more software will be used.

Bioinformatics pipelines could be shared through a secured protocol and approved by participants, into a single Galaxy instance hosted by one partner and shared. All data and pipelines will be stored together, backed up and easily shared. Moreover, changes in any of the bioinformatics stages or analysis packages developed in the subtask WP4.3 can be easily applied to all samples.

WP3. Phenotypic characterisation of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

WP3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M16

WP Leader: ANSES (Christophe Soumet)

Deputy WP Leader: INRA (Michel Hebraud)

WP participants: NVI, INRA, ANSES

Description of the WP:

Such phenotypic data will participate in connection to genomic analyses to the identification of genetic determinants involved in the adaptation of *L. monocytogenes* to the various considered ecosystems (food, human, animal and environment). In particular, differences and similarities within genetic clusters and the strain reservoirs will be considered.

WP3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP.

Task 3.2. The effects of biocides on *Listeria monocytogenes* strains adaptation

T3.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M3

Task end month: M16

Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: NVI

Participants: INRA

Description of the task:

Ability of some *Listeria monocytogenes* strains to adapt to biocides will be evaluated in both planktonic and biofilm growth mode. Strain selection will be made to represent the diversity of resistance phenotypes identified in previous task of the WP3 and on the basis of genomic analyses in WP2.

Sub-task 3.2.1 Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of Listeria monocytogenes strains

Sub-task start month: M3

Sub-task end month: M16

Sub-task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Sub-task Leader: INRA

Sub-task Participants: NVI

Description of the task:

Profiles of resistance to antibiotics and biocides will be investigated for 200 *Listeria monocytogenes* strains through the determination of Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) to a series of representative antibiotics (~10) and biocides (5-8) using a standard broth dilution method.

Sub task 3.2.2: Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant Listeria monocytogenes strains

Sub task start month: M12

Sub task end month: M16

Sub task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Sub-task Leader: INRA

Participants : NVI

Description of the sub-task:

The ability to adapt to biocides for some *L. monocytogenes* strains was evaluated. Bacteria will be daily repetitively exposed to sublethal concentrations of biocide using suspension tests. At least two biocidal active substances commonly found in industrial biocides formulations will be tested: a quaternary ammonium and an oxidizing agent. The impact of this adaptation on antimicrobial resistance profiles will be evaluated by measuring MIC to biocides and antibiotics. Comparison of MIC between strains of *Listeria monocytogenes* adapted to biocides and those not exposed will enable to characterise the evolution of susceptibility to biocide and the development of cross-resistance to antibiotics.

Sub task 3.2.3: The effect of biocides on *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in biofilm

Sub task start month: M12

Sub task end month: M16

Sub task Leader: NVI

Deputy Sub-task Leader: INRA

Participants : ANSES

Description of the sub-task:

The biofilm lifestyle enhances the bacteria's phenotypic tolerance to external stress, including biocides. Repeated treatments of bacteria in biofilm with biocides may thus stimulate surviving bacteria which in the biofilm to develop genetic resistance to the biocide. The effect of various biocides on the *L. monocytogenes* strains in biofilm will be studied by the Biofilm-Oriented Antiseptics Test (BOAT) measuring the metabolic activity as indicated by reduction of tetrazolium chloride, and the Bactericidal Biofilm Test. Results will be confirmed by Confocal light scanning microscopy.

Task 3.3 Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

T3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M3

Task end month: M16

Task Leader: INRA

Deputy Task Leader: NVI

Task Participants: ANSES

Description of the task:

Biofilm formation will be investigated by discriminating early and late stages of biofilm development in microtiter plates. Early stage of biofilm formation will be investigated using the Biofilm Ring Test (Chavant *et al.*, 2007), whereas late stage of biofilm formation will be investigated using the crystal violet staining method. These complementary techniques will allow estimating the adhesion and sessile development abilities of the *L. monocytogenes* strains. Furthermore, the strains' abilities to form biofilm under different environmental conditions, e.g. temperature, nutrient availability and osmotic pressure will also be studied, as well as the effect of various surfaces.

The biofilm forming abilities of the biocide resistant strains developed in Task 3.5 will also be tested.

Task 3.4 Survival and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in different ecological niches

T3.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M3

Task end month: M16

Task Leader: NVI

Deputy Task Leader: INRA

Description of the task:

Bacteria can establish in new ecological niches due to selection or adaptation. In this task, the isolates ability to survive and grow under conditions that are typical for ecological niches will also be investigated.

Sub task 3.4.1: Survival of *L. monocytogenes* in food products and gastro-intestinal environment

Sub task start month: M3

Sub task end month: M16

Sub task Leader: NVI

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: INRA

Description of the sub-task:

The 200 isolates will be tested for different parameters, in order to 1) assess how well the isolates are adapted to the niche they were isolated from, and 2) search for similarities and differences between strains in the same genetic clones.

The selected conditions are:

- Food: Growth potential at cold storage temperature and presence of common preservatives like lactate and acetate. The studies will be done in broth with conditions similar to meat products.
- Animals and humans: Survival in synthetic stomach acid at 37°C.

Food production environment will not be considered in this task as biofilm formation is supposed to be most important for persistence in this niche.

Sub task 3.4.2: Survival of *L. monocytogenes* in soil microcosm

Sub task start month: M3

Sub task end month: M16

Sub task Leader: INRA

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: NVI

Description of the sub-task:

The ability to survive and/or invade soil habitats and/or grass at representative outdoor temperatures will be additionally investigated in soil microcosms. The selected isolates will be inoculated individually in microcosms prepared with one soil sampled in a cultured field. Soil will be sampled once and aliquoted in 50 ml plastic vials. All microcosms will be stored at -20°C until required. Thawed microcosms will be inoculated with 10⁶ cfu/g and the fate of the population of *L. monocytogenes* will be followed over 15 days.

WP 4 : Identification of genetic traits in *Listeria monocytogenes* underlying adaptation to the ecological niches

WP4 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. WP4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month : M1

WP end month : M22

WP Leader : DTU (René Hendriksen)

WP deputy leader : NVI (Karin Lagesen)

WP participants : ANSES, DTU, NVI, AGES, IZSAM, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the WP:

Task 4. 1. Analyze the distribution / prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs

Task 4.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M14

Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: INRA

Task participants: ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the task:

As explained in WP 1, the consortium is able to provide a collection of 9000 strains of which 2000 strains are already whole sequenced (WP1, Table1). All the additional strains collected in WP1 (T1.2) will be sequenced in WP2. MLST data will be extracted automatically from *de-novo* assemblies using BIGSdb (<http://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/listeria/listeria.html>). PFGE data is available for the majority of remaining strains. Out of strains already available in the consortium collection, PFGE profiles will be centralized in the molecular database set up from the beginning of "Listadapt" (WP1 T1.1). We will use the mapping developed in a previous Anses/DTU research project (Henri et al., 2016), that identifies matches between Clonal Complexes, Sequence Type and PFGE types and aids in the assignment of strains to clonal complexes.

For all the strains, we will analyze the prevalence and the distribution of CC among the reservoirs. By using original statistical analysis (AMOVA, Gini coefficient...), we expect to identify the CCs with unbalanced distribution between the reservoirs and those with equal distribution. We aim to obtain possible associations between clonal complexes and reservoirs, in relation to the geographic diversity. In particular, we will focus on distribution of hypervirulent clonal complexes, as defined in Maury et al (2016) within environment and animals compartments.

Task 4.2: Literature search of genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for virulence, adaptation and survival

Task 4.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month :M9

Task end month : M12

Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: INRA

Task Participants: All : ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the task:

We will do a literature search for genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for virulence adaptation, and survival. In particular, we will focus on significant genes related to (i) biofilm formation (exopolysaccharides – Quorum sensing – Cell wall dynamic), (ii) disinfectant and antibiotic resistance genes. We will classify the genes according to :

Description of gene,

family, function, putative function

Gene location

Silent or coding mutation

Description of gene, family, function, putative function

Chromosome or plasmid loci

Within gene operon

Inter-genic location

Gene promoter
RNA features
Non coding RNA

Task4.3.: Biostatistic analysis of annotated genomes

Task 4.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month :M6
Task end month : M21
Task Leader: NVI
Deputy Task Leader: DTU
Task Participants: ANSES, AGES, IZSAM

Description of the task :

This task focuses on the differences between the 2000 genomes obtained in WP2 with the additional 2000 genomes presently available within the consortium. This could be *via* statistical approaches based on the bioinformatic analysis and also metadata associated with the samples

We would like (i) to determine which genes or lack of genes that make some clonal complexes successful in a given reservoir but unsuccessful in another (ii) uncover new genes or new mechanisms involved in the strain ecophysiology and in the virulence of clinical human and animal strains. Of particular interest are genetic factors relating to virulence, survival, colonization, persistence, adaptation. For practical considerations, this task is divided into two subtasks:

Sub-Task: 4.3.1 Identification of statistically relevant methods and development of analysis

Sub-Task start month: M6
Sub-Task end month: M16
Sub-Task Leader: NVI

Sub-Task description:

Existing software will be evaluated to find software suitable for this task, and an analysis procedure will be developed using a small subset of the listerias available as a test set.

Sub-Task: 4.3.2 Processing of all isolates

Sub-Task start month: M16
Sub-Task end month: M21
Sub-Task Leader: NVI

Description of the sub-task:

Once a good procedure has been laid out, all the isolates available will be analyzed.

Task 4.4 : Comparative analysis phenotypical data / genotypical data

Task 4.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month :M17
Task end month : M22
Task Leader: ANSES
Deputy Task Leader: IZSAM
Task Participants: All : DTU, ANSES, AGES, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the sub-task :

The aim of the task is to correlate the findings of phenotypic analysis obtained in WP3 (T3.2, T3.3, T3.4) with the results from the studies conducted in WP4 (T4.3.2)

The data correlation and association will be investigated by multivariate analysis; a particular emphasis will be devoted to the analysis of population genetics within the Listeria isolates into each

biological niche by analysis of molecular variance for which specific software have been implemented (AMOVA, Arlequin)

We expect to clarify which genes are involved in adaptation of *Lm* to different ecological niches and discover strain-specific genes/markers which will strongly assist in diagnostic, phylogenetic and functional research. Strains would be assigned into well-defined clusters relevant to biological investigations.

WP 5 Trainings and dissemination

WP5 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP. WP5 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

WP start month : M1

WP end month : M24

WP Leader: Given as the strategic importance of this WP, the coordination will be done by the “Listadapt” coordinator and the leaders and the deputy-leaders of the WPs.

WP participants: All : DTU, ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the WP

Task 5.3.: Proficiency Testing Trials

Task start month : M19

Task end month : M22

Task Leader: DTU

Deputy Task Leader: IZSAM

Task Participants: DTU, ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA

Description of the task :

In “Listadapt”, we plan to set up appropriate quality standards and WGS Proficiency Testing Trials, in close collaboration with **Compare** (WP 2) and the **Global Microbial Identifier** (GMI) networks. The PT trial aims at evaluating the ability of NRLs to perform WGS according to Compare SOPs.

Quality management will be ensured and regularly tested using reference strains and reference datasets from humans, animals, environment and food. The SOPs and workflows from Compare will be evaluated here and validated by a PT trial on (1) sample preparation, (2) sequencing and (3) data analysis. René Hendriksen (DTU) chairs the working group for proficiency testing of the GMI initiative. Cesare Camma (IZSAM) is also involved in GMI. Their expertise will be then instrumental in this task.

Task 5.4.: Dissemination

Task 5.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP

Task start month : M1

Task end month : M24

Task Leader: ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: DTU

Task Participants: All : DTU, ANSES, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, VRI, NFA, INRA

Description of the task:

We have to regularly communicate and inform the scientific community about “Listadapt” progress and results obtained.

Delivery of 2000 new genomes

One of the outcomes of the project (WP2, T2.3) is the delivery of 2000 new genomes of *Listeria monocytogenes*. The sequences will be made available to the scientific community. They will be deposited in public access internet databases. Whole Genome Sequence data will be described in relevant Genome Announcements (American Society for Microbiology) and also deposited at NCBI.

Participation in national and international conferences, seminars and symposia

Sharing information in national and international meetings and congresses will also be done, in particular during the annual EURL/NRLs workshop dedicated on Listeria. Our results will be presented to the International research community, in major conferences and congresses such as :

- International Symposium on Problems of Listeriosis (ISOPOL XX) organized by the European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO) in 2019 ;
- 14th International Conference on Molecular Epidemiology and Evolutionary Genetics of Infectious Diseases (MEEGID)
- 12th International Meeting on Microbial Epidemiological Markers (IMMEM XII)

Publishing in peer-reviewed scientific journals

Results obtained in the framework of this project will be aimed for publication in high impact journals (Plos One, Frontiers in Microbiology, Applied and Environmental Microbiology, International Journal of Food Microbiology...). Med –Vet EJP funding will be acknowledged in every publication and communication.

Promotion of Listadapt

We promote the project by using the EURL Listeria website (<https://eurl-listeria.anses.fr>) and also magazines on line such as Euroréférence to reinforce the visibility of Listadapt among all referencing stakeholders in Europe.

Our results will be communicated to the non-scientific community whenever possible, via press releases, with the help of Press services from each partner organization. We will also promote the fast circulation of the project results to a large public, by writing popular articles.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP7-0.3	Plan for dissemination and Exploitation of results	M14
D-JRP7-1.4	Report on strain collection and strategy for selection of strains for sequencing.	M14
D-JRP7-2.3	Annotation of the <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> assembled genomes from 2 nd batch sequencing	M15
D-JRP7-2.4	Annotation of the <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> assembled genomes from Ad hoc Whole genome sequencing	M17
D-JRP7-3.2	Assessment of the ability to adapt to biocides and develop cross-resistance to antibiotics for some illustrative <i>L. monocytogenes</i> strains	M22
D-JRP7-3.3	Data on the effect of biocides on <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains in biofilm	M22
D-JRP7-3.4	Biofilms phenotypes for the 200 <i>L. monocytogenes</i> strains	M22
D-JRP7-3.5	Collection of data on survival of <i>L. monocytogenes</i> as planktonic cells in various ecological niches	M22
D-JRP7-3.6	Collection of data on survival of <i>L. monocytogenes</i> in soil microcosms	M22
D-JRP7-4.1	Bibliographic study on catalogues of genes	M13
D-JRP7-4.2	Report on prevalence and distribution of clonal complexes among the reservoirs	M13

D-JRP7-4.3	Software chosen for bioinformatics analysis	M16
D-JRP7-5.3	Publications and communications	M24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP7-15	WGS raw data produced	13
M-JRP7-16	Second batch Lm genomes assembly completed	14
M-JRP7-17	The database includes MLST data (CC and ST) of all the strains	14
M-JRP7-18	Second batch Lm genomes annotation completed	15
M-JRP7-19	Ad hoc batch Lm genomes assembly completed	16
M-JRP7-20	Bioinformatic analysis done for all the strains	16
M-JRP7-21	Bioinformatic analysis done for all the strains	17
M-JRP7-22	Ad hoc batch Lm genomes annotation completed	17
M-JRP7-23	Face-to face meeting -2019	17
M-JRP7-24	WGS Proficiency Testing trial (PTtrial) done	22

2.1.3.1.15 JRP8-METASTAVA

Set of activity		JRP8/R1/FBZ-2 NGS-based methods								
Project title		Standardisation and validation of metagenomics methods for the detection of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.								
Project acronym		METASTAVA								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym) ^c		P04-Sciensano			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P10-FLI		
Project Coordinator person name		Steven Van Borm			Project Deputy Leader person name			Dirk Höper		
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							Y2: second annual period			
Project Start month				M1				Project End month		M24
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	18.7		63.8					28.2		
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M										
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI
P.M									15.2	
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAY	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M									20.4	
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying knowledge and data gaps in concertation with ongoing initiatives (COMPARE, EFFORT, and GMI). Collecting reference data to allow informed design of metagenomics experiments fitting to a precisely defined diagnostic question Collecting validation data to understand and document the analytical test properties (sensitivity, specificity, robustness) of metagenomics workflows for model pathogens (in their most relevant sample matrices), including hepatitis E, norovirus, large DNA viruses, antibiotic resistant bacteria and Shigatoxigenic Escherichia coli (STEC). 										

- Proposing quality assurance metrics to guide the evaluation and interpretation of metagenomics datasets. To this purpose, available datasets will be collected and investigated in a meta-analysis. Sample type specific qualitative and quantitative metrics for the evaluation of metagenomics datasets will be proposed. In addition, we aim to develop a system of relevant process controls to monitor the robustness of the complete assay including sample treatment, data generation, and analysis.
- Provide dissemination of the outcome of other initiatives & METASTAVA.
- Ensure interlaboratory reproducibility of the delivered data and principles by organizing a proficiency test that is relevant for diagnostic laboratories and by crossanalysing metagenomics data generated by the partners

Description of work

WP1: Collect reference data from other metagenomic projects select the metagenomic methods to be used for the project, and provide guidance data for informed metagenomic workflow design.

WP1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month M1

WP end month M24

WP Leader Dirk Höper

Deputy WP Leader Frank Vandenbussche

WP participants Steven Van Borm, Sander van Boheemen, Lihong Liu, Yannick Blanchard, Sigrid DeKeersmaecker, Isabelle Kempf, Kevin Vanneste, Frank Vandenbussche

Description of the WPI

WP1 collects reference data from literature, sequence databases, partner's datasets, and ongoing initiatives. Sequence data, metadata, and published data about error rates and biases in metagenomics data generation and analysis workflows will be included in a meta-analysis aiming to produce guidelines for informed metagenomics experiment design, and quality metrics for the validation and interpretation of metagenomic data.

Task T-1.4: propose a standardised framework for the description of the application scope and analytical properties of a metagenomics assay.

Task start month M18

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm

Deputy Task Leader: Dirk Höper

Task Participants: all

Description of the task:

proposed on all delivered data (WP1-WP3), a workgroup will propose a standardised framework for the description of scope & analytical properties of a metagenomics assay.

WP2: Quality assurance tools for the validation and interpretation of metagenomics.

WP2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month M10

WP end month M24

WP Leader Sander van Boheemen

Deputy WP Leader Yannick Blanchard

WP participants Steven Van Borm, Sander van Boheemen, Lihong Liu, Yannick Blanchard, Sigrid DeKeersmaecker, Isabelle Kempf, Kevin Vanneste, Frank Vandenbussche

Description of the WP

WP2 develops quality assurance tools for metagenomics in a diagnostic context, including quality metrics, process controls, data about reproducibility and batch effects, and proficiency tests.

TaskT-2.1: develop quality metrics for metagenomics dataset evaluation.

T-2.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M10

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Kevin Vanneste

Deputy Task Leadercxix: Steven Van Borm

Task Participants: Van Borm, De Keersmaecker, van Boheemen, Höper, Blanchard, Vandenbussche

Description of the task

Based on the propositions of T-1.4, develop and validate both raw data QC metrics and endogenous (internal) control target sequences that can provide indications about the quality of a metagenomics dataset

TaskT-2.2: Development and evaluation of external controls for metagenomics.

T-2.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M18

Task Leader: Frank Vandenbussche

Deputy Task Leadercxii: Yannick Blanchard

Task Participants: Vandenbussche, Blanchard, Van Borm

Description of the task

Develop and evaluate exogenous process controls that can be spiked in samples to allow a full control of the assay from sample treatment until data interpretation.

Task T-2.4: evaluate QC metrics on additional datasets.

Task start month M13

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

partners will analyse existing and generate additional metagenomics datasets to cross-validate the developed QA principles (QC metrics and/or process controls) on additional case studies and samples.

TaskT-2.5: METASTAVA metagenomics proficiency test.

Task start month M13

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Lihong Liu

Deputy Task Leader

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

In concertation with ongoing initiatives, we will provide added value by providing a PT focused on diagnostic sample matrices (both at the sample and dataset level) and targeted to diagnostic

institutes. The collected reference samples and datasets will provide leverage for benchmarking and validation of future methodological developments in data generation and analysis.

WP3: evaluation of the analytical properties of metagenomics workflows.

WP3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month M1

WP end month M24

WP Leader Yannick Blanchard

Deputy WP Leader Lihong Liu

WP participants Steven Van Borm, Sander van Boheemen, Lihong Liu, Yannick Blanchard, Sigrid DeKeersmaecker, Isabelle Kempf, Kevin Vanneste, Frank Vandebussche

Description of the WP

WP3 experimentally determines the analytical properties (sensitivity, specificity) and robustness of metagenomics data generation and analysis protocols for the selected model pathogens in diagnostically relevant sample matrices.

Task T-3.1: analytical sensitivity, hepatitis E virus.

T-3.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Nicole Pavio

Task Participants: Pavio, Martin-Latil, Liu, Van Gucht, Suin, Van Borm, Vandebussche, Cotten, Koopmans, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan.

Description of the task

Replicate metagenomics analysis of hepE dilutions in diagnostically relevant sample matrices for human, animal and food samples to estimate the analytical sensitivity and robustness.

TaskT-3.2: analytical sensitivity, norovirus.

T-3.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Sandra Martin-Latil

Task Participants Martin-Latil, Liu, van Boheemen, Koopmans

Description of the task

Replicate metagenomics analysis of norovirus dilutions in diagnostically relevant sample matrices for human and food samples to estimate the analytical sensitivity and robustness. Higher uncertainty for deliverables on food items (very low NoV titers), high certainty for human (fecal or vomit) samples.

TaskT-3.3: analytical sensitivity, large DNA viruses.

T-3.3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Martin Beer

Task Participants: Beer, Höper, Pohlmann, van Boheemen, Koopmans, De Clercq

Description of the task

Replicate metagenomics analysis of poxvirus dilutions in diagnostically relevant sample matrices.

Task T-3.4: analytical sensitivity, STEC.

T-3.4 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: DeKeersmaecker

Task Participants: Kempf, Blanchard, Denayer

Description of the task

Replicate shotgun metagenomics of STEC dilutions in diagnostically relevant sample matrices for human and/or food samples to estimate the analytical sensitivity and robustness.

Task T-3.5: analytical sensitivity, detection of ABR genes.

T-3.5 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Kempf

Task Participants: DeKeersmaecker, Blanchard

Description of the task

Replicate shotgun metagenomics of antibiotic resistant bacteria in diagnostically relevant sample matrices to estimate the analytical sensitivity and robustness.

Task T-3.6: bioinformatics and statistical analysis of analytical performance experiments

T-3.6 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Kevin Vanneste

Task Participants: Van Borm, Vandenbussche, Blanchard, Höper, van Boheemen, DeKeersmaecker

Description of the task

Concertation to align the analysis of all data generated in T-3.1 - T-3.5.

WP4: Concertation with ongoing efforts and dissemination.

WP4 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month M1

WP end month M24

WP Leader Steven Van Borm

WP participants all

Description of the WP

WP4 assures via direct concertation that all research overlap with ongoing initiatives is avoided. It also ensures formal PI issue arrangements in accession to data, knowledge, tools, and samples where needed. In addition, WP4 assures dissemination of the project findings.

Task T-4.1: concertation with ongoing initiatives.

T-4.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm

Task Participants: Van Borm, Blanchard, Koopmans, Beer, Roosens, De Keersmaecker.

Description of the task

Coordination with the related projects of COMPARE, EFFORT, DECATHLON and GMI, to give input for WP1, 2, and 3. Identify gaps in the current technology relevant for applying metagenomics for diagnostics. In addition, existing ISO workgroups on QA of NGS based methods will be contacted. A coordination meeting will be organised with participants from these other projects, Intellectual property (IP) issues regarding access to their knowledge and technology will be addressed (as will any background IP at the start of the consortium), this information will be provided to WP1 and WP2, and an analysis of important gaps in the current technology for applying metagenomics for diagnostics will be identified. Continued coordination with related initiatives to exchange findings.

Task T-4.2: Formal dissemination.

T-4.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

SOPs, scientific papers, conference contributions, participation to working groups

Task T-4.3: dissemination of recommendations to stakeholders

T-4.3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

Dissemination of recommendations from project findings to the various stakeholders (e.g. policy-makers, industry, citizens, research community in the different domains of 'One Health').

Task T-4.4: Organization of a scientific meeting

T-4.4 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M20

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

Organisation of a scientific meeting to disseminate the project findings.

WP5: Project management

WP5 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month M1

WP end month M24

WP Leader Steven Van Borm

Deputy WP Leader Dirk Höper

WP participants all

Description of the WP

Responsibilities include liaising with the EU, consolidating a consortium agreement, organising project meetings, reports, and internal coordination. The project coordinator will be assisted in these duties by a deputy coordinator, work package leaders and task leaders. A General Assembly (coordinator + WPLs) will be established to allow important decisions impacting on project organisation and output. Yearly project meetings will be organised, supplemented with additional online meetings (either project-wide, or WP or task specific).

Task T-5.2: internal communication.

T-5.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M1

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

Yearly progress meetings and intermediary communication

Task T-5.3: reporting and liaising with the EU

T-5.3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

Task start month M20

Task end month M24

Task Leader: Van Borm

Task Participants: all

Description of the task

Half term (Y1) reporting and final report.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP8-1.4	SOP: guidelines for the description of scope and analytical properties of a metagenomic method in a diagnostic context	M24
D-JRP8-1.5	Review paper	M24
D-JRP8-2.1	SOP: use of endogenous quality metrics for metagenomics dataset evaluation	M24
D-JRP8-2.2	Report and guidelines for the use of exogenous process controls in metagenomics	M24
D-JRP8-2.4	Report on proficiency test	M24
D-JRP8-3.3	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , hepE	M24
D-JRP8-3.4	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , NoV	M24
D-JRP8-3.5	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , pox	M24
D-JRP8-3.6	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , STEC	M24
D-JRP8-3.7	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , ABR genes detection	M24
D-JRP8-4.2	SOP's , guidelines, scientific papers, presentations	M24
D-JRP8-4.3	Minutes of scientific meeting	M24
D-JRP8-5.2	Progress and final meeting minutes	M24
D-JRP8-5.3	Half term report	M13
D-JRP8-5.4	Final report	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP8-M6	Proficiency test panel ready for shipping	M18
M-JRP8-M7	Scientific meeting	M24
M-JRP8-M8	Dissemination to various stakeholders including joint communication with ongoing initiatives	M24
M-JRP8-M9	Final meeting	M24

2.1.3.1.16 JRP9-AIR-SAMPLE

Set of activity		JRP9/R1/FBZ-3 Biosecurity, interventions.								
Project title		Air-sampling: A Low-Cost Screening Tool in Biosecured Broiler Production.								
Project acronym		AIR-SAMPLE								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P12-DTU		Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			NVI			
Project Coordinator person name		Jeffrey Hoofar		Project Deputy Leader person name			Mona Torp			
Indicate for which annual period of the EJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month				M13			Project End month			M24
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M						5.3				15.5
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M										
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M						10				
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
P.M	5.5	9.6								
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To validate the air sampling and DNA extraction methods against current international standards using boot swabs. To prepare Standard Operating Procedures (SOP's). To disseminate the above protocols through hands-on workshops. 										
Description of work										
WP2. Validation and standardization.										

WP start month: 13.

WP end month: 24.

WP Leader: Gro Johannessen (NVI).

Deputy WP Leader: Ivana Koláčková (VRI).

WP participants: Ivana Kolackova (VRI), Julia Christensen (DTU), Mona Torp and Gro Johannessen (NVI), Kinga Wieczorek and Jacek Osek (NVRI), Giuliano Garofolo (IZSAM).

Description of the WP: WP2 departs from the achievements of the first annual period and takes place over the second annual period of the EJP. Validation is important to regulatory approvals before the methods can be used. Hence, the air sampling protocol from WP1 will be validated. Following statistical data analysis of the results obtained, the best performing protocol will be drafted as a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP). This will be disseminated among the EJP partner laboratories involved in testing of *Campylobacter*, and as a new working item to microbiology working groups of International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and Committee of European Normalization (CEN). A draft manuscript will be submitted to the EFSA Journal.

Task 2-1. Parallel validation of air and sock sampling and DNA extraction methods.

Task start month: M13

Task end month: M21

Task Leader: Gro Johannesen (NVI)

Deputy Task Leader: Julia Christensen (DTU)

Task Participants: Ivana Kolackova (VRI), Kinga Wieczorek (PIWET), Giuliano Garofolo (IZSAM).

Description of the task: Two best-performing, pre-PCR DNA extraction protocols will be implemented at the partner labs included in the present project. As part of field studies, each partner will (in a two-phase setup) assess the DNA extraction methods for air filter and sock sample on own field samples that were collected during WP1. The best DNA extraction method will be subsequently validated on 10 field samples per partner. The samples will be collected in a new round of sampling during the summer of 2019. Each field sample will represent one chicken house (flock). A farm may contribute with more than one chicken house. The validation will only include the sampling and DNA extraction steps, as individual labs are free to use own PCR. At all stages of validation, one sock sample will be included as “golden” standard sample and tested according to the international (ISO) method. Results of local field studies will be collected by the project coordinator and centrally analyzed using the same statistical method.

Task 2-2. Statistical analysis, Standardization and dissemination.

Task start month: M21

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: Renata Karpickova (VRI)

Deputy Task Leader: Jeffrey Hoorfar (DTU)

Task Participants: Gro Johannesen (NVI), Jacek Osek (PIWET), Mona Torp (NVI), Giuliano Garofolo (IZSAM).

Description of the task: The main aim of this task is to disseminate the outcome. Results of air samples used in qPCR and culturing will be statistically validated against sock samples, but also using latent class analysis where no gold standard is assumed.

Project results will be communicated through various relevant channels as follows:

1. Preparation of a draft manuscript to the official journal of European Food Safety Authority.

2. Preparation of an SOP to be submitted to the consortium and to ISO and CEN for consideration as a future guideline or standard
3. Communication of the project outcome to the national food safety authorities
4. Online video animation material for the education of broiler industry, and
5. Dissemination through a hands-on, wet-lab workshop.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP9-2.1.	Online video demonstration of air sampling for farmers.	M24
D-JRP9-2.2.	Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for air sampling.	M24
D-JRP9-2.3.	Draft manuscript for publication in EFSA Journal.	M24
D-JRP9-2.4.	Hands-on, wet-lab workshop for relevant EJP partners.	M24

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP9-3	Local field studies completed.	M18
M-JRP9-4	Statistical analysis completed.	M21

2.1.3.1.17 JRP10-MoMIR-PPC

Set of activity		JRP10/R1/FBZ-3 Biosecurity, interventions.								
Project title		Monitoring the gut microbiota and immune response to predict, prevent and control zoonoses in humans and livestock in order to minimize the use of antimicrobials.								
Project acronym		MoMIR-PPC								
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P19-INRA			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			P17-VISAVET-UCM		
Project Coordinator person name		Velge Philippe			Project Deputy Leader person name			María Ugarte Ruiz		
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies:							2			
Project Start month				M1			Project End month			M20
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	8.28			25		12				
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M					29		33.6			
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI
P.M	12.8				14.5		11		18.82	13
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
P.M										
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of tools to predict Super-shedder animals and human prolonged <i>Salmonella</i> carriers • Development of pro- and pre-biotics to prevent the appearance of Super-shedders • Development of new models of pathogen transmission • Development of new intervention strategies to fight zoonotic pathogens • Dissemination of the original information acquired during this project 										
Description of work										

Heterogeneity of infection is influenced by a complex set of variables involving the intestinal microbiota, mucosal immunity, intestinal physiology and pathogen adaptation to its host. We have demonstrated that immune status before infection can modulate *Salmonella* infection (Chausse *et al.* Infect Immun 2011) and we can transfer the Super shedder phenotype through transfer of gut microbiota (Menanteau *et al.* in preparation). These results open new avenues to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to high/low shedding and thus to predict the animals which will be Super shedders.

For these WP, partners 1, 18 and 27 have already **developed infection models** to analyze the heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection in pig and chickens. Moreover, we will analyze animal and human infections in “field condition” (P6, P16, P29, P32). We will visit poultry and pigs farms across Europe with high and low *Salmonella* status based on serology surveillance data. Individual animal samples will be collected and examined for *Salmonella* and other pathogens from relevant age groups: for example, weaning pigs, slaughter pigs, and sows at different time points during pregnancy or nursing period. Differences in shedding patterns will be related to age, feed, antimicrobial treatment, zinc supplementation, and other relevant parameters. In the majority of cases, the same animal will be used to define immunological and microbiota markers and to test the virulence of *Salmonella* strains. For humans, we will follow volunteers’ post-*Salmonella* infection and identify risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* excretion.

WP0:
Management

WP0 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP WP start month: **M13**
WP end month: **M24**

WP Leader: **P18-Tours** Philippe Velge
Deputy WP Leader: **P16,** María Ugarte Ruiz
WP participants:

All partners

Description of the WP:

WP0 exists to ensure effective and efficient management of the project. The objectives of this work package are:

- ☐ To facilitate communications and collaboration between partners and with the EC and its representatives. To coordinate the technical work carried out in the project across all work packages
- ☐ To ensure that the project objectives are achieved within the planned time and budget and provide management reports to the EC.

To ensure the quality of work including deliverables; to track technical and financial risks to the project and manage the response to ameliorate them.

Description of work

With a variety of partners across a wide geographical location, MoMIR-PPC will require dedicated project and stakeholder management to ensure that project objectives are realized and that partners are fully engaged with progress throughout. After the second year of the project, the steering committee, composed of at least one representative from each participating laboratory will pay attention to:

Risk mitigation and management: All categories of risk will be considered such as financial, delivery, procurement, human resources, reputational and business demand. Risk register reviews will be conducted by the steering committee every 3 months.

Dispute resolution: It is recognised that, as a large and complex international project with multiple parties across different countries and legal jurisdictions, MOMIR-PPC requires an effective mechanism for the resolution of any potential conflict or dispute which may arise between Consortium partners. The Consortium Agreement will include specific provisions for dispute resolution. Amicable resolution of any dispute arising from the implementation of the Action will be encouraged and supported by the steering committee, which will in the first instance endeavour to find an acceptable outcome.

Data Management Plan: Data Management Plan will be worked into the overall Project Plan. The plan will

include information on how the project will manage the research data generated/collected on the project in order to meet the conditions for the Open Research Data pilot, ensuring that all research data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable and that subject-identifiable confidential data kept and published so that data protection regulations are respected.

Task-0.2 Produce project-planning, control documentation and Data Management Plan:

T-0.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period

of the EJP Task start month: M13

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: **P1**, Martine Denis

Deputy Task Leader: **P27**, Barbara Chirullo

Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

Documents to be produced for the purposes of planning, monitoring and controlling project execution will include a Project Plan, profiled budget plan, workflow schedule, output profile, change log and risk management plan. A plan for the effective management of project data – covering matters that will include data collection, handling, transfer, storage, security, exploitation, accessibility and preservation – will be produced using the template provided and following the Horizon 2020 guidelines on data management. FAIR principles will be observed within the plan to ensure that the research data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. **The plan will be reviewed and updated throughout the lifespan of the project.**

Task-0.3 Control and manage activity progresses, the timely delivery of project tasks and outputs

T-0.3 takes place over the first and the second annual period

of the EJP Task start month: M13

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Philippe Velge

Deputy Task Leader: **P6**, Hristo Daskalov

Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

The steering committee will have the responsibility for ensuring that milestones and deliverables will be accomplished on time. **He will facilitate the day-to-day running of the project.** These will include regular and effective communication, troubleshooting and the overseeing of general administrative duties.

Task-0.4 Control and manage the project closure and outputs

Task start month: M22

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Philippe Velge

Deputy Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Beatrice Laroche

Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

Project closure plans will be developed in line with Horizon 2020 requirements. The detailed closure process comprising a template and related guidelines developed by the INRA Team will be used as a framework for this process. The closing meeting will allow discussion about future initiatives.

WP1: Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human prolonged *Salmonella* carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses.

WP1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP WP start month: **M1**

WP end month: **M12**

WP Leader: **P22**, Roberto La Ragione

Deputy WP Leader: **P29**, Giovanni Loris Alborali

WP participants: **P1, P8, P16, P18, P22, P27, P29, P32**

Description of the WP:

The goal of this WP is to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to high/low shedding before and/or after infection, which allow us to predict and identify the animals which will be Super shedders. For this WP, we will use already developed infection models (P1, 18 and 27) but also animal (Task 1 and 2) and human infections (Task 3) in “field condition” (P29, P32). Taking into account the great adaptability of pathogens for their hosts, the virulence and immunogenicity of *Salmonella* strains of human and animal origins and from Super- and low-shedders will be compared (P18-Tours, P22). The gut microbiota composition (P8, P22), the cellular biomarkers and the immune response parameters (P18, P27, P29) will be studied with the same chickens and pigs. **The second year will be devoted to the analysis of the data recovered the first year in order to define the predictive markers associated to high and low shedders.**

This WP will be divided into 4 tasks:

Task-1.1: Predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

T-1.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: M13

Task end month: M20

Task Leader: **P27**, Barbara Chirullo

Deputy Task Leader: **P1**, Martine Denis

Task Participants: **P1, P16, P18-Tours, P27, P29**

Description of the task:

The goal of the task will be to identify immune markers able to identify the super-Shedders and other able to predict the most susceptible animals and/or the animals that will become super-shedders, if infected. The activities will be focused on the most prevalent serotypes: *S. Typhimurium* for pig, and *S. Enteritidis* for chicken. They will use global approaches but also already published markers (Knetter *et al.* Innate Immun, 2015 ; Chaussé *et al.* Infect Immun 2011). A set a markers has been already defined by several members. Moreover, we will study the predictive power of the IgM and IgA dynamics before and after infection to distinguish the super-shedders. To reach intestinal biomarkers at different level of shedder and between species Partner 16 will realize proteomic comparative study.

Task-1.2: Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

T-1.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: 13

Task end month: 20

Task Leader: **P8**, Ivan Rychlick

Deputy Task Leader: **P22**, Roberto La Ragione

Task Participants: **P1, P8, P18-Tours, P22, P27, P29, P32**

Description of the task:

The goal of the task is to analyse the gut microbiota composition before and after *Salmonella* infection to identify predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs. Samples from representative pigs and chickens originated from activities of task 1.1 will be analyzed (P8 and P22 respectively) based on Illumina sequencing of V3/V4 variable region of 16S rRNA genes. The microbiome composition will be related to shedding status for *Salmonella* with ACP analyses and hierarchical clustering. Several bacterial genera have been already correlated with susceptibility/ resistance to become a super-shedder. However, it is important to demonstrate numerous correlations in poultry and/ or pig before to purify and test these commensal bacteria in WP2.

Task-1.3: Risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* shedding in humans

T-1.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP Task start month: 13

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: **P32**, Anke Corinna Stüken

Task Participants: **P22, P32**

Description of the task:

This task will encompass a Norwegian prospective cohort study as detailed for task 1.3 in the first annual period of the EJP. All NT-Salmonellosis cases registered during Sept-18 and Sept-19 in the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) with an accompanying isolate submitted to Norwegian National Reference Laboratory (NRL) will be asked to participate. At four intervals during the collection year, the database will be accessed to identify cases with *Salmonella* positive samples. Cases will be divided into three groups according to date of sampling in relation to month of accession: i) ≤ 1 month, ii) $>1 \leq 2$ month, and iii) >2 month. In the second annual period, stool samples will be screened for *Salmonella* growth and stored for downstream microbiome analyses (16Sr RNA gene sequencing). Growth will be interpreted as continued *Salmonella* shedding; no *Salmonella* growth as termination of the shedding state. Participants with continuous shedding will be asked if they are willing to give a new stool sample. All initial *Salmonella* isolates submitted to NRL will be serotyped and screened for antibiotic susceptibility to beta-lactams (ampicillin, ceftazidime, cefotaxime, meropenem), quinolone (pefloxacin), aminoglycoside (gentamicin) and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole by disk diffusion. Subsequently, all isolates will be whole genome sequenced (Illumina) following DNA extraction and library preparation (2 x 300bp). Analyses of genome sequences will be carried out in the second annual period of the EJP. Furthermore comparative genomic analyses will search for possible additional marker genes that may predict long term *Salmonella* excretion in humans.

Task-1.4: Virulence of *Salmonella* strains originated from high and low shedders

T-1.4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP Task start month: 13

Task end month: 20

Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Mustapha

Berri Deputy Task Leader: **P22**,

Roberto La Ragione Task

Participants: **P18-Tours, P22, P32**

Description of the task:

We will continue to compare the adhesion and invasion capabilities as well as the induced immune response between different *Salmonella* strains of human and animal origins and from super- and low-shedders using epithelial and macrophages pig and chicken cell lines and organoids (P18, P22). In addition transcriptomic analysis will be set up to compare the immune response. For the *Salmonella* strains, which will be sequenced, within the project a comparative study between the virulence and the genome will be performed. If needed, we will analyse for few strains whether *Salmonella* can cross the host barriers, gets access to deeper tissues and elude the immune response thereby promoting their dissemination using pig intestinal explants or intestinal ligated loops model (P18).

WP2: Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedders by modifying feed and/or microbiota

WP2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP

WP start month: **M13**

WP end month: **M24**

WP Leader: **P16** VISAVET-UCM. Antonio Rodríguez Bertos

Deputy WP Leader: **P29**, Giovanni Loris Alborali

WP participants: **P6, P8, P16, P18-Tours, P22, P27, P29,**

Description of the WP:

Production animals when infected by a foodborne pathogen such as *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* or toxigenic *E. coli*, are in most cases mere asymptomatic carriers which release the bacteria to the environment through their faeces. The removal of super-shedders from a population may significantly reduce transmission and contamination with these foodborne pathogens. However, far from being beneficial, prolonged antibiotic treatment may alter dramatically the intestinal flora composition, may increase the pathogen's antimicrobial resistance and trigger the super-shedder phenotype (Crowell *et al.* 2009 Infect immun ; Sana & Monack 2016 Nature).

The aim of WP2 is to ascertain, through the use of –omics technology, whether pre-biotics, probiotics or nutraceutical formula would be able to considerably lower the numbers of *Salmonella* (and other foodborne pathogens such as *Campylobacter* and toxigenic *E. coli*) released by super-shedders. The impact of these food supplement formula on gut microbiota composition, immune response and susceptibility to pathogens like *Salmonella* will be investigated. We will also analyze their impact on the resistome of the microbiome and on animal's parameters (P29, P6 respectively). Close cooperation with the other partners will allow us to better understand super-shedding basis and to set up the best options to achieve a drastic reduction of *Salmonella* release to the environment. We will test the efficacy of a series of commensal bacteria (probiotics) and of natural diet additives which are expected to alter the intestinal microbiota by promoting the growth of "beneficial" microorganisms, whilst avoiding the use of antibiotics. The main goal would be to modify microbiota composition to improve immune response and the barrier effect procured by gut microbiota, with the ultimate goal of preventing super-shedder status in animals and carriage status in humans. Some approaches have been reported on this respect in human and animal (Drakoularakou *et al.* 2010 Eur J Clin Nutri; Yadav *et al* (2016) J Exp Biol Agri Sci).

Task-2.1: Use of probiotics in chicken and pig

T-2.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: M13

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: **P8**, Ivan Rychlick

Deputy Task Leader: **P29**, Giovanni Loris Alborali

Task Participants: **P6, P8, P18-Tours, P22, P27, P29,**

Description of the task:

The main objective of this task will be to improve immune response and barrier effect procured by gut microbiota by introducing already identified probiotics, which will be identified by partner 22 and isolated from healthy pigs and poultry. These commensal bacteria will be phenotypically and genotypically characterised using WGS, Biolog, NMR and *in vitro* organ culture studies. We will also test *in vitro* the competitive exclusion of these commensal bacteria by themselves and/or the metabolites generated for *Salmonella*. The effect of putative probiotics identified in WP1 on gut microbiota and pathogen infection will be tested in established experimental avian and porcine models described in WP1 (P18-Tours, P8, P27), but also on farms with presence of *Salmonella* (P6, P29). The pro and pre-biotics (task 2.2) will be tested in pig farms (P6, P29) and in broiler farms (P6). Blood count test - hemoglobin, hematocrit, white blood cells, total blood protein, blood albumin, glucose, serum bactericidal activity and immunoglobulin levels according

ELISA method will be recorded as well as welfare, health status and animal performance parameters.

Task-2.2: Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical already defined by the consortium partners in chicken and pig.

T-2.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: **M13**

Task end month: **M24**

Task Leader: **P16**, María Ugarte Ruiz

Deputy Task Leader: **P6**, Hristo Daskalov

Task Participants: **P6, P8, P16, P22**

Description of the task:

The goal of this Task is to measure the effect of several pre-biotics (pellet, meal, liquid, or feed with various fibers) (P1, P6) and nutraceuticals (P16) in farms and experimental conditions. We will analyse their effects on animal health status (P6, P16), blood parameters (P6), animal performances (P6, P16), gut microbiota composition (P8, P16, P22), immune response (P6, P27, P29) and welfare (P6, P29). Microbiota composition and immune status will be tested with the same approaches than in WP1. They will be mainly analysed the second year from the samples recovered the first year.

WP3: Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms

WP3 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP WP start month: **M13**

WP end month: **M24**

WP Leader: **P30** Thomas Hagenaars

Deputy WP Leader: **P18-Jouy**, Beatrice Laroche

WP participants: **P18-Tours, P30**

Description of the WP:

WP3 will focus on the problem of *Salmonella* in poultry and pig in order to develop the building blocks and tools that are needed for design and assessment of intervention strategies. For this purpose we will develop multiscale computational models (from within-host to between-host scale) of heterogeneous pathogen transmission by integrating data from WP1 and 2 and already available datasets by consortium partners in order to design and assess intervention strategies. The models will be designed to allow assessment of the efficiency and/or cost-effectiveness of different intervention strategies. In particular, assessment of intervention strategies targeting super-shedders and based on probiotic and/or prebiotic treatments are of interest, as well as combinations of such strategies with biosecurity measures based on hygiene and movement restriction. This WP will be divided in two main tasks:

T-3.1: Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales

T-3.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: **M13**

Task end month: **M24**

Task Leader: **P18-Jouy**, Beatrice Laroche
Deputy Task Leader: **P30**, Thomas Hagenaars
Task Participants: **P18-Jouy, P30, P41**

Description of the task:

In this task, mathematical models will be developed to integrate quantitative knowledge on the heterogeneity of infection and the role of gut microbiota, linking up two scales. **The models, built the first year, will be improved the second year after inclusion of data obtained in WP1 and WP2.**

Sub-Task 3.1.1: Within-host scale: modelling individual responses and shedding

Sub-Task start month: M13
Sub-Task end month: M24
Sub-Task Leader: **P18-Jouy**, Béatrice Laroche
Sub-Task Participants: **P18-Jouy**,

Description of the Sub-task:

Our ambition is to develop simplified, but relevant models of the host including key features of the gut microbiota dynamics and key features of the immune system response. This work will rely on the data generated by WP1 and WP2. The general idea would be to implement stochastic or deterministic dynamic interaction models between groups of gut bacteria (typical models are generalized Lotka-Volterra models, but other options are possible). Some bacterial genus will be explicitly represented, based on the knowledge generated in WP1. For other operational taxonomic units, aggregation prior to modelling is a key problem that we will address through clustering approaches. The links with the hosts immune response will be modelled, first in order to include possible feedback loop between the host and its microbiota and second in order to include super-shedder detection strategies in the model. The final models will include as much as possible the mechanisms described in WP1 and WP2

Sub-Task 3.1.2: Between-host scale: modelling transmission, linked to within-host results

Sub-Task start month: M15
Sub-Task end month: M21
Sub-Task Leader: **P41**, Mart de Jong
Sub-Task Participants: **P18-Jouy, P30, P41**

Description of the Sub-task:

The modelling aims to integrate, the second year, data from the two other WPs and already available datasets (first year). Between-host transmission models will be formulated based on the results of the within-host modelling, relating host susceptibility and transmission parameters to intra-host characteristics (P18-Jouy, P30). Then, environmental dissemination of infectious material has to be incorporated, based on part on data from experiments. The coupling of between-animal heterogeneities (of shedding) to environmental transmission is important to both distinguish and combine host-pathogen interactions and pathogen-environment interactions. We envisage including both transmission between stables (animal groups coinciding temporally but not spatially) and between rounds (animal groups coinciding spatially)

but not temporally), such that this model can in task 2 be further developed to mimic interventions: super-shedder detection/removal, between-stable biosecurity measures, between-round biosecurity measures.

T-3.2: Interventions strategies: Identification and evaluation tools

T-3.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: **M13**

Task end month: **M24**

Task Leader: **P30**, Thomas Hagenaars

Deputy Task Leader: **P18-Jouy**, Béatrice Laroche

Task Participants: **P18-Jouy, P30, P41**

Description of the task:

The results of WP1 and WP2 will help designing intervention strategies targeting super-shedders and based on probiotic and/or prebiotic treatments. As these rely on a complex interplay between the ecological behaviour of the gut microbiota and the host immune response, the multi-scale modelling approach is essential to assess and improve the efficiency of these intervention strategies. Moreover, such strategies can be combined with other biosecurity measures based on hygiene and movement restriction.

Sub-Task 3.2.1: Systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures

Sub-Task start month: M17

Sub-Task end month: M19

Sub-Task Leader: **P30**, Thomas Hagenaars

Sub-Task Participants: **P30, P41**

Description of the Sub-task:

In order to identify specific husbandry and/or biosecurity actions that can form building blocks for intervention strategies in combination with those based on probiotic and/or prebiotic treatments, knowledge of the husbandry practices is important. Based on expert knowledge, an inventory of such practical building blocks will be developed in year 1. Based as much as possible on results from the models of task 3.2.2, these building blocks can be weighed using a HACCP methodology. A first such weighing will be attempted in year 2.

Sub-Task 3.2.2: Inclusion of potential interventions into the modelling

Sub-Task start month: M13

Sub-Task end month: M2

Sub-Task Leader: **P18-Jouy**, Béatrice Laroche

Sub-Task Participants: **P18-Jouy, P30, P41**

Description of the Sub-task:

In part based on WP2 results, mathematical representations of the mechanisms through which potential intervention measures act will be included in the models developed in task 3.1.2

Sub-Task 3.2.3: **Development of economic analysis tools**

Sub-Task start month: M13

Sub-Task end month: M24

Sub-Task Leader: **P30**, Ron Bergevoet

Sub-Task Participants: **P30**, P41

Description of the Sub-task:

Economic analysis tools will be developed that can be used in combination with the transmission-dynamical models to evaluate cost effectiveness of intervention strategies. In this context the (socio-) economic viability of intervention strategies, including consumer acceptance, needs to be taken into consideration, as well as effective implementation strategies of promising interventions. For this, behavioural insights will be applied to the agricultural domain to predict the adoption of policy measures and interventions. In year 2 the economic analysis tools will be developed from a first description of these tools completed in year 1.

WP4: Communication and Dissemination for Impact

WP4 takes place over the first and the second annual period

of the EJP WP start month: **M13**

WP end month: **M24**

WP Leader: **P18-Tours**, Philippe Velge

Deputy WP Leader: **P32**, Anke Corinna Stüken

WP participants: **All partners**

Description of the WP:

This WP will be embedded in the animal and human value chain through all work being carried out. It aims to raise awareness of the progress and benefits of the project by continually communicating with stakeholders through the targeted routes and media. The Steering committee will identify and set clear communication objectives that will ensure that all messages are tactically planned. Dissemination and communication strategies will acknowledge demand from beyond Europe for new knowledge that will afford effective infection-control measures. Individual partners' specific roles in communication activities will be set out and agreed during the initial stages of the project. The communication strategy will remain sufficiently flexible to respond positively to unforeseen opportunities and may evolve during the life of the project. A special budget has been devoted to scientific exchanges, conference organization etc.

T-4.1: Dissemination of data within the project and management of data

T-3.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the EJP Task start month: **M13**

Task end month: **M24**

Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Philippe Velge

Deputy Task Leader: **P32**, Anke Corinna Stüken

Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

The main objectives of this task will be to develop:

- The project website will include a private-facing area allowing data exchanges within the consortium; The website will also collate all proposals and applications for short training visits between laboratories to learn particular skills.

- Data management policy and strategies will be designed to afford efficient handling, storage and sharing of data during the life of the project and to facilitate access to the data after the project ends. MOPIR-PPC will be a highly-collaborative project in which participants will share their existing knowledge and innovation with the goal of achieving collectively results of a magnitude and significance that could not be obtained in isolation.

T-4.2: Dissemination of data outside the project and management of data

T-4.2 takes place over the first and the second annual period

of the EJP Task start month: **M13**

Task end month: **M24**

Task Leader: **P32**, Anke Corinna

Stüken Deputy Task Leader: **P1**,

Martine Denis Task

Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

The overarching objective of WP4 is to ensure that new knowledge, information and data from MoMIR-PPC are passed to relevant user communities and other recipients – including the general public – in a timely and accessible manner in order to ensure that maximum impact potential is achieved. The applicants have

extensive experience of delivering both research outputs and more general information on food-borne pathogens through all branches of the popular media, and will play an active role in engaging with the public. They will be supported by the press offices in their respective organizations that will help draft and target press releases and arranging interviews and media visits. The consortium well understands that issues of food quality and hygiene, public health and farm-animal welfare offer excellent opportunities for engaging with a public that has high interest in such matters.

- The project website will include a public-facing area within which content will be tailored for a lay audience, while social media will be used where appropriate to put emerging stories rapidly into the public domain.

- In the second year, we will disseminate our research findings through peer-reviewed publications and through presentations at national and international conferences.

- MoMIR-PPC partners will communicate with policy-makers and regulators to ensure, wherever relevant and practical, that significant ground-breaking results are encapsulated within formal best-practice guidelines, national policies and/or statute. Dissemination activities will further extend to the scientific and lay-public communities.

- A high strategy meeting will be organized to disseminate the results of the project to the fields of animal husbandry and animal and human health. Attention will be paid to ensuring that the above dissemination efforts reach those Member States not represented in the MOMIR-PPC consortium. Partner 30 has already organized such meeting as he organized in April 2016 a High Strategy Meeting related to the subject of *Dermanyssus gallinae* on human health where specialists in human medicine, veterinary medicine, animal husbandry, pest control and occupational health were invited.

Deliverables

D-JRP10-0.4	Minutes of project meetings (mid term meeting)	13
D-JRP10-0.5	Minutes of project meetings (closing project)	24
D-JRP10-0.6	Financial and scientific reports for the EJP Coordinator (Intermediated report)	13
D-JRP10-0.7	Financial and scientific reports for the EJP Coordinator (closing report)	24

D-JRP10-1.04	In vitro virulence levels of different Salmonella strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (first round)	20
D-JRP10-1.05	Microbiome analyses of human stool samples	21
D-JRP10-1.06	Definition of predictive immunological markers associated to the high and lowshedders in chickens and in pigs.	20
D-JRP10-1.07	Definition of immunological markers associated to the high and lowshedders in chickens and in pigs.	20
D-JRP10-1.08	Characterization, evolution and comparison of the microbiome of pig and poultry with different shedding status of Salmonella	18
D-JRP10-1.09	Definition of predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20
D-JRP10-1.10	Definition of microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20
D-JRP10-1.11	Recovery of all human samples	15
D-JRP10-1.12	Antimicrobial susceptibility testing, serotyping and whole genome sequencing of all Salmonella isolates from participants submitted to the Norwegian Reference laboratory	17
D-JRP10-1.13	Microbiome analyses of human stool samples. Salmonella colonization in low shedders (first round)	24
D-JRP10-1.14	Identification, from in vitro studies, of immune parameters related to high and low shedders	20
D-JRP10-1.15	Understanding whether high and low shedder phenotypes are mainly related to Salmonella strain variation, immune status, or microbiota composition.	24
D-JRP10-2.03	Characterization of protective commensal bacteria able to inhibit Salmonella colonization (two rounds)	14
D-JRP10-2.04	Characterization of protective commensal bacteria able to inhibit Salmonella colonization (two rounds)	22
D-JRP10-2.05	Determine the influence of defined and undefined probiotics on the microbiome signature, the immune response, gut physiology and welfare of pig and/ or chicken	24
D-JRP10-2.06	Impact of defined and undefined probiotics on Salmonella colonization in pig and chicken	24
D-JRP10-2.07	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on the immune parameters, the microbiome and resistome, gut physiology and welfare of pig and chicken.	24
D-JRP10-2.08	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on Salmonella colonization in pig, chicken. Effect on the super-shedders and low-shedders.	24
D-JRP10-2.09	Dynamics of the microbiome and resistome in the different groups and conditions	24
D-JRP10-2.10	Validation of immunological and microbiota markers, identified in WP1 and associated to high/low shedding, in the control groups of WP2	24

D-JRP10-2.11	Evolution of the immune-signature in pig, chicken and/ or human according to the context (infection, treatment...)	20
D-JRP10-3.01	Models at within-host scale taking into account the interactions between infection and microbiota and mechanisms of interventions	22
D-JRP10-3.02	Models at between-host scale, linking to the within-host modelling and taking into account the mechanisms of interventions	22
D-JRP10-3.03	Intervention measures inventory	20
D-JRP10-3.04	Economic analysis tools	24
D-JRP10-3.05	Definition of intervention measures to target super-shedders	24
D-JRP10-3.06	Evaluation scheme for cost effectiveness of the intervention strategies	24
D-JRP10-4.04	Publication, and presentation at conferences	24
D-JRP10-4.05	Dissemination to lay-public communities, to policy-makers and regulators, farmers and companies	24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP10-22	Organization of consortium meetings (intermediate and closure)	13
M-JRP10-23	Recruitment of the fourth set of human participants including stool sampling and Salmonella culture	15
M-JRP10-24	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with probiotics	16
M-JRP10-25	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	18
M-JRP10-26	MALDI TOF Imaging processing and workflow on the paraffin wax slides of intestine wall in high and low shedder from chickens and pigs	18
M-JRP10-27	Comparison of microbiota composition between high and low shedders in chickens and pigs and in humans between prolonged and short <i>Salmonella</i> excretion.	18
M-JRP10-28	In vitro infection of several cell lines and organoids with the different Salmonella strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (second round)	18
M-JRP10-29	Comparison of the immune signature of high and low shedders in chicken and pig	18
M-JRP10-30	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	19
M-JRP10-31	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced in vitro between different strains to identify immunological markers	20
M-JRP10-32	Final inventory of intervention measures completed	20
M-JRP10-33	Updated version of within-host models completed	21
M-JRP10-34	Updated version of between-host models completed	21
M-JRP10-35	Comparative genomic analyses of human Salmonella isolates in relation with their virulence level	22
M-JRP10-36	Updated version of economic analysis tools completed	22

M-JRP10-37	Potential interventions included in between-host modelling	22
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2.1.3.1.18 JRP11-Med-Vet-Klebs

Set of activity		JRP11/R1/FBZ-4 Source attribution									
Project title		Klebsiella pneumoniae: from ecology to source attribution and transmission control									
Project acronym		Med-Vet-Klebs									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P20-Institut Pasteur (IP)			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)						
Project Coordinator person name		Sylvain Brisse (IP)			Project Deputy Leader person name						
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies:							2				
Project Start month			M1				Project End month			M24	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M	7.84	6								1	
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M	14.25						25.5	48.25			
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI	
P.M			4.78			18		3			
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
P.M											
Objectives											
The objectives in Year 2 will be to start the broad sampling from multiple sources; define the best sources to perform deep sampling; and perform genomic sequencing analyses and modelling of transmission among sources.											
Description of work											
WP1, Task 1.2											
Real-time PCR assays will then be evaluated for sensitivity and specificity from spiked matrices, first in simple matrices, then in more complex and relevant ones as defined in task 2.1. The limit of											

detection will be determined. The qPCR developed at INRA will be tested at Pasteur and IZSAM and validated protocols will be sent to all partners.

WP1, Task 1.3

An important objective of the project is to diffuse protocols and harmonize their use. This will be achieved through our scientific meeting of Month 13 through a dedicated session, by e-mail exchanges, by short bilateral visits of hired personnel and by exchange of staff between participating institutions.

WP2 will consist of sampling and evaluating of the prevalence and types of Kp in reservoirs and sources. It will encompass two complementary and temporally ordered approaches. First (T2.1), we will sample broadly in order to probe the presence of Kp in as many as possible relevant types of sources. This will provide comparative data on the occurrence of Kp in various types of samples and will lead to the identification of the most relevant potential sources in terms of transmission to animals and humans. In a second step (T2.2), we will focus our sampling on the most important sources of Kp in order to define precisely the prevalence of Kp in these sources, and quantify occurrence as a function of geography or other relevant parameters (processing, conservation). Finally (T2.3), selected Kp isolates from positive samples will be characterized for antimicrobial susceptibility and by genomic sequencing to define their subtype and harbored genes.

WP3 will deal with the analysis of genomic sequences, and the development of models of Kp transmission.

IN T3.1, we will deliver clonal subtypes and gene distribution in the sources, which will be used for transmission models refinement and testing. In task 3.2, we will improve current modelling methods and develop specific extensions, using two different approaches: (1) source attribution methods and (2) dynamic modelling.

WP4 will deal with overall coordination, management and dissemination

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP11-2.2	Prevalence in selected sources	18
D-JRP11-2.3	Prevalence in selected sources	24
D-JRP11-2.4	Quantification of Kp in selected sources	18
D-JRP11-2.5	Quantification of Kp in selected sources	24
D-JRP11-2.6	Genome sequence data	18
D-JRP11-2.7	Genome sequence data	24
D-JRP11-3.1	Source distribution of clonal groups, plasmids and genes	18
D-JRP11-3.2	Source distribution of clonal groups, plasmids and genes	24
D-JRP11-3.3	Source attribution models by microbial subtyping and comparative exposure assessment	24
D-JRP11-3.4	Computer program for dynamic models simulation	18
D-JRP11-3.5	Estimates of the attribution proportion for different food, animal and environmental sources for the countries included.	24
D-JRP11-3.6	Estimates of the relative contribution of different transmission routes for exposure to Kp in the different countries included.	24

D-JRP11-4.2	Project Periodic Reports	18
D-JRP11-4.5	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	24
D-JRP11-4.7	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results	18
D-JRP11-4.8	Final Report	24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP11-8	Initial prevalence, quantification and genomic data for model refining	18
M-JRP11-9	1st batch of clonal groups, plasmids and genes defined, for refinement of models	18
M-JRP11-10	Compilation and integration of the data produced in WP1 and WP2 to be used in the dynamic and source attribution models	18
M-JRP11-11	Identification of a list of scenarios for control measures to be assessed through model simulations	18
M-JRP11-12	Consolidated prevalence, quantification and genomic data for modeling of kp transmission	24
M-JRP11-13	Application of dynamic and source attribution models to data collected from different countries	24
M-JRP11-14	Reporting of transmission and source attribution estimates	24

2.1.3.1.19 JIP1-ORION

Set of activity		JIP1/R1/IA-1 Surveillance data - Standardised data									
Project title		One health surveillance Initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation									
Project acronym		ORION									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P09-BfR		Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)				P41-SVA			
Project Coordinator person name		Matthias Filter		Project Deputy Leader person name				Fernanda Dórea			
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies:								2			
Project Start month					M1			Project End month		M36	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M			8				39	21		21	
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M	23.67								7.34	4.65	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NIJG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI	
P.M								9.33	3.84	10.5	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAY	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M	14.5							10	35		
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft first version of “OH Surveillance Codex” guidance document • Enrich the “OH Knowledge Base – Epi” • Enrich the “OH Knowledge Base – NGS” • Enrich the “OH Knowledge Base – Integration” • Enrich the “OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub” • Create first draft of “Sustainability Roadmap” 											

- Start OH pilot studies

Description of work

WP:**WP2 – Integration**

WP2-Integration takes place over the first, second, and third annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: 12-DTU

Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI

WP participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA, 38-SVA

Description of the WP:

This WP2 has two main aims:

- 1) to ensure integration of the knowledge and methods generated by the two subWP2s – Epi / NGS to avoid duplications and maximise benefits of the project;
- 2) a pilot study to demonstrate integration of all disciplines.

Specifically, during the first year we will create an inventory on WP2-Integration on current integrated OH surveillance approaches in use in the EU. The inventory generated in this WP2 (OH Knowledge Base Integration) also cover current best practice guidelines and recommendations. To accomplish that this WP2 will carry out jointly with the other ORION WPs expert interviews. Finally this WP2 will carry out a GAP analyses to identify gaps and missing resources for reaching the OH integration and harmonization objective.

In a joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13) a “OH surveillance resource development plan” will be defined. This plan detail and synchronize the improvement work carried out in all WP2s. New or improved resources developed by this WP2 will be integrated into the OH Knowledge Base Integration.

In the third task this WP2 will carry out a pilot study that enhances OH surveillance on a specific topic, e.g. AMR. The pilot will not only integrate human, veterinary and food surveillance data, but also integrate the traditional disciplines with NGS from the work in the other WP2s. A specific objective of this OH pilot study is to ensure a robust, novel, future surveillance framework without losing the value of the historic data. The pilot study will try to use relevant outputs from all ORION WPs. WP2-Integration will further support the development of the “Sustainability Roadmap” (Task 4.3) in order to secure continued implementation and adoption of the “OH surveillance resource development plan” created by WP2 (M13).

Task T-2Int.2:**Improving OH Knowledge Base - Integration**

Task 2Int.2 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M13

Task end month: M24

Task Leader: 12-DTU

Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA, 38-SVA

Description of the task:

This task will develop a “OH surveillance resource development plan” for the OH surveillance data harmonization framework. The development plan will make use of existing tools already identified, and that each WP2 will start to develop lacking / unavailable OH resources. Decisions on the specific development tasks will be taken within a ORION prioritization workshop immediately after completion of the domain-specific GAP analyses (M13). The ORION integration workshop will prioritize and synchronize the WP2 development work across surveillance sub-domains. This task

will focus on developments in the area of data collection and integration, and data analysis and validation. Links to knowledge integration and decision making will also be established.

Task T-2Int.3: Integration OH pilot studies

Task 2Int.3 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7
Task end month: M30
Task Leader: 12-DTU
Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI
Task Participants: 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 33-NVI

Description of the task:

A multi-domain topic will be chosen, such as AMR, Listeria or VTEC/EHEC. This pilot will not only integrate human, veterinary and food surveillance, but also integrate the disciplines in WP2 – epidemiology, microbiology and novel genomic sequencing methods, to ensure a robust future surveillance system without losing the value of the historic data.

Phase1 (M7 - M12): Selection of the OH pilot study topic

Phase2 (M13 – M18): Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot. This includes: specification of targets, definition of performance indicators, identification and making available required data sources and software tools etc.

Phase3 (M19 – M30): Execution of the OH pilot - applying the resources from “OH Knowledge Base Integration”

WP: WP3 - OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure

WP3 takes place over the first, second, and third annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1
WP end month: M36
WP Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy WP Leader: 37-FOHM/PHA
WP participants: 9-BfR; 10-FLI, 12-DTU; 13-SSI; 20-APHA; 21-PHE; 31-RIVM; 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI; 37-FOHM/PHA; 38-SVA

Description of the WP:

WP3 will focus on identifying infrastructural resources which can support the harmonization and integration of existing methods to collect and analyse surveillance data. These infrastructural resources include - among others - data standards, software libraries, ontologies, terminology mappings, semantic networks, software tools. The specific development tasks to be carried out by WP3 will be identified by requirements expressed from WP1 (in relation to the “OH Surveillance Codex”), WP2 (supporting their developments) and through interviews of domain experts from other EJP partners and projects. Through the close interaction with WP1 and WP2 in the requirement analysis phase, WP3 will identify existing resources along the full surveillance data lifecycle. WP3 will inventory and where possible / required improve these tools and resources. The decision on the specific WP3 developments to be carried out in task 3.2 will be taken together with WP1 and WP2 during the joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13). In contrast to the other ORION WPs, this WP will focus on specifications for necessary data standards along the full surveillance data lifecycle – from annotation of analytical data, documentation of analytical methods, applied data processing and modelling steps to visualization of results. These proposed data standards will exploit the “One-Health Surveillance Ontology” also generated by this WP.

One or more pilots will allow for testing how the improved infrastructural resources, and in particular the proposed data standards, support the goal of surveillance data harmonisation. Based on the lessons-learned from these OH pilot studies WP3 will make necessary adjustments to their

developed resources and update the inventory of OH surveillance infrastructural resources that then becomes part of the “OHS Knowledge Hub” operated by WP4. Throughout the duration of the project WP3 will use workshops organized by WP4 to train other EJP projects and stakeholders and disseminate its knowledge. WP3 will further support the development of the “Sustainability Roadmap” (Task 4.3) in order to secure continued development of OH surveillance infrastructural resources.

Task T-3.2: Improving OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure

Task 3.2 takes place over the second annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M13
 Task end month: M24
 Task Leader: 9-BfR
 Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA
 Task Participants: 9-BfR; 10-FLI, 12-DTU; 13-SSI; 20-APHA; 21-PHE; 31-RIVM; 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI; 37-FOHM/PHA; 38-SVA

Description of the task:

Once harmonization resources are identified in Task 3.1, in Task 3.2 the existing resources will be adapted or improved to the specific ORION needs or if necessary missing infrastructural resources will be developed. Prioritization will be made together with the other ORION partners during the joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13) hosted by WP4. There the “OH surveillance resource development plan” will be defined, determining direct demands for infrastructural resources to be provided by WP3. This plan therefore drives the technical development work carried out by WP3 for WP2. E.g. it can clearly be delineated which data formats have to be harmonized or for which entities the One-Health Surveillance Ontology should be enriched. A second line of demand is generated by WP1, which needs infrastructural resources to facilitate the easy adoption of the proposed “OH Surveillance Codex”

These proposed standards will make use of the One-Health Surveillance Ontology, which will be an overarching goal of this task. While the duration of this task is very short compared to the time necessary to build an ontology, this task will focus on developing the main data model for the ontology. It will also build the collaboration model for the work, setting the necessary user and application programme interfaces necessary to collaboratively maintain and access the ontology, validating the cycles of development with pilot modules of the ontology, and establishing the community necessary to continue the work beyond the extension of the project. Where necessary, workshops to train partners and external community members will be carried out through WP4 (coordination and training).

Sub-Task sT-3.2.1 (M13 – M24): Systematic compilation and further development of infrastructural harmonisation resources - supporting high priority needs identified in WP2

Sub-Task Leader: 13-SSI
 Sub-Task Participants: 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 38-SVA

Sub-Task sT-3.2.2 (M13 – M24): Systematic compilation and further development of infrastructural resources - supporting high priority needs identified in WP1

Sub-Task Leader: 38-SVA
 Sub-Task Participants: 9-BfR, 38-SVA

Task T-3.3: One Health pilot

Task 3.3 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7
 Task end month: M30

Task Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy Task Leader: 37-FOHM/PHA
Task Participants: 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA; 38-SVA

Description of the task:

The OH pilot aims at illustrating the usefulness and the added value of the infrastructural resources collected and improved within this WP. The pilot will be carried out by a veterinary health partner (National Veterinary Institute (SVA)) and a public health partner (National Public Health Agency (FoHM) of Sweden). Other participating institutions will be encouraged to join the OH pilot. The pilot will also assess the sustainability value of newly developed infrastructural resources when applied across domains.

Phase (M7 - M12): Selection of the OH pilot study topic which will be a zoonotic agent from the following four candidates that have already been pre-selected by the WP partners: Campylobacter, Salmonella, VTEC/EHEC, and Listeria.

Phase (M13 – M18): Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot. This includes: specification of targets, definition of performance indicators, identification and making available required data sources and software tools etc.

Phase (M19 – M30): Execution of the OH pilot - applying resources from the OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub

WP: WP4 - Coordination, Communication, Training and Sustainability

WP4 takes place over the first, second, and third annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1
WP end month: M36
WP Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy WP Leader: 38-SVA
WP participants: all ORION partners

Description of the WP:

This WP integrates all horizontal project activities including the coordination of internal and external communication, the set-up of shared technical resources (Wiki's, web-based OHS Knowledge Hub, software code repositories etc.), and the development of a "Sustainability Roadmap" paving the way to broad adoption of project results in future European surveillance practice. This WP will also organize all cross-WP workshops (M4, M13, M33) and promote wider group assessment / validation of findings at critical points in the project. The training and dissemination activities organized by this WP will promote knowledge exchange between project partners as well as other EJP partners and projects. Special focus will be given to the synchronization with the other(s) EJP Integrative action project(s), funded under IA-2. All external communication and knowledge transfer activities will be integrated into the overarching activities carried out by EJP WP5 "Science to Policy Translation". This includes promotion of knowledge transfer to responsible entities (e.g. EU reference laboratories, EFSA, ECDC) and international statutory bodies.

Task T-4.1: Internal project coordination

Task 4.1 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M1
Task end month: M36
Task Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA
Task Participants: all ORION partners

Description of the task:

This task takes responsibility for and effective project coordination. This will be facilitated by hosting monthly full consortia conference calls / WebEx meetings, one full consortia project meeting and dedicated cross-WP workshops in month 4, 13, and 33 to promote synchronized decision making and development within the ORION project. This task also disseminates duties to corresponding partners and keeps track of timely provisioning of partner's deliverables. Further it will manage the creation of yearly project reports.

Task T-4.2: External project integration (synchronized with EJP WP5)

Task 4.2 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M1
Task end month: M36
Task Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR
Task Participants: all ORION partners

Description of the task:

This task will deal with the coordination of *collaboration* with other EJP initiatives, and also *support* to other projects. We will *support* other funded EJP initiatives in two main ways: by including these projects in the phase of requirement analysis, for all WPs, so that they have a chance to contribute their views on current gaps and opportunities for OH integration; and by providing training (see specific training tasks below). The requirement analysis is also a point of close collaboration in the work to be carried out. We foresee that many projects may plan to conduct tasks similar to ORION's requirement analysis, and partner interviews. We suggest that integration with other projects will be needed to maximize resources, and avoid reducing the quality of survey responses due to an excessive number of questionnaires being mailed to EJP partners. Further, the results of this project should be closely tied to the Integrative Area 2, so that the accomplishments in integration of data collection and analysis can be in line with the issues of knowledge integration and decision making.

Task T-4.3: Sustainability roadmap

Task 4.3 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7
Task end month: M36
Task Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA
Task Participants: all ORION partners

Description of the task:

Sustainability issues will arise throughout the project, in all WPs, and in all tasks. For this reason, it has been assigned to the coordination to follow and document raised issues of sustainability, whether legal or technical. Budget has been planned for legal and technical consultation, where needed, in order to inform potential solutions to sustainability issues, and trace a road map of sustainability for the integration of data and methods in a OH surveillance context. The final "Sustainability Roadmap" document will be created based on the results of the joint ORION Evaluation workshop hold in M33. This document will give recommendations on how the "ORION OH surveillance data harmonization framework" with all its components should be consolidated by EJP partners and European veterinary and public health agencies in the future.

Task T-4.4: Training and Dissemination

Task 4.4 takes place over the first, second and third annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M1
Task end month: M36
Task Leader: 38-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR
 Task Participants: all ORION partners
 Description of the task:
 This task will be concerned with planning and conducting, throughout the project, training that aims at sharing the knowledge already available within the consortium among all partners, training partners in the use of new tools produced/adopted, and disseminating results and training external partners in the adoption of tools and guidelines published by ORION. All partners have assigned a minimum of 2PM to training, so that they can take part in the activities listed below – receiving training, training others, or helping with dissemination activities.

Sub-Task sT-4.4.1 (M1- M12): Internal training (sharing knowledge on currently available national solutions)
 Sub-Task Leader: 9-BfR
 Sub-Task Participants: all ORION partners
 Description of the task:
 During the first year 2 workshops are planned in order to integrate knowledge available within the partner institutions. As the requirement analysis progresses, we will identify capacity already available in some partners, and carry out workshops to allow partners to train each other on their tools of expertise.

Sub-Task sT-4.4.2 (M7 – M36): Knowledge integration (web portal, Wiki, curricula, tutorials, videos, sample data)
 Sub-Task Leader: 9-BfR
 Sub-Task Participants: all ORION partners
 Description of the task:
 All WPs have tangible outcomes that are meant to benefit the surveillance community - e.g. the OH Surveillance Codex from WP1, the OH surveillance data inventories with validated tools in WP2, the ontology generated in WP3. This task will oversee the production of dissemination means, while training will be provided in the following Sub-Task. Workshops and webinars to the overall public are planned to the last year of project, while permanent dissemination means – such as videos and a wiki – will guarantee access to the project outcomes after the conclusion of the project. Particular emphasis is given to the “OHS Knowledge Hub”, which will be a repository of all the tools and guidelines produced in the project.

Sub-Task sT-.4.4.3 (M7 - M36): Training and support for other EJP projects & partners
 Sub-Task start month: M7
 Sub-Task end month: M36
 Sub-Task Leader: 38-SVA
 Sub-Task Participants: all ORION partners
 Description of the task:
 Training on all the guidelines, framework, and tools produced as part of ORION will be provided to other interested EJP partners. Two dedicated training workshops for external EJP project members are planned for the third year.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JIP1-1.2	Draft on OH Surveillance Codex	M24
D-JIP1-2.4	Status report on OH Knowledge Base – Epi	M24
D-JIP1-2.5	Status report on OH Knowledge Base - NGS	M24

D-JIP1-2.6	Status report on OH Knowledge Base - Integration	M24
D-JIP1-3.2	Status report on OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub	M24
D-JIP1-4.2	Draft on Sustainability Roadmap	M18
D-JIP1-4.3	Two training workshops for other EJP	M24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JIP1-2	ORION prioritization workshop	M15

2.1.3.1.20 JIP2-COHESIVE

Set of activity		JIP2/R1/IA-2 Joint platform for sharing surveillance data									
Project title		One Health Structure In Europe									
Project acronym		COHESIVE									
Coordinator institute (number and acronym)		P30-RIVM			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym)			31-WBVR			
Project Coordinator person name		Kitty Maassen			Project Deputy Leader person name			Hendrik-Jan Roest			
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies:								2			
Project Start month				M1			M36				
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agés	Sciensan	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M		1.67	2.7				31.9	1.5		0.25	
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M									5.95	1.28	
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI	
P.M					4.9	49	9	14	4.7	8.36	
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M	3.9						3	1.6	8.6		
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulating sustainable One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries, focussing on strengthening human-veterinary collaboration with respect to early signalling and assessing zoonotic threats. • Roadmap towards an EU zoonoses risk-assessment or risk-analysis structure • Design and test a common platform for the collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on foodborne zoonoses. • Capacity building within and between EU countries at several levels within the area of zoonotic diseases 											
Description of work											

WP1 Coordination, communication and sustainability

WP start month: 1

WP end month: 36

WP Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy WP Leader: Hendrik-Jan Roest, WBVR

WP participants: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM, SVA: All actively involved in this WP. All other project partners will have a reactive role in this WP, such as attending annual meetings.

Description of the WP: WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The objective of this WP is to coordinate the activities of the partners as described in the various WPs and ensure the smooth running of the project. This also includes overseeing the links between the WPs and assist with linking to other projects within the EJP and outside. The project is aiming at sustainable products (risk analysis structures, collaborations, data platform). The steering group will stimulate partners and associate partners to reach for those goals. Within this WP also internal and external communication is coordinated.

Task: T-1.1 Coordination

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 36

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: Hendrik-Jan Roest, WBVR

Task Participants: WP (deputy)leaders: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task: Task 1.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The RIVM is project coordinator and responsible for the project management and leading the steering group. WBVR (formerly CVI) will be deputy task-leader to ensure a good follow-up and management of the task. WBVR will remain the first sparring partner of the coordinator to discuss upcoming problems with. A steering group is formed consisting of the WP-leaders and deputy WP-leaders. To ensure efficient progress within the WPs, a teleconference is organized every six weeks. They will have at least one meeting per year, when possible coupled to the overarching project. The steering group will steer upon the completion of deliverables in time and reaching the milestones (in time). Complete and timely reporting to the EJP management team is a joined responsibility of the steering group with final responsibility lying with the project coordinator. The project coordinator will liaise with the overarching EJP management. Important is also to oversee possibilities to connect activities between different WPs, look for opportunities to involve external organisations, such as EFSA and ECDC and link to other (EU) projects. The steering group can stimulate and facilitate to act upon such opportunities.

Task: Communication/dissemination

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 36

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: Hendrik-Jan Roest, WBVR

Task Participants: WP (deputy)leaders: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task : Task 1.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Within this task internal project communication is coordinated in close collaboration with task T-1.1. An annual meeting will be organized in the beginning of 2019 for all partners. In the meeting, general project issues will be discussed and progression in the WPs is

shared and discussed. In view of efficiency, a steering group meeting will be coupled to the annual meeting. In addition, there is also the possibility to combine steering group meetings with workshops or other meetings organized within other WPs. A general EJP One Health website has been developed. This website does have the possibilities for private groups. At least two groups will be set up. One group for (secure) exchange of information between members of the steering group and one to inform all Cohesive members. Possibly also WPs within Cohesive will set up a group to exchange information. In addition, we will develop opportunities to disseminate information to the public, most likely via the public area of the website. Targeted dissemination of information will be also defined, to address specific stakeholders with project progress and main results/deliverables. Concerning sustainability, basic activities such website maintenance, networking with partners will be planned to continue after the end of the project. The main tools and procedures developed will be disseminated not only among the project partners but also to other national/international institutions/organizations potentially interested in the activities, favouring the further development of the tools and the extended networking.

WP2. Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy WP Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

WP participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, ISZ AM, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, FOHM/PHA.

Description of the WP: WP2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The objective of this WP is to provide common procedures and tools that can be used to improve the human veterinary collaboration in the area of (emerging) zoonosis or even implement a sustainable integrated One Health structure at the national level. Examples of best practise methods will be used to design common procedures and tools, but also differences between countries and barriers for efficient collaboration will be taken into account as well. Importantly, the project will facilitate in the first step of creating support for a One Health structure by organizing local workshops with national stakeholders. In addition, a systematic way to select good tools to help assess zoonotic threats will be developed to be used within the One Health structures.

Task: T-2.1 Development of guidelines for national One Health structures

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M26

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, ISZ AM, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, FOHM/PHA

Description of the Task: Task 2.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. First, an inventory will be made of current practice of One Health risk analysis (structures) at the national level. This will be done based upon the results obtained from the workshop organized in November 2018, which was accessible to all project partners, EJP partners and EU countries outside the consortium. This workshop (in year 1) will focus on current practice on human-veterinary collaboration, risk analysis and good practice, but also aims to reveal barriers to good practise, such as technical, political barriers, legal issues, logistics, difference in interests (economic versus health), difference in terminology and privacy. In this workshop also national goals and ambitions to improve the integration of human-veterinary risk-analysis will be inventoried. The

next step is to organize thematic workshops to discuss and progress towards possible solutions for the most important barriers as identified within the first workshop. This WP will be in close collaboration with WP3, because of similar issues arise on European level. All information gathered will be used to develop guidelines for setting-up/improving a national One Health structure. The guidelines should provide information, checklists and procedures/approaches, taking into account the specifics of countries. The guidelines will also contain suggestions on how to incorporate and use the national information system and tracing framework to be developed in WP4. The products developed will be publically available and will be used as input for task 3 of this WP and in WP3.

Task: T-2.2 Development of structured decision making

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 18

Task Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, , FOHM/PHA

Description of the Task: Task 2.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Rapid risk-assessments of threats are merely based on expert opinion. This expert knowledge is, however, subjective. Several tools for priority setting for communicable infectious diseases surveillance, epidemiological research, and national notification have been proposed in literature. These tools are commonly based on a set of criteria assessed by a Delphi process or qualitative algorithm. After a fruitful discussion during the kick-off meeting the aim of this task has been adjusted to the development of a tool to support risk assessors when deciding on the most suitable tool to use in risk assessment. Therefore, the milestone 2.1 has been changed to 'Development of prototype decision support tool for selection of risk assessment system' and extended to month 24. In order to achieve that, following completion of the questionnaire in Y1 the resulting inventory will be used in the development of this structured decision making tool. Y2 will produce a prototype of a tool to support risk assessors when deciding on the most suitable tool to use in risk assessment. Therefore, there will be a close collaboration with WP3 to ensure tools identified within Y1 are included in the inventory where appropriate. As the tool will be designed for risk assessors from a variety of backgrounds, the project team, and some outside experts, will be asked to test the prototype and provide feedback to make improvements. Finalisation of the tool will be focused in Y3. Meanwhile, the prototype tool will be tested against a selected range of zoonosis threats. The prototype tools developed will be publically available on request and will be used as input for task 2.3.

WP3.Towards an EU zoonoses structure

WP start month 1

WP end month 36

WP Leader: Elina Lathi, SVA

Deputy WP Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

WP participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, AGES.

Description of the WP: WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The overall aim of the workpackage is to bring together existing risk analysis and epidemiological tools, skills and facilities that are required for a 'one-health' approach with respect to zoonotic diseases in Europe. One of the main tasks will be in assessing the barriers encountered by risk analysis experts and surveillance experts to collaborate across country

borders and recommending changes to be made to overcome them and ensure that experts have access to the tools and data (see WP4) that are needed to provide a comprehensive risk analysis and surveillance. As much progress in this area has already been made by some partners, a literature search will be undertaken to include white papers and informal reports and experiences by partners and other institutes. Identifying good practice throughout this area will require maintaining a knowledge base that is constantly curated by experts and subject to scrutiny both within and outside the project. The aims of work package 3 will be delivered via 5 tasks:

Task: T-3.1 Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines - pathway analysis

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: Elina Lathi, SVA

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task: Task 3.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This task will encourage all interested partners to build on the results of the workshop held in November 2016 and thematic workshops of WP 2.1. Interested partners will be asked to nominate person(s) from the thematic workshops to attend an EU level workshop to collate the information on data sharing and barriers to sharing at an EU level. This may include formal disease/pathogen surveillance systems, like regulated surveillance, such as that of Salmonella in poultry, or informal systems for newly identified threats. By identifying key processes, people, roles and responsibilities in each country a contact network consisting of the veterinary and human side will be built up that will make it easier to identify the counterparts within all the partners involved. The aim of these professional networks is to enable more efficient and timely response to threats by exchanging both formal and informal communications and signals on emerging zoonotic issues. The work in this task will also include identifying specific barriers to relevant data sharing; these may be legal barriers to releasing sensitive data or infrastructure. This will be closely aligned to WP4 where the infrastructure platform to share information will be designed and developed. Where internal project expertise cannot resolve issues it may be possible to commission external expertise to find a working solution or advise on alternative actions. The partners of the workpackage will have a close contact with the Compare project for legal implications of data sharing. This workpackage will work closely with WP2 and WP4. Contacts with ECDC are made and we will be involved in given suggestions for the new ETMS (event threat and management solution) and testing it.

Task: T-3.2 Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 24

Task Leader: Rickard Knutsson, SVA

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task: Task 2.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP and will be finalised in year 2. The task will identify and share information on various One Health horizon scanning approaches. An inventory of medium and long term horizon scanning methods will provide recommendations for future developments. In addition, the task

will concentrate of some of the analytical tools that are available both within and between partners involved. We will carry out an inventory of the automated signal detection methods already in use or under development for syndromic surveillance and other data types collected. Thus, an analysis of the different types of data currently being monitored will be done and specifically, how generic the algorithms are and if they could be applied to other data. Data users, who get notified of anomalies in data are included in this analysis. In addition, the escalation/review points are included. Whether methods could be easily exchanged between countries and cross domains will be looked at using free online repositories for analysis methods, such as Docker, GitHub and the R-project. An element of temporal & spatial analysis where the data allow. This task will be running in parallel with Task 2.2 in workpackage 2 to ensure that both short term and long term risk assessment tools are available to EU partners and can be used both nationally and internationally. We will not include an analysis of NGS data as this has been covered within other work packages and EU funded projects.

Task: 3.3 Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks

Task start month: 6

Task end month: 30

Task Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task: Task 3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. Following the workshop in Y1, with relevant participants identified in the inventory of the project as well as the listed partners, a systems map of selected risk analysis systems will be used to identify certain key areas that are strong in identifying zoonotic pathogens of concern. Between country comparisons will be made to identify areas that consistently perform well in analysing zoonotic threats or provide key hubs of communications. Such analysis will aim to identify strengths and weaknesses in current surveillance systems whilst building relationships and cross -country/-department knowledge of surveillance systems and institutional knowledge. The extension of this task is the development of a pilot into task 3.4.

WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M36

WP Leader: Armando

Giovannini, IZSAM

Deputy WP Leader: Armin Weiser, BfR

WP participants: BfR, FLI, IZS, FHI/NIPH, NVI, NFA, PHE, IZSLER, ISS, WBVR, FOHM/PHA, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, AGES

Description of the WP: WP4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. WP4 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The aim of this platform is to provide IT tools and data that are quickly available, usable and helpful in outbreak situations and for risk assessments. Especially tools for tracing, WGS and standardized risk assessments are established, harmonized and improved. All tools are planned to be developed into one software platform which will be available in the cloud to be evaluated during the project. These tools will be tested in a subset of the country involved in the project, willing to participate in the experimentation and to provide test data. The countries in this subset will be called "participating

countries" thereafter.

WP4 as a whole is going to spread the usage of this set of tools (genetics, analysis, tracing and risk assessment tools) via workshops, interactive online courses and also bilateral courses and historical data applications with all partners including EFSA and ECDC. The aim is that it is usable by everyone – for local, but also for international outbreaks.

WP4 will take care of synchronization with other projects, especially IA-1: ORION and the other work packages WP2 and WP3. The development of other tools/data structures will be supported.

The ownership and privacy of data is a major important point when providing central software platforms. The data protection procedures will be evaluated case by case, on the basis of the contents of the national databases of participating countries.

WP4 will be very aware of this fact and will take care of integrated solutions for this in collaboration with WP3.

The COHESIVE project will provide a reasoned list of the available Information Systems for WGS data (NGS raw data and output of additional bioinformatics analysis) and associated meta data. This reasoned list will include the specifications of the available databases (data structures, etc.) and pros and cons of each information system. This reasoned list can be used by Member States to build up their own official system. Thus, it is anticipated the possibility of different implementations of the Information System for WGS data and associated meta data at Member States level. Such different implementations, however, should be harmonized and able to exchange their information at the European level. Specific task of the COHESIVE project will be to foster the harmonization and to implement the exchange tools for the various information systems implemented (or experimented) at the national level. No new databases will be produced by COHESIVE, but support is given to combine available databases into practical Information Systems, within Member States.

Task: T-4.1 Molecular typing data and metadata – database implementation

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M32

Task Leader: Cesare Cammà,

IZSAM Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, FHI/NIPH, FLI, IZS-AM, IZS-LER, ISS, NVI, WBVR

Description of the task: Task T-4.1 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The adoption of WGS is becoming more and more widespread and it is progressively replacing older techniques (e.g. PFGE) for the definition of the links between cases within an outbreak and to link cases with their putative sources. What is missing is a link to be promptly used to connect results of WGS with other information on the various components of an outbreak: human cases, contaminated foods, pathway of contamination along the food processing chain, environmental conditions, location, etc.

The activities of this task will be based on the results of a set of activities and projects now ongoing at the EU level (ORION, COMPARE, EFSA and ECDC activities), which will give the outlines for the standardization of the databases to be used in European countries. Based on the specifications given by EFSA and ECDC, national databases will be experimentally implemented in this WP, able to feed data into a common European database and useful for the experimentation of epidemiological analysis of WGS data at the national level. In the lack of usable databases, for the sake of the fulfilling of the objectives of this project, prototype databases will be implemented, completely in compliance with the European standards set by EFSA and ECDC. EFSA/ECDC WGS mandate will be monitored in order to ensure that the final data models proposed by COHESIVE will be compliant with EFSA/ECDC WGS system.

For a more detailed description of the prototype system to be experimented, we will make reference to the architecture of the information systems relevant for our tasks already implemented in Italy (as a paradigmatic example of a member state), and with which we need to interface.

A set of databases are already operative in Italy (see diagram A1, buckets colored in blue for genetic data and yellow for metadata and other data useful for health purposes):

1. The database of the strains of pathogens isolated from human beings and clinical cases, including the genetic typing of these strains when available. This database is at the Italian national health institute (ISS), one of the partners of COHESIVE.
2. The databases of the strains of pathogens isolated from animals, food and the environment, including the genetic typing of these strains when available. These databases are mainly at the Italian national laboratories for the pathogens. The IZSAM is NRL for *Campylobacter* and has been recently appointed as the National Reference Centre for Whole Genome Sequencing of microbial pathogens: database and bioinformatics analysis.
The databases in (1) and (2) also include metadata directly related to each isolate (date, place, name of the patient or holding code, etc.)
3. The databases of the animal holdings and of animal movements, which contain the complete register of active animal holdings and the Italian animal trade networks. These databases are hosted in the servers at IZSAM.
4. The database of the food companies and plants, which is incomplete, contains only the main companies, especially those involved in the intra-community trade and in export to third countries. No data are readily available of the food trade networks. To be useful in outbreak investigations, therefore, this database needs to be integrated with ad hoc investigations in the case of an outbreak.

Another very important database with which the COHESIVE information system has to interface is the EU Joint DB EFSA/ECDC (colored in blue and with an EU flag in the diagrams).

The core of the prototype we are proposing to develop is the Prototype COHESIVE Information System (the bucket coloured in red in the diagrams). The Prototype COHESIVE Information System is not a database with data of its own, rather it is a collection of procedures, queries, indexes, pipelines, needed to link all the other relevant and already existing databases each other. In some cases, to speed up tracing activities and analyses, part of the data stored in the national databases or in the EU joint DB, could be temporarily downloaded to the Prototype COHESIVE Information System.

One of the tasks of the Prototype COHESIVE Information System will be to harmonize and feed the genetic typing data produced at the national level into the EU Joint DB EFSA/ECDC. It is, therefore, interfaced with the national databases and the EU Joint DB.

It also has a number of other important tasks:

1. It will perform bioinformatic analysis on the data stored in the national Clinical/Human isolates DB and in the Animal/Food/Environment isolates DBs. Through these analyses, it may produce (see diagram A2, outputs) periodic reports on
 - a. AMR profiles and trends in AMR,
 - b. virulence profiles,
 - c. phyloGIS (geographic distribution of genetic profiles)
 - d. movements of genetic profiles in the trade network
 - e. clustering (phylogenetic trees)
2. In the case of an outbreak without involvement of other European countries (diagram A2, outputs), the Prototype COHESIVE Information System will feed the systems for epidemiological analysis and tracing developed by the Task 4.2 (coloured in green in the diagrams) with the relevant data stored in the National databases. The aim of this activity

is to trace the origin of the outbreak (and possibly foresee its potential spread through the trade network).

3. In the case of an outbreak involving other EU member countries (diagram A3, EU outbreak), the linking of the Prototype COHESIVE Information System with the EU Joint DB EFSA/ECDC and with systems like TRACES may facilitate the transboundary outbreak investigation (not included as a possible output of COHESIVE).

In conclusion, it is important to underline that no official EU wide system will be implemented. On the contrary, a study on the best possible integration of different information systems at member state level will be provided: for both WGS information, and associated metadata.

The final output of such study will be some Information system specifications. A member state could then realize an official national information system based on such specifications. The advantage will be that different systems among member states will be harmonized.

NATIONAL INFORMATION SYSTEMS

[Diagram A1: National information systems]

[Diagram A2: Outputs]

[Diagram A3: EU Outbreaks]

This task is subdivided into 6 sub-tasks, which will be realized at the national level by the Member countries and institutions involved in this WP:

Sub-Task sT4.1.1 - Workshop on data and DBs

Sub-Task start month M1

Sub-Task end month M12

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, Bfr, FLI, NVI, ISS, FHI/NIPH

Sub-task T-4.1.1 took place over the first annual period of the EJP. The first sub-task included a workshop to collect data on what already exists in the European countries participating to the

project and a subsequent review of the collected information. The workshop took into consideration: Databases for molecular epidemiology investigations and for classical epidemiological investigations, and Tools for investigations (Milestone M-IA2.COHESIVE.4.1). Also, the results of examples of investigations performed in Europe to assess the origin and the extent of outbreaks of food-borne zoonoses were collected, which took advantage of molecular epidemiology methods. Finally, in this initial workshop, a few (1-3) pathogens are chosen to be used in a pilot study aimed at the testing and validation of the tools implemented in WP4.

The workshop was postponed to November of Y1, so it could be held together with the workshop of WP2/WP3. The analysis of the available data was continued after the workshop until M12 and will provide the necessary background for all the activities of task 4.1.

Sub-Task sT4.1.2: Design and implementation of DBs

Sub-Task start month M6

Sub-Task end month M22

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, Bfr, FLI, NVI, FHI/NIPH

Sub-task T-4.1.2 takes place over the first and second annual period of the EJP. The activity of the project subsequent to the workshop will be the production of the reasoned list of the available Information Systems for WGS data (NGS raw data and output of additional bioinformatics analysis) and associated meta data. This reasoned list will include the specifications of the available databases (data structures, etc.) and pros and cons of each information system. The Member States and institutions willing to experiment on the use of genetic data for the outbreak investigations will decide, based on this list, the characteristics and specifications of their own information system.

This activity will start after the review of the available data and will take from M6 to the end of M22. The implemented Prototype COHESIVE information system will be the first deliverable of task 4.1 (D-4.1.1). The availability of these databases will be a further milestone of this project (M-IA2.COHESIVE.4.4).

Sub-Task sT4.1.3: Interconnection of the available systems within a Member State

Sub-Task start month M13

Sub-Task end month M21

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, Bfr, FLI, NVI

Sub-task T-4.1.3 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP and refers to the interconnections between the National DBs available in those Member States and institutions willing to experiment on the use of genetic data for the outbreak investigations. This sub-task is aimed at connecting the three databases, so that metadata is properly connected to the relevant WGS information, and data collected on patients without a genetic typing of their pathogens may be, whenever possible, linked to the relevant cluster of pathogen genomes.

This sub-task will need 9 months to be completed and will generate the second deliverable of task 4.1 (D-4.1.2), the description of the links and the linked databases. The conclusion of this sub-task will be monitored using the Milestone M-IA2.COHESIVE.4.5

Sub-Task sT4.1.4: Analysis of the systems in the participating countries

Sub-Task start month M13

Sub-Task end month M25

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, Bfr, FLI, NVI, FHI/NIPH

Sub-task T-4.1.4 This sub-task is an integration of sub-task 4.1.3 and takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP. The national databases already existing in the participating countries, interconnected each other by sub-task 4.1.3, need to be connected also to the Prototype COHESIVE information system. The Prototype COHESIVE information system is harmonized with the EFSA and ECDC joint database. The connection of the already existing national DBs with the Prototype COHESIVE information system will be realized by sub-task 4.1.5. Propaedeutic to this connection is an analysis of the systems in each participating country, including the type of data stored, the semantic of these data and how these data can be translated/transformed to fulfil the standards defined for this project. This analysis is the core of sub-task 4.1.4, will take one year and is necessary for the proper linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system, and the epidemiological analysis tools.

Sub-Task sT4.1.5: Linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the epidemiological analysis tools

Sub-Task start month M15

Sub-Task end month M26

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, IZS-LER, FLI, ISS, NVI

Sub-Task T-4.1.5 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP. In this sub-task, based on the analysis performed in sub-task 4.1.4, we will implement the procedures necessary to link the national DBs relevant for this project (WGS, metadata and classical epidemiology) with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the tools for the epidemiological analysis of the data contained in the DBs. As far as possible, and depending on the priorities of each participating country, the data used to test the system will refer to the paradigmatic pathogens chosen during the initial workshop. The amount of time allocated for this activity is because of possible unexpected difficulties faced during the linking of data, which are very likely to occur every time data are translated and migrated between two different systems.

This sub-task will produce the third deliverable of the task 4.1 (D-4.1.3): Databases containing the country data linked to the epidemiological analysis tools realized by tasks 4.2 and 4.3. The conclusion of this sub-task will be monitored using the Milestone M-IA2.COHESIVE.4.7

Sub-Task sT4.1.6: Study of available pipelines

Sub-Task start month M21

Sub-Task end month M32

Sub-Task Participants: IZS-AM, Bfr, FLI, NVI

Sub-task T-4.1.6 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP. The final sub-task of task 4.1 is the Design and implementation of the pipelines to feed the tools for epidemiological analysis from the relevant DBs by those Member States and institutions willing to experiment on the use of genetic data for the outbreak investigations.

The first step will be a survey of available bioinformatics analysis (pipelines) and, in particular, the output format. Consequently, the output format will follow a flexible data model, able to accept the results of pipelines used by different laboratories around Europe. No design of additional pipelines is foreseen in the project. This sub-task will be performed in close cooperation with the units at BfR responsible for tasks 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4. This sub-task will produce the fourth deliverable of task 4.1 (D-4.1.4), consisting in the description of the pipelines implemented to feed the analysis tools with the data stored in the three databases of this project.

The conclusion of this sub-task will be monitored using the Milestone M-IA2.COHESIVE.4.9

Task: T-4.2 Development of a platform-independent tracing framework

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M32

Task Leader: Armin Weiser, BfR

Deputy Task Leader: Birgit Lewicki, BfR

Task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, NVI, ISS, FOHM/PHA

Description of the task: Task 4.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This task is going to combine and improve available tracing algorithms with analysis and visualization of WGS data into modern software integrating surveillance and outbreak data. Within this task a server system will be provided freely offering all developed tools browser-ready and open source.

The server will run on a Linux machine and the framework used is a Node.js / Angular framework providing secure areas for sensitive data. The server will be available worldwide for modern browsers, which mainly mean that only very old versions of common browsers are excluded, but the Internet Explorer is completely excluded.

Sub-Task sT4.2.2

Sub-Task start month

M1

Sub-Task end month

M32

Sub-task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

Sub-task 4.2.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. This subtask is mainly a software programming and algorithm developing task. It seems as if FoodChain-Lab (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de>) is the state of the art tracing tool in Europe supporting quick supply chain data gathering and fastening in solving outbreak investigations. FoodChain-Lab has some room for improvements, e.g. eased availability and implementation of additional algorithms like traditional network analysis or modelling on the spread of germs along the collected supply chains. Therefore, a cloud-based browser-ready and user-friendly tracing tool based on FoodChain-Lab will be developed.

The deliverable of this subtask is the ready-to-use tool with integrated network analysis module.

Sub-Task sT4.2.3

Sub-Task start month

M13

Sub-Task end month

M32

Sub-task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, ISS

Sub-task T-4.2.3 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP. This subtask takes care of the integration of even more meaningful surveillance and outbreak data into the software platform for analysis. Especially for 4.2.2, further data sources from MED- and VET-side, like cases, sampling results and also analysis results based on WGS-data from WP4.1 are going to be implemented resulting in a new algorithm based on probabilities for the

scoring of common sources of an outbreak.

This subtask does also take care of the synchronization with IA-1: ORION and WPs 2 and 3. Selected promising tools will be taken into account for integration into the software platform of WP4. Especially, Task5 from WP3 seems promising, and it may come out that Task3 also develops into a candidate for the platform.

The deliverable of this subtask is the ready-to-use tool with extended WGS-Epi module and a report on additionally needed tools.

Task: T-4.3 Development of a platform-independent risk modelling framework

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Matthias Greiner, BfR

Deputy Task Leader: Christine Müller-Graf, BfR

Task Participants: BfR, FHI/NIPH, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

Description of the task: Task 4.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the EJP. The risk modelling framework will provide a flexible support to conduct high-end statistical modelling and simulation (including two-dimensional Monte Carlo and Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis) with automatic reporting and model documentation, modular structure and options for using pre-defining templates for parts of the model. Risk scenarios defined in other task groups are considered as use cases.

The graphical user interface for risk modelling will be developed and implemented with shiny R package to build an interactive web app. The app will hosted on BfR webpage and server. Moreover, all scientific code will be made available under open source license model.

Sub-Task sT4.3.2 Implementation

Sub-Task start month

M10

Sub-Task end month

M30

Sub-task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

Sub-task T-4.3.2 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the EJP.

- a. implementation of standards and specific tasks of the risk modelling framework, including automated thorough documentation of the risk model,
- b. GUI implementation,
- c. technical documentation and user guidance.

Sub-Task sT4.3.3 Validation of the risk modelling framework

Sub-Task start month M19

Sub-Task end month M33

Sub-task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, IZS-LER, FHI/NIPH, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP

Sub-task T-4.3.3 takes place over the second and third annual period of the EJP.

- a. Defining testing scenarios for verification and validation for each programme module,
- b. Testing using testing scenarios and benchmarking (i.e. runtime),
- c. Comparison with external programmes when available.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JIP2-1.3	Annual meeting	14
D-JIP2-1.4	Annual report	16
D-JIP2-2.3	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18
D-JIP2-2.4	Thematic workshops	20
D-JIP2-3.2	Thematic workshops	20
D-JIP2-3.4	Inventory and analysis of tools for horizon scanning	18
D-JIP2-3.5	System analysis of detection of outbreaks	24
D-JIP2-4.1	implemented database	17
D-JIP2-4.2	description of the links and the linked databases	21
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JIP2-5	Annual report	16
M-JIP2-6	Databases for WGS data consistent with COMPARE standards, for the metadata of the samples included in the WGS database, and for the data collected by classical epidemiology investigations (case-control studies)	17
M-JIP2-7	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18
M-JIP2-8	Fully operating and linked databases	21
M-JIP2-9	Pathway and system analysis of signal exchange and outbreak detection	24
M-JIP2-10	Prototype for tracing framework ready	24

2.1.3.1.21 ET5-PEMbo

Set of activity		PhD/R1/E-5 Emerging threat – Ecology of emerging pathogens									
PhD full title		From genotype to phenotype: patho-evolution of French strains of <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> .									
PhD acronym		PEMbo									
PhD host institute (number and acronym)		P01-ANSES			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym) (if any)			NA			
PhD Coordinator person name		Boschioli Maria Laura			Project Deputy Leader person name (if any)			NA			
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3 or Y4)							2				
PhD Start month				M13			Project End month			M48	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M	12										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M											
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	WBVR	FHI	
P.M											
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M											
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtaining reference sequences by Illumina / PacBio sequencing of strains belonging to main clonal groups • Identification of genomic events (insertion / deletion or broad sequence polymorphism (LSP)) by comparison study of genetic variation: analysis focused on the study of 182 virulence genes, genes involved in envelope biosynthesis and the study of excreted antigens. • Study of the antigenic variation: biochemical and lipidomic analyses of the strains 											
Description of work											

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups

WP1 start month: M13

WP1 end month: M30

WP1 Leader: Boschioli Maria Laura

Deputy WP1 Leader : Lorraine Michelet

WP1 participants: Jennifer Tambosco, PhD student

Description of the WP1: 20 strains will be selected from the NRL collection. They will be chosen according to conventional genotyping criteria (spoligotype and MLVA) and geographical location to represent the groups SB0120, SB0134, SB0121, Family F4 and Family F9. These strains will be re-cultured and cloned. The DNA extraction will be performed to obtain a quality and concentration for PacBio sequencing in particular. Sequencing will be performed using two complementary technologies: PacBio sequencing to obtain long reads combined with Illumina sequencing. A *de novo* assembly will be performed in order to obtain the complete genome of the French strains.

This is the founder WP as the subsequent ones are based on the data generated by it.

Task-1.1: Culture, cloning and extraction of *M. bovis* strains

Task-1.1 start month: M13

Task-1.1 end month: M18

Task-1.1 Participants: Jennifer Tambosco, PhD student

Description of the task-1.1: Selected strains from the NRL collection will be re-cultured in liquid medium and then cloned on solid medium. After an enrichment of the selected clone in liquid medium, the DNA will be extracted for the sequencing by using the NucleoBond® AXG kit (Macherey-Nagel).

Task-1.2: Sequencing and *de novo* assembly

Task-1.2 start month: M19

Task-1.2 end month: M30

Task-1.2 Participants: PhD student

Description of the task-1.2: The genome of *M. bovis* strains will be sequenced by two complementary technologies, PacBio and Illumina (pe-250x2), in order to take advantage of the long readings obtained for one and the low error rate of the other. The assembly will be performed with the Canu tool from PacBio data, then circularized with Circlator. Assembly errors will be corrected with Pilon by integrating Illumina data into the analysis.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis

WP2 start month: M21

WP2 end month: M36

WP2 Leader: Boschioli Maria Laura

Deputy WP2 Leader : Lorraine Michelet

WP2 participants: PhD student

Description of the WP2: The genomic data (87 genomes) already available at the NRL will be supplemented by sequencing (Illumina) additional strains in order to extend the panel of isolated strains from various hosts, from different foci of different locations but also of "modern" versus "old" strains. An overall analysis will be performed by comparing these data with the new reference sequences generated in WP1 to identify variants (SNPs) as well as other genetic events (deletion, insertions and LSPs). A genome-wide analysis will be also carried out focusing on the selection of 182 virulence genes. Strains showing interesting profiles or particular mutations profiles in those genes will be selected to for further *in vitro* analysis (WP3).

Task-2.1: Sequencing of supplemental strains

Task-2.1 start month: M21
Task-2.1 end month: M24
Task-2.1 Participants: PhD student
Description of the task-2.1: The sequencing of additional strains by Illumina technology (pe-250*2) will be performed in order to extend the panel of isolated strains. These data will be analysed regarding the reference genome generated by WP1. The task 2.2 will highlight genetic markers specific of different French clonal groups.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-E5-1	First steering committee report	M18

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-E5-1	PacBio + Illumina sequencing for reference genome	M22
M-E5-2	Assembly and annotation of reference genome	M30
M-E5-3	Illumina sequencing on supplemental strains	M24

2.1.3.1.22 ET14-ECAMREP

Set of activity		PhD/R1/E-14 The dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR									
PhD full title		Investigate the gaps in the transmission dynamics of AMR <i>E. coli</i> in commercial laying hen production									
PhD acronym		ECAMREP									
PhD host institute (number and acronym)		P17-UCM			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym) (if any)			P12-DTU			
PhD Coordinator person name		Miguel A. Moreno			Project Deputy Leader person name (if any)			Valeria Bortolaia			
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3 or Y4)								2			
PhD Start month				M13			Project End month			M48	
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M											
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M					12						
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI	
P.M											
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
P.M											
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reveal to what extend the table egg production system represents a risk for spread of AMR to humans and the environment. • Effect of reduced antimicrobial use in the production animals on the AMR bacteria initially present in one-day chicks. 											
Description of work											

WP: WP1. Review of the existing data on the collection of bacterial isolates from a laying hen's farm along a four years period.

WP start month: M13

WP end month: M13

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

WP participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the WP: The field study on the farm should be finished before December 2018, so, at January 2019, all the analysis of samples and isolates should be finished. The objective of this WP is the student become familiar with the project.

Task: T1.1. Phenotypic data. Gaps detection.

Task start month: M13

Task end month: M13

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective is the student become familiar with the phenotypic data of the project.

Task: T1.2. Genotypic data. Gaps detection.

Task start month: M13

Task end month: M13

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective is the student become familiar with the genotypic data of the project.

WP: WP2. Training in bioinformatic analysis of whole genomic sequences (WGS).

WP start month: M14

WP end month: M15

WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

WP participants: DTU, UCM

Description of the WP: The objective of this WP is to perform the training of the student of this topic on the lab of the collaborative supervisor (DTU).

Task: T2.1. From raw sequence data to sequence data ready for analyses: quality control and initial processing.

Task start month: M14

Task end month: M15

Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: DTU, UCM

Description of the task: The objective is to perform the training of the student on processing of raw sequence data on the lab of the collaborative supervisor (DTU).

Task: T2.2. Antimicrobial resistance genes (AMR) by ResFinder.

Task start month: M14

Task end month: M15

Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: DTU, UCM

Description of the task: The objective is to perform the training of the student on detection of AMR genes using ResFinder on the lab of the collaborative supervisor (DTU).

Task: T2.3. Plasmid replicons by PlasmidFinder.

Task start month: M14

Task end month: M15

Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: DTU, UCM

Description of the task: The objective is to perform the training of the student on detection of plasmid replicons using PlasmidFinder on the lab of the collaborative supervisor (DTU).

Task: T2.4. Clustering analysis (cgMLST, SNP).

Task start month: M14

Task end month: M15

Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: DTU, UCM

Description of the task: The objective is to perform the training of the student on clustering analysis on the lab of the collaborative supervisor (DTU).

WP: WP3. Review of the bioinformatic analysis of whole genomic sequencing (WGS) data already available.

WP start month: M16

WP end month: M18

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

WP participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the WP: The objective of this WP is to review the preliminary bioinformatic analysis for improving the data.

Task: T3.1. Genes used for cgMLST.

Task start month: M16

Task end month: M18

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective of this WP is to review the preliminary bioinformatic analysis regarding genes used for cgMLST for improving the data.

Task: T3.2. AMR genes.

Task start month: M16

Task end month: M18

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective of this WP is to review the preliminary bioinformatic analysis regarding AMR genes for improving the data.

WP: WP4. New searches on the WGS of AMR isolates.

WP start month: M19

WP end month: M124

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

WP participants: UCM, DTU
Description of the WP: Analysis of genetic platforms putatively associated with the transfer of AMR genes. The objective of this WP is to use bioinformatic analysis to identify on the surrounding of AMR genes platforms that could be involved on their horizontal transfer.

Task: T4.1. Integron sequences.

Task start month: M19

Task end month: M124

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective of this WP is to use bioinformatic analysis to identify integron sequences on the surrounding of AMR genes platforms that could be involved on their horizontal transfer.

Task: T4.2. Transposon (Tn) and Insertion sequences (IS).

Task start month: M19

Task end month: M124

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: The objective of this WP is to use bioinformatic analysis to identify Transposons and Insertion sequences on the surrounding of AMR genes platforms that could be involved on their horizontal transfer.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-E14-1	Updated list of phenotypic features of the <i>E. coli</i> isolates collection	M2
M-E14-2	Training of the PhD-student on bioinformatic analysis of raw sequences	M4

2.1.3.1.23 ET26- Environment and Foodborne Zoonosis: Linking Mechanism and Phenomenology

Set of activity		PhD/R1/E-26									
PhD full title		Environment and Foodborne Zoonosis: Linking Mechanism and Phenomenology									
PhD acronym		N/A									
PhD host institute (number and acronym)		P23-UOS			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym) (if any)			N/A			
PhD Coordinator person name		Giovanni (Gianni) Lo Iacono			Project Deputy Leader person name (if any)			Alasdair (Alex) Cook			
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3 or Y4)							2				
PhD Start month				M13			Project End month				M48
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
P.M											
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
P.M											
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI	
P.M	12										
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
P.M											
Objectives (for all years)											
<p>01. Can we identify and access “big data” – existing information that can be interrogated to yield new evidence for decision-making in One Health? The generation of new analytical approaches would provide tools that could then be adapted to specific animal or human health issues where environment plays a key role in aetiology.</p> <p>02. Can we identify the key environmental processes triggering and propagating zoonoses?</p> <p>03. Can we disentangle the role of animal, human (including socio-economic factors) and environmental factors in zoonoses?</p>											

- O4.** Can we identify the delay between variations in the environment (e.g. increase in the temperature or behavioural change) and the occurrence of a foodborne outbreak?
- O5.** How can we quantify their impact on Animal and Public Health?

Description of work

WP1

WP start month: January 2019 (13M)

WP end month: December 2021 (48M)

WP Leader Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy WP Leader: Alex Cook

WP participants: PhD Student

Description of the WP:

To develop a general tool to assess the risk of infectious diseases (in particular zoonosis) when we have information of relevant environmental factors.

Task:

Task start month: 13M

Task end month: 24M

Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: PhD Student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Description of the task: Review of the literature; Collection of the available data from different sources; Generate specific hypotheses about the underlying mechanisms envisaged in Figure 1 in the case for support; Interaction with colleagues who have estimated the probability of *Salmonella* cases, knowing recent environmental parameters at a certain location shown in Figure 2 and 3 in the case for support.

Sub-Task Review of the literature

Sub-Task start month: 13M

Sub-Task end month: 18M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: PhD Student

Sub-Task Participants: PhD student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Sub-Task Collection of the available data from different sources;

Sub-Task start month: 13M

Sub-Task end month: 24M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Alex Cook

Sub-Task Participants: PhD student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Sub-Task Generate specific hypotheses about the underlying mechanisms envisaged in Figure 1 in the case for support

Sub-Task start month: 13M

Sub-Task end month: 24M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Alex Cook

Sub-Task Participants: PhD student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Sub-Task Interaction with colleagues who have estimated the probability of *Salmonella* cases, knowing recent environmental parameters at a certain location shown in Figure 2 and 3 in the case for support.

Sub-Task start month: 13M

Sub-Task end month: 24M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Alex Cook

Sub-Task Participants: PhD student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-XX-6.1	Mandatory Trainings	6
D-XX-6.2	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars)	12
D-XX-6.3	End of Year Confirmation Report	12
D-XX-6.4 (Optional)	Attending Relevant Training courses (this is optional and it might happen in year 2 depending on the student's needs.)	12

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-XX-6.1	Review of the literature on <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Leptospirosis</i> , environmental epidemiology and modelling approaches;	6
M-XX-6.2	Collection of the available data from different sources, MEDMI, APHA, CEH etc. (Objective 1);	12
M-XX-6.3	Generate specific hypotheses about the underlying mechanisms envisaged in Figure 1 in the case for support (Objective 2-3);	12
M-XX-6.4	Interaction with colleagues at PHE and Gianni Lo Iacono who have estimated the probability of <i>Salmonella</i> cases, knowing recent environmental parameters at a certain location shown in Figure 2 and 3 in the case for support. (Objective 2-3)	12

2.1.3.1.24 ET27-LIN-RES

Set of activity		PhD/R1/E-27 Linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin										
PhD full title		Investigation of the molecular basis, origin, transferability and risk factors associated with linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin.										
PhD acronym		LIN-RES										
PhD host institute (number and acronym)		P04-Sciensano			Deputy Leader institute (number and acronym) (if any)			P04-Sciensano				
PhD Coordinator person name		Dr. Cécile Boland			Project Deputy Leader person name (if any)			Dr. David Fretin				
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3 or Y4)								2				
PhD Start month				M13				Project End month				M48
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
P.M			12									
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22		
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
P.M												
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI		
P.M												
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41			
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA			
P.M												
Objectives												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate the molecular basis, origin, transferability and risk factors associated with linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin. 												
Description of work												
<p>WP: WP1- Sampling and Collection of bacteria WP start month: M13</p>												

WP end month: M28
WP Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland
Deputy WP Leader: Dr. David Fretin
WP participants: Sciensano, BfR and ANSES

Description of the WP:
Mention introductorily: WP1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the PhD (OHEJP Y2 and Y3).
Collection of Gram-positive bacteria (mainly Staphylococci and Enterococci) resistant to Linezolid from animal and human origin and, if feasible, sampling of environmental bacteria from suspected "at risk" biotopes. The coordinator (Sciensano) will contact the other participants and other partners to gather this collection.

Task: T1.1 Sampling and Collection of bacteria
Task start month: M13
Task end month: M28
Task Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland
Deputy Task Leader: Dr. David Fretin
Task Participants: Sciensano, BfR and ANSES
Description of the task: Collection of Gram-positive bacteria (mainly Staphylococci and Enterococci) resistant to Linezolid from animal and human origin and, if feasible, sampling of environmental bacteria from suspected "at risk" biotopes. The coordinator (Sciensano) will contact the other participants and other partners to gather this collection.

WP: WP2- Next Generation Sequencing

WP start month: M13
WP end month: M46
WP Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland
Deputy WP Leader: Dr. David Fretin
WP participants: Sciensano

Description of the WP:
Mention introductorily: WP2 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the PhD (OHEJP Y2,Y3 and Y4).
Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) analysis of all the strains collected during the WP1 and that will be collected during investigation of risk factors at farm level (WP4).

Task: T2.1 NGS resistance analysis
Task start month: M13
Task end month: M30
Task Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland
Deputy Task Leader: Dr. David Fretin
Task Participants: Sciensano
Description of the task: NGS resistance analysis (search of linezolid resistance genetic determinants (cfr, optrA, mutations in the 23SrRNA gene,...) and analysis of the genetic context of the resistance genes.

Task: T2.2 NGS subtyping of the strains and associated host specificity
Task start month: M13
Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland
 Deputy Task Leader: Dr. David Fretin
 Task Participants: Sciensano
 Description of the task: In silico subtyping and analysis of host specificity of the strains starting from NGS raw data.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-E27-2.1	Genetic resistance profiles and subtypes of strains sequenced during M13-M24	M24
D-E27-2.2	Poster presentation at an international conference of the first results obtained from NGS analysis of linezolid-resistant strains.	M24
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-E27-1	Synthesis of genetic resistance profiles and subtypes of strains sequenced during M13-M24	M24
M-E27-2	Poster presentation at an international conference of the first results obtained from NGS analysis of linezolid-resistant strains.	M24

2.1.3.2 Table 2.3.b: Annual set of activities

Activity N°	Activity Title	Lead Beneficiary N°	Short name of lead beneficiary	PersonsXMonths	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Coordination and Management	1	Anses	41.00	13	24
WP2	Integrative Strategic Research Agenda	30	RIVM	6.80	13	24
WP3	Joint Scientific Projects	4	Sciensano	23.50	13	24
WP4	Joint Integrative Platforms	41	SVA	15.57	13	24
WP5	Science to policy translation to stakeholders	9	BfR	26.33	13	24
WP6	Education and Training	23	University of Surrey	15.50	13	24
WP7	Sustainability	27	ISS	16.00	13	24
JRP01	AMR1-IMPART	31	WbvR	77.28	13	24
JRP02	AMR2-ARDIG	21	APHA	123.52	13	24
JRP03	AMR3-RADAR	30	RIVM	129.03	13	24
JRP04	ET1-MADVIR	13	SSI	29.78	13	24
JRP05	ET1-TOXDETECT	1	Anses	111.36	13	24
JRP06	FBZ1-NOVA	41	SVA	209.05	13	24
JRP07	FBZ2-LISTADAPT	1	Anses	136.08	13	24
JRP08	FBZ2-METASTAVA	4	Sciensano	146.30	13	24

JRP09	FBZ3-AIR SAMPLE	12	DTU	45.90	13	24
JRP10	FBZ3-MOMIR PPC	19	INRA	178.00	13	24
JRP11	FBZ4-MEDVETKLEBS	20	IP	128.62	13	24
JIP01	IA1-ORION	9	BfR	207.83	13	24
JIP02	IA2-COHESIVE	30	RIVM	152.31	13	24
T&E5	PhD/R1/E-5 PEMbo	1	ANSES	12.00	13	24
T&E14	PhD/R1/E-14 ECAMREP	17	UCM	12.00	13	24
T&E26	PhD/R1/E-26	23	UoS		13	24
T&E27	PhD/R1/E-27 LIN-RES	4	Sciensano	12.00	13	24

2.1.3.3 Table 2.3.c: Annual deliverables list

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	WP N°	Short name of lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery month
D1.4	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the first year	1	Anses	R	PU	M13
D1.5	Complete version of annual report for stakeholders	1	Anses	R	PU	M13
D1.6	Summary progress report year 2	1	Anses	R	PU	M21
D1.7	Annual work plan for the third year	1	Anses	R	PU	M21
D3.6	Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects (JRP&JIP)	3	Sciensano	R	PU	M13
D3.7	1st periodic report on ongoing JRP	3	Sciensano		CO	M13
D3.8	Abstract book for 1st Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)	3	Sciensano	R	PU	M16
D3.9	Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports	3	Sciensano	R	PU	M18

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	WP N°	Short name of lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery month
D3.10	Second call for projects: Evaluation reports of full proposals	3	Sciensano	R	CO	M19
D4.10	1st periodic report on ongoing JIPs	4	SVA	R	CO	M13
D4.11	Report from 3rd cogwheel workshop	4	SVA	R	PU	M16
D4.12	Instructions for final reporting of JIPs	4	SVA	R	PU	M18
D4.13	Reports on evaluation of JIP proposals, 2nd call	4	SVA	R	CO	M19
D4.14	Report from 4th cogwheel workshop	4	SVA	R	PU	M22
D4.15	Report from thematic meeting II	4	SVA	R	PU	M24
D5.7	Second annual report on dissemination activities to international stakeholders	5	BfR	R	PU	M24
D6.4	Report on one workshop per year associated with ASM (with WP1,3,4 and 5)	6	Surrey	R	PU	M24
D6.5	Report of the four, 4-week One health summer schools with a minimum of 12 delegates.	6	Surrey	R	PU	M24
D6.6	Two week CPD module in one health to 15 participants	6	Surrey	OTHER	PU	M24
D6.7	Reports of the 10 short term missions per year completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	6	Surrey	R	PU	M24

2.2 Participation in Annual Work Plan activities

Beneficiaries concerned : P01-Anses, P02-Ages, P04-Sciensano, P06-NDRVMI, P07-SZU, P08-VRI, P09-BfR, P10-FLI, P11-RKI, P12-DTU, P13-SSI, P14-UTARTU, P15-VFL, P16-INIA, P17-UCM, P18-MVNA, P19-INRA, P20-IP, P21-APHA, P22-PHE, P24-OKI, P25-NUIG, P23-ISS, P27-IZSAM, P28-IZSLER, P32-FHI, P33-NVI, P34-PIWET (NVRI), P35-INIAV, P36-INSa, P37-IISPV, P38-IC, P39-SLV, P40-FoHM, P41-SVA	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.2.1 P23-UoS

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	Y
<p>University of Surrey will use article 15 of the Model Grant Agreement in order to pay stipends to the PhD student which will carry out activity PhD/R1/E26-Environment and Food-Borne Zoonosis.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The maximum amount paid as stipend to the selected PhD fellow is planned to amount a bit lower to €60'000 for the three years duration of the PhD programme and will not exceed this amount. 2. The exact amount of financial support is calculated according to the official rates used by the Surrey University to hire PhD students. 3. The PhD student will perform the required work as expected in the work plan described for activity PhD/R1/E-26 in section 2.3.1.23 on page 171 4. The category of persons to receive the funds are students engaging in a PhD cycle. 5. student selection will be undertaken by the supervisory team according to University of Surrey guidelines and eligibility, and to include the following criteria: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Demonstrated intention to pursue a career in at least one area of zoonotic disease: prevent-detect-respond, improve integration and preparedness b. Demonstrated enthusiasm for a One Health approach c. Demonstrated experience or potential for international integration 	

2.2.2 P26-TEAGASC

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	Y
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WP3, T3.4: 2019 Annual Scientific Meeting organisation:
P26-TEAGASC will organise and host the 2019-ASM. In order to ensure a very well organised meeting it will hire a Professional Conference Organiser (PCO).

Justification

There is a considerable resource effort needed to organise a major professional congress (250 international delegates expected). At the host institute (Teagasc, P26) there are no in-house staff with the resource time available or the necessary experience in this type of event organisation, therefore the host (Teagasc) will hire a Professional Conference Organiser (PCO) to undertake the organising and administration of the congress. Their role will be to set up and manage the website, set up and manage registration, marketing and promotion, attract sponsorship, delegate queries, finances and budget, production of conference materials, running of event at the venue and the social programme. The process to recruit the PCO is fully in line with national procurement rules. The PCO fee structure will be set out in a contract with the host organisation.

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.2.3 P30-RIVM

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y

RIVM and UMCU are active in One Health research together with other leading parties to forge an open innovation network named Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH). In this centre Dutch One Health knowledge is brought together with the goal to create added value by centralizing the specific knowledge of the partners (<http://ncoh.nl/>).

As previously agreed between the REA and RIVM in course of 2018, RIVM envisages the use of the following in-kind contributions, provided by the following third parties under Articles 11 and 12 of the GA:

- Activity JRP03-Radar: University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU) will provide personnel having specific knowledge of AMR

	in-kind contribution used in the UMCU premises	in-kind contribution used in the RIVM premises			Budget amount of total direct costs	Budget amount of indirect costs	Budget amount of total costs	Budget amount of direct costs of in-kind contribution not used in the RIVM premises	Budget amount charged by UMCU to RIVM	Budget amount to be declared by RIVM as receipt in the annual report
RIVM/UMCU JRP03-Radar	yes	no	art 11 against payment	RIVM	99 419.00	24 854.75	124 273.75	N/A	N/A	43 868.75
				UMCU	27 838.00	6 959.50	34 797.50	34 797.50	34 797.50	
			art 12 free of charge	UMCU	35 095.00	8 773.75	43 868.75	43 868.75	N/A	
			Total		162 352.00	40 588.00	202 940.00	78 666.25	34 797.50	43 868.75

- Activity JRP11-MedVetKlebs: University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU) will provide personnel having specific knowledge of Klebsiella

	in-kind contribution used in the UMCU premises	in-kind contribution used in the RIVM premises			Budget amount of total direct costs	Budget amount of indirect costs	Budget amount of total costs	Budget amount of direct costs of in-kind contribution not used in the RIVM premises	Budget amount charged by UMCU to RIVM	Budget amount to be declared by RIVM as receipt in the annual report
RIVM/UMCU JRP11-Med-Vet Klebs	yes	no	art 11 against payment	RIVM	0.00	0.00	0.00	N/A	N/A	24 746.2
				UMCU	15 703.00	3 925.75	19 628.75	19 628.75	19 628.75	
			art 12 free of charge	UMCU	19 797.00	4 949.25	24 746.25	24 746.25	N/A	
			Total		35 500.00	8 875.00	44 375.00	44 375.00	19 628.75	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)									N	

2.2.4 P31-WbvR

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	Y

WbvR, UU, EMC and WU are active in One Health research together with other leading parties to forge an open innovation network named Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH). In this centre Dutch One Health knowledge is brought together with the goal to create added value by centralizing the specific knowledge of the partners (<http://ncoh.nl/>).

As previously agreed between the REA and WbvR in course of 2018, WbvR envisages the use of the following in-kind contributions, provided by the following third parties under Articles 11 and 12 of the GA:

- Activity JRP01-IMPART: Universiteit Utrecht (UU), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, will provide strains resulted from sample material from its diagnostic microbiology laboratory for small animal, research results obtained with these strains and small animal microbiology expert knowledge. These activities are centred around the diagnostic apparatus of the veterinary microbiology diagnostic centre of the faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Utrecht. Therefore the in-kind contributions will be executed at the third party's premises

	in-kind contribution used in the UU premises	in-kind contribution used in the WbvR premises			Budget amount of total direct costs	Budget amount of indirect costs	Budget amount of total costs	Budget amount of direct costs of in-kind contribution not used in the WbvR premises	Budget amount charged by UU to WbvR	Budget amount to be declared by WbvR as receipt in the annual report
WbvR/UU JRP01-IMPART	yes	no	art 11 against payment	WbvR	91 251.00	22 812.75	114 063.75	N/A	N/A	29 132.6
				UU	18 311.92	4 577.98	22 889.90	22 889.90	22 889.90	
			art 12 free of charge	UU	23 306.08	5 826.52	29 132.60	29 132.60	N/A	
			Total		132 869.00	33 217.25	166 086.25	52 022.50	22 889.90	

- Activity JRP08-METASTAVA: Erasmus Medical Centre (EMC) will provide personnel having specific expertise in metagenome analysis

	in-kind contribution used in the EMC premises	in-kind contribution used in the Wbvr premises			Budget amount of total direct costs	Budget amount of indirect costs	Budget amount of total costs	Budget amount of direct costs of in-kind contribution not used in the Wbvr premises	Budget amount charged by EMC to Wbvr	Budget amount to be declared by Wbvr as receipt in the annual report
Wbvr/EMC JRP08-METASTAVA	yes	no	art 11 against payment	Wbvr	168 500.00	42 125.00	210 625.00	N/A	N/A	117 950.00
			EMC	74 140.00	18 535.00	92 675.00	92 675.00	92 675.00		
			EMC	94 360.00	23 590.00	117 950.00	117 950.00	N/A		
	Total				337 000.00	84 250.00	421 250.00	210 625.00	92 675.00	117 950.00

- Activity JRP10-MoMIR-PPC: Wageningen University (WU) will provide personnel that is able to do the WU part of the research

	in-kind contribution used in the WU premises	in-kind contribution used in the Wbvr premises			Budget amount of total direct costs	Budget amount of indirect costs	Budget amount of total costs	Budget amount of direct costs of in-kind contribution not used in the Wbvr premises	Budget amount charged by WU to Wbvr	Budget amount to be declared by Wbvr as receipt in the annual report
Wbvr/WU JRP10-MoMIR	no	yes	art 11 against payment	Wbvr	248 700.00	62 175.00	310 875.00	N/A	N/A	28 728.00
			WU	22 572.00	0.00	22 572.00	22 572.00	22 572.00		
			WU	28 728.00	0.00	28 728.00	28 728.00	N/A		
	Total				300 000.00	62 175.00	362 175.00	51 300.00	22 572.00	28 728.00

2.3 Resources to be committed

2.3.1 Summary effort table

	JIP-R1-01	JIP-R1-02	JRP-R1-01	JRP-R1-02	JRP-R1-03	JRP-R1-04	JRP-R1-05	JRP-R1-06	JRP-R1-07	JRP-R1-08	JRP-R1-09	JRP-R1-10	JRP-R1-11	PhD-E05	PhD-E14	PhD-E26	PhD-E27	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total	
P01.5-ANSP																										
P01-Anses			8.24	3.47	29.15	2.03	27.41	18.52	51.58	18.70		8.28	7.84	12.00				35.00	0.19						222.41	
P02-Ages		1.67							6.50				6.00												14.17	
P04-Sciensano	8.00	2.70					11.00	16.90		63.80							12.00	6.00	0.13	20.40	1.25				142.18	
P06-NDRVMI												25.00													25.00	
P07-SZU																										
P08-VRI						0.40			8.00		5.30	12.00													25.70	
P09-BfR	39.00	31.90	7.00	12.00	33.00		13.00	0.00											0.13			13.33			149.36	
P10-FLI	21.00	1.50						0.00		28.20															50.70	
P11-RKI				13.50				36.00																	49.50	
P12-DTU	21.00	0.25	3.00		10.00			16.00	12.50		15.50		1.00						0.19						79.44	
P13-SSI	23.67		2.50				16.80	19.00					14.25									13.00			89.22	
P14-UT																										
P15-VFL																										
P16-INIA						5.20		19.00																	24.20	
P17-UCM				28.00				19.00				29.00			12.00				2.44						90.44	
P18-MVNA																										
P19-INRA							51.50		27.00			33.60	25.50												137.60	
P20-IP				6.00			6.95						48.25											1.50	62.70	
P21-APHA	7.34	5.95	7.51	37.45	6.69	2.15		3.79																	70.88	
P22-PHE	4.65	1.28	3.13	3.00				2.14																	14.20	
P23-UoS				6.04			1.20					12.80								0.32			14.00		34.36	
P24-OKI							0.40																		0.40	
P25-NUIG													4.78								1.00				5.78	
P26-TEAGASC																					0.50				0.50	
P27-ISS		4.90			7.50			7.00				14.50								0.32				4.50	38.72	
P28-IZS AM		49.00				0.40		2.50	20.00		10.00		18.00												99.90	
P29-IZS LER		9.00				0.40						11.00													20.40	
P30-RIVM	9.33	14.00	2.40		26.49			6.00		15.20			3.00							2.25					78.67	
P31-WbVR	3.84	4.70	17.50	3.06	4.20							18.82									1.60		1.50		55.22	
P32-FHI	10.50	8.36						19.70				13.00								0.19					51.75	
P33-NVI	14.50	3.90	5.75	11.00	12.00		1.50	2.50	10.00		5.50								0.19		1.00				67.84	
P34-PIWET			14.25				0.80				9.60									0.19					24.84	
P35-INIAV																										
P36-INSA																							3.90		3.90	
P37-IISPV																										
P38-IC																										
P39-SLV		3.00							0.50																3.50	
P40-FoHM	10.00	1.60						2.50																	14.10	
P41-SVA	35.00	8.60	6.00					18.50		20.40									0.26		9.42			10.00	108.18	
Total	207.83	152.31	77.28	123.52	129.03	29.78	111.36	209.05	136.08	146.30	45.90	178.00	128.62	12.00	12.00			12.00	41.00	6.80	23.50	15.57	26.33	15.50	16.00	1855.76

2.3.2 Other major cost items (equipment, goods and services, travel & subsistence, meetings organisation)

APC: Article Publication Charges

FOC: Free Of Charge delegate

ASM: Annual Scientific Meeting

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
P01.5-ANSP	0		0		1 200		0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P01-Anses	0		293 275		84 050		5 598	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		17 500	Consumables to perform laboratory work APC	2 000	Project meetings WPL meetings	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		30 800	Lab consumable reagents, sequencing APC	3 000	Regular meetings with partners in Europe Meeting in Paris	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		2 000	APC	10 000	RADAR consortium meeting International Bioinformatics Symposium Specific inter-WP RADAR meeting International ABR symposium	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	4 500	2nd annual meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	0		31 000	Multiwell plates, cell medium, serum, antibodies, dyes, buffers, plastics for cell culture, chemicals (WP2) Plastic consumables for molecular biology (WP2) Reagent for molecular biology (e.g. PCR and RT-PC kits ...) (WP2) Reagents and consumables for implementation of mass spectrometry and ELISA methods (WP3, WP4) APC	4 000	Organization of meetings and travels	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		4 300	Consumables APC	3 300	NOVA meeting	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		65 000	consumables for whole genome sequencing , microbiology (pipets, cryovials, Flasks, storage media) shipment parcels Whole Genome Sequencing APC	13 100	Various meetings	0	
JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA	0		62 000	Molecular biology and NGS externalized sequencing APC	5 000	Metastava meeting	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		38 750	bacterial, serological and molecular analysis 16S microbiome profiling from feces genomic DNA APC	7 500	one meeting one international congress	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		26 000	methods, sampling, strain characterization APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		26 250	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 CT/REA meeting 1 in Brussels (BE) CT/REA meeting 2 in Brussels (BE) CT/REA meeting 3 in Brussels (BE) CT/REA meeting 4 in Brussels (BE) various (SC, ESAB, etc.) ESAB members (EU) invitation to ASM 2019 ESAB members (US) invitation to ASM 2019	5 598	PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18 Financial meeting 2-2019 at Anses (FR) M18
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		3 000	5 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
PhD-E5-PEMbo	0		1 500	training bioinformatics	0		0	
P02-Ages	0		31 000		7 700		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	400	Annual meeting	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		7 000	consumables for whole genome sequencing APC	2 000	Participate to meetings/conferences with EJP partners	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		22 000	methods, sampling, strain characterization APC	2 000	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P04-Sciensano	5 500		72 700		51 450		2 200	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	1 000	Laptop	3 000	Software licences APC	5 000	1 "ORION consortium meeting" 1 "combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop"	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	1 000	Laptop	3 000	Software licence APC	5 000	Annual meeting combined WP meeting & workshop	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	1 500	LC column (peptides) maintenance cost LC-MS/MS	7 000	Reagents, cut-off filters, trypsin SPE cartridges (100x) Peptide standards for S.aureus enterotoxins detection to be used the interlaboratory study APC	2 000	project meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	2 000	Laptop	4 000	Software License APC	10 000	1 "NOVA consortium meeting" 1 "combined NOVA WP meeting & integration workshop"	0	
JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA	0		46 500	sequencing costs, molecular biology reagents, preparation libraries, preparation samples etc. APC	8 000	project meetings, networking with other projects, and exchange visits	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		13 700	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 CT meeting at Anses 1 CT meeting at Anses 2 CT meeting at Anses 3 CT meeting at Anses 4 various (SC, ESAB, etc.) PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	900	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		5 750	Meetings with JRPs 5 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	1 300	annual JRPs/JIP meeting relating to Task 3.2.1 General support along the JRPs
WP4-JIPs management	0		0		1 000	Workshop organisation relating to Task 4.3.3	0	
PhD-E27-LIN-RES	0		9 200	Next generation sequencing Sampling and analysis of environmental samples (not included in the monitoring campaign)	1 000	1 International conference	0	
P06-NDRVMI	0		33 000		23 900		0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		33 000	Consumables for laboratory study; reagents; feed and feed production; animal experiments; publication APC	20 000	Travel to 2 poultry farms where we will do the experiments. Not less 20 visits as a whole of 2 persons will be necessary.	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P07-SZU	0		0		3 300		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P08-VRI	0		83 425		12 800		0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	1 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		14 000	Chemicals, PCR enzymes and reagents, cultivation media, laboratory plastware and glasware, etc. Transport of strains Sequencing analysis APC	4 000	Consortium meeting	0	
JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE	0		6 000	PCR reagents, sample pre-treatment, farm sampling, general lab consumables. APC	1 500	WP2 meeting Final meeting	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		49 000	faecal DNA purification kit, PCR mixes, NextGeneration sequencing chemistry, disposable laboratory plastic APC	2 500	participation at project annual meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P09-BfR	0		39 000		38 367		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		2 000	APC	5 667	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	4 000	Annual meeting and Workshops	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		7 000	WP1,2,3 (culture media, antimicrobial test reagents, other consumables) APC	1 500	project meetings	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		12 000	WP 3 (culture media, antimicrobial test reagents, other consumables) WP3 (Costs for sequencing) APC	2 000	Project meeting (intern.) WP meeting (WP1 for data analysis) WP meeting (WP3 for result discussion)	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		2 000	APC	3 000	Consortium Meeting 3 Consortium Meeting 4 FG33 consortium meeting 3 FG33 consortium meeting 4	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	0		12 000	Reagents for Toxin-development Reagents for Antibody-development "Media, reagents for micro- and molecular biological testings (e.g. kits etc)" Lab consumables (e.g. microtitration plates etc) APC	4 000	project meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	1 000	WP meeting	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		5 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0		0		10 400	Consolidation of results 1 meeting relating to Task 5.2.3 Scientific support to enhance exploitation of results relating to Task 5.3.2 3rd Stakeholders Committee meeting, planned to be held in November 2019 relating to Tasks 5.4 and 5.1 Dissemination/collaboration activity relating to Task 5.4 Dissemination/collaboration activity relating to Task 5.4	0	
P10-FLI	0		44 233		18 300		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		5 333	Costs for data collection, literature costs, costs for publications, consumables APC	5 000	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	4 000	Annual meeting and workshops	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	1 000	Annual assembly	0	
JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA	0		34 900	laboratory consumables for sampling, sample preparation, and sequencing APC	5 000	participation at project meetings or scientific meetings (dissemination)	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P11-RKI	0		5 000		9 400		0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		3 000	APC	2 000	Meeting with project partners	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	4 100	Meeting with NOVA project partners	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P12-DTU	0		55 500		24 724		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		2 000	APC	3 274	1 Orion consortium workshop 1 WP meeting and integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	750	Annual meeting and workshop	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		4 500	Consumables APC	800	Travel to one project meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		6 000	To cover costs related to the structured expert study i.e. costs for expert interviews. APC	4 000	RADAR Consortium meeting Work package meeting RADAR Consortium meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	3 200	project meetings	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		16 000	Illumina DNA purification kits and Miseq (in house) / Hiseq (Oxford subcontracting) sequencing APC	3 000	Various meetings	0	
JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE	0		21 000	General lab consumables, culture microbiology, in-herd sampling, bioinformatics license APC	4 000	WP-2 meeting 1 WP-2 meeting 2 Final project meeting	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		2 000	APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P13-SSI	0		122 842		23 167		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		6 167	Consumables to perform microbiological/laboratory work Consumables to perform epidemiological work APC	2 667	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		4 000	consumables APC	300	Meeting	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		84 675	Microarray analysis (reagents and utensils) Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	4 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	2 500	Consortium meeting	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		26 000	methods, sampling, strain characterization APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		5 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		2 400	4 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0		0		3 400	3rd Stakeholders Committee meeting, planned to be held in November 2019 relating to Tasks 5.4 and 5.1 Dissemination/collaboration activity relating to Task 5.4 Dissemination/collaboration activity relating to Task 5.4	0	
P14-UT	0		0		3 300		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P15-VFL	0		0		3 300		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P16-INIA	0		89 675		9 100		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		84 675	Microarray analysis (reagents and utensils) Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	4 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		5 000	costs of stationery and computer science, program licences, scientific publications, cibercloud... APC	2 000	Project scientific/management meeting, scientific congress...	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		1 400	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P17-UCM	0		80 500		15 300		4 575	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		34 200	Consummables for Molecular Biology, Whole Genome Sequencing (Illumina/PacBio), MALDI-TOF APC	3 000	Conference and Meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		11 200	software licences APC	1 000	congresses and conferences	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		31 100	Reagents, consumables and material for molecular Biology and sequencing; Immunology (MALDI TOF) ; Animal experiments; Publication APC	1 500	Final meeting	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		4 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	4 575	
WP2-SRA	0		0		2 500	Meetings related to Task 2.2.2: strategic interactions	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
PhD-E14-ECAMREP	0		4 000	Laboratory consumables	1 500	Conferences	0	
P18-MVNA	0		0		5 100		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		3 000	5 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P19-INRA	0		149 500		16 700		4 500	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	0		65 000	Culture media, Laboratory glasswares and chemicals for microbiology and proteomic, small equipments (chromatography columns...) (WP3) Molecular biology and small equipment (WP2) Molecular biology and small equipment (WP4) RNA seq for B cereus characterization (WP2) sequencing and antibodies production (WP4) APC	4 000	project meetings	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		29 500	laboratory glassware, Listeria enrichment and selective media. PCR products for molecular identification/confirmationL, Biofilm Ring Test kits for biofilm screenings, small equipment (micropipette) APC	3 000	Meetings	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		35 500	Reagents, consumables and materials for Bacteriology ; molecular Biology ; Cell Biology ; Immunology ; Animal experiment APC	4 000	1 final meeting in Nederland Participation Workshops with consortium partner; visits or conferences	4 500	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		19 500	qPCR development, methods, sampling APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P20-IP	0		117 500		25 500		0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		27 000	Sequencing kits (Illumina) Pac Bio sequencing Microbiology media Molecular biology (enzymes, primers, Q-PCR) Antibiotics and reactif for susceptibility determination Pastics (tups, tubes, plaques) antibodies APC	2 000	Participation to a scientific meeting Visit to another partner of the consortium	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	0		22 000	Reagents for proteomics experiments, consumable for LC-MS (WP3) Reagents for molecular biology; consumables for molecular biology and bacteriology; Culture media; gaz for anaerobic cultures (WP2) RNASeq / Toxin genes expression profiling (Construction of the libraries, sequencing runs, bioinformatical and statistical analysis of the data) (WP2) APC	4 000	project meetings	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		68 500	Methods, sampling and characterization ; Illumina & PacBio sequencing APC	11 500	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		4 000	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP7-Sustainability	0		0		2 200	WP 7 coordination activity meeting relating Tasks 7.1 and 7.4 Meetings with other WP Leaders Attendance at the 2019 Stakeholders meeting relating to Tasks 7.1 and 7.4	0	
P21-APHA	0		112 241		23 722		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		5 548	Budget for procuring specialist IT solutions such as cloud computing, online code repositories and online collaboration sites APC	2 365	Orion consortium meeting Combined Orion EP meeting and integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		4 365	Cloud computing time / Collaboration hosting site costs APC	5 913	Annual Meeting Workshop 1 Workshop 2 Workpackage Meeting	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		5 759	For purchasing culture media, antibiotics, performing MALDI-ToF and WGS on selected isolates APC	3 548	To travel to consortium meetings and conferences	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		7 894	cost for culture media, molecular biology kit, WGS APC	4 730	to travel to meetings and conferences	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		2 000	APC	1 183	RADAR consortium meeting RADAR consortium meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		84 675	Microarray analysis (reagents and utensils) Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	1 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	1 183	Travel to project meetings, including European travel for up to 2 persons, and travel within UK for project leader (based remotely)	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P22-PHE	3 159		20 095		14 620		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP01-IA1-ORION	2 000	Software / data platform/IT cloud or equivalent - cost for inter-institution sharing of Salmonella sequence data and metadata for WP2 pilot project	2 000	APC	1 980	Orion Consortium meeting Combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	840	COHESIVE Workshop COHESIVE Yearly project meeting	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		5 400	Laboratory consumables APC	3 000	Travel to attendance at conference / meetings	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		8 000	Laboratory consumables APC	2 500	Attendance at meetings and presentation of work at conferences	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	1 159	Computing equipment and data storage	2 695	Training and development APC	3 000	Attendance at meetings and presentation of work at conferences	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P23-UoS	0		52 758		29 200		0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		9 333	General laboratory consumables and Consumable costs for in vitro models. APC	3 000	Overseas travel - Project meetings UK travel Conference Overseas travel Conference	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	4 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		14 500	General laboratory consumables and consumables for in vitro assays APC	4 300	Overseas travel - Project meetings UK travel Conference Overseas travel Conference	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		8 500	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		2 400	4 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
WP6-T&E management	0		0		2 700	Attendance at meetings relating to management of WP6, PMT and SSB. Relating to Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.4 and 6.5	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
PhD-E26	0		14 500	<p>Training courses (e.g. “Introduction to Epidemiology and Surveillance” at PHE or “Advanced Course in Epidemiological Analysis” at LSHTM) Registration fees 1st year Other consumables: e.g. books, subscriptions to relevant services (e.g. data service such as https://knoema.com/), printing material (posters for meeting, leaflets for stakeholders and partners as Zoetis) The project will require a dedicated laptop, two computer screens, keyboard, mouse and docking station. It also requires a Virtual Machine (6vCPU/24GB RAM/100GB disk for local storage, OS and applications) for long, intensive simulations. Overall cost £4500 (£1500+£3000).</p>	3 800	<p>Annual International Conference/meeting (budgeted as € 700 for registration, € 700 for economy airfare, travel from and to airports €150, €150 for daily accommodation/subsistence and €40 for catering. Registration fees is included in the unit travel cost) Annual National Conference/meeting (budget as €500 for registration, €175 for economy train fare, €150 for daily accommodation/subsistence and €40 for catering. Registration fees included in the unit travel cost)</p>	0	
P24-OKI	0		14 425		4 800		0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	<p>Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC</p>	1 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P25-NUIG	0		26 000		5 400		0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		26 000	methods, sampling, strain characterization APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		900	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P26-TEAGASC	0		40 937		2 100		59 250	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0		40 937	ASM 2019 – 250 delegates expected: Delegate materials Marketing and Promotion Signage General costs (Insurance, photos, prizes etc.) General costs (Insurance, photos, prizes etc.) Audio Visual Shuttle Invited speakers	0		59 250	ASM 2019 – 250 delegates expected: catering Gala dinner Barbeq Welcome reception
P27-ISS	0		37 588		28 100		0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		3 000	APC	2 500	Annual meeting and workshops	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		5 000	shipment of strains to ISS from hospitals and laboratories consumable for laboratory work APC	5 000	Consortium meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	2 800	Participation to the annual general meeting of the NOVA (3x); meeting with the stakeholders (in Italy) to carry out the activities of WP1 and WP3.	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		24 588	Reagents, consumables and materials for Bacteriology ; molecular Biology ; Cell Biology ; Immunology ; Animal experiment ; Publication ; APC	6 000	Consortium meetings	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		5 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		2 400	4 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
WP7-Sustainability	0		3 000	tool for on line surveys and interviews relating to T 7.1 T 7.2, T 7.3 and T 7.4	4 400	WP 7 coordination activity meeting relating Tasks 7.1 and 7.4 Meetings with other WP Leaders Attendance at the 2019 Stakeholders meeting relating to Tasks 7.1 and 7.4	0	
P28-IZS AM	0		87 925		20 400		0	
JIPO2-IA2-COHESIVE	0		4 000	Cloud services APC	2 500	Annual meeting and workshops	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	1 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	3 000	Travels to meetings	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		27 000	Reagents (lab test including NGS) APC	5 000	Missions	0	
JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE	0		10 000	Materials and reagents for WP2 activities APC	2 600	WP2 meeting Final meeting	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		30 500	methods, sampling, strain characterization APC	2 500	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P29-IZS LER	0		52 225		10 300		0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	1 500	Annual meeting and workshops	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	1 500	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		35 800	Reagents, consumables and materials for Bacteriology ; molecular Biology ; Cell Biology ; Immunology ; Animal experiment ; Publication ; APC	4 000	Consortium meetings	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P30-RIVM	5 000		155 534		62 698		4 575	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		22 000	NGS sequencing APC	2 000	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		43 667	Participation of OHEJP consortium partners not already in the COHESIVE consortium Meeting costs APC	30 000	Annual meeting and workshops Participation of OHEJP consortium partners not already in the COHESIVE consortium	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	5 000	Materials to perform the ringtrials in WP 1 and 2 (growth media, lab utensils, confirmation PCR materials, etc.)	4 700	Lab materials APC	2 000	travel to kick-off meeting and training course	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		2 000	APC	4 998	2 radar consortium meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	8 500	WP meetings	0	
JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA	0		66 667	Sequencing costs APC	4 500	Collaboration meetings	0	
JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs	0		14 500	sampling, strain characterization APC	2 400	regular meetings, site visits/exchanges, participation to final symposium	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		4 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	4 575	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15
WP2-SRA	0		0		2 500	Meetings related to Task 2.1.2: Development of the SRA and Task 2.2.2: strategic interactions	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P31-WbvR	0		65 206		26 114		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		2 000	APC	1 500	ORION consortium meeting Combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 400	literature office needs meeting costs APC	1 000	annual meeting and workshop	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		31 200	Consumables to perform laboratory work laboratory materials e.g. culture media, disposables for susceptibility testing APC	4 000	Project meetings WPL meetings meetings for the entire group and if needed getting hands-on training; international scientific meeting for sharing results	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		25 000	Lab disposables, media and molecular kits APC	1 000	Microbiology meeting, to be determined	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		2 000	APC	0		0	
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		2 606	Consumables for Task 3 APC	2 764	Consortium meetings	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		8 050	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		6 100	annual JRP/JIP meeting travel to JRP meetings relating to Task 3.2.1 4 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
WP6-T&E management	0		0		1 700	participation to summer school 2019 relating to Task 6.3	0	
P32-FHI	0		59 457		24 467		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		18 667	consumables to perform laboratory work APC	6 667	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting and integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	5 000	annual meeting, WP meetings, workshop	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	3 500	Project meetings and WP meetings	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC	0		36 790	Consumables to lab Whole genome Sequencing of 60 Salmonella isolates Microbiome sequencing Serotyping and AST (7 antibiotics) of 60 Salmonella isolates Stool sampling kits for DNA Extraction, 60 x Stool sampling kits for Salmonella culture, 60x Postage - 60 sampling kits- tur/retur Postage - microbiome samples to sequence center on ice tur/retur Prize for participation (lottery) APC	6 000	Consortium meetings	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P33-NVI	0		110 200		36 695		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		12 000	Sequencing at a sequencing facility Contracting of compute/storage at a HPC facility APC	7 000	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting and integration workshop	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		6 000	Contracting of compute resources and storage at a HPC facility APC	5 000	Annual meeting, WP meetings, workshop	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		12 000	Consumables to perform laboratory work APC	1 500	IMPART - WPL meeting IMPART consortium meeting (final)	0	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0		12 000	Consumables to perform laboratory work APC	2 250	2 ARDIG consortium meetings	0	
JRP03-AMR3-RADAR	0		7 500	Contracting of computer resources and storage at a HPC facility APC	4 500	Radar consortium meeting International Conference	0	
JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT	0		5 000	chemicals, growth media, shipment costs of strains APC	2 000	project meetings	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		3 500	APC	3 745	"2 international travels to NOVA meetings. Participation at two international conferences"	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		38 000	Growth media, chemicals, plastic consumables for laboratory experiments Computer analysis of WGS data APC	5 400	Coordination meeting a conference if needed: travel for collection of strains	0	
JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE	0		14 200	Covers the costs of sampling, and the consumables to perform laboratory work. APC	2 000	WP2 meeting Final meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P34-PIWET	0		47 805		9 900		0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		18 000	reagents, consumables, services APC	1 000	final meeting	0	
JRP04-ET1-MADVIR	0		14 425	Sample collection, sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs or Microfluidic PCRs or Nanostring analysis and shipment (on dry ice) APC	3 000	2nd annual meeting	0	
JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE	0		15 380	Culture media and reagents for reference cultivation of Campylobacter. Disposable materials for bacteriological sampling and storage. Reagents for identification and typing of isolated Campylobacter. Consumables such as laboratory plastics, gloves and other accessories. Cost of samples collection and shipments across the partner laboratories. Cost of DNA isolation and sequencing. APC	2 000	WP2 meeting Final meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 Free of Charge delegate for Annual Scientific meeting 2019	0	
P35-INIAV	0		0		3 900		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P36-INSA	0		0		8 300		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		5 000	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 800	3 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP4-JIPs management	0		0		1 500	Meetings for project monitoring relating to Task 4.2.2 annual JRP/JIP meeting in Brussels (BE) relating to Task 3.2.1	0	
P37-IISPV	0		0		3 300		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P38-IC	0		0		3 300		0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P39-SLV	0		4 000		5 800		0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	2 500	Yearly project meeting Workshop	0	
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	0		2 000	APC	0		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P40-FoHM	0		12 667		11 830		0	
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		8 667	Software (e.g. Licenses) contracted analysis APC	3 330	Orion consortium meeting WP meeting and integration workshop	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	0		2 000	APC	3 600	Workshop Workshop Annual meeting	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		2 000	APC	1 600	Travel to project meeting	0	
WP1-Coordination	0		0		2 100	SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		1 200	2 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
P41-SVA	1 500		104 250		63 393		0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
JIP01-IA1-ORION	0		12 000	Adobe connect license Training materials Workshop organization (local, food, etc) APC	8 960	ORION consortium meeting combined ORION WP meeting & integration workshop veterinary Epidemiology and surveillance conference	0	
JIP02-IA2-COHESIVE	1 500		12 000	Rental of workshop facilities, lunches and refreshments for workshop APC	10 000	Annual meeting, WP meetings, workshops	0	
JRP01-AMR1-IMPART	0		18 500	Microdilution plates, antibiotics, cultivation agar/medium, molecular microbiology, reference strains, transportation, APC	2 000	Project meetings, conferences, workshops, 1-3 people	0	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0		9 000	Conference fees Annual assembly APC	5 000	Conference attendance Annual assembly	0	
JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA	0		48 000	Sequencing related costs such as kits for sample preparation, library construction, quality control and sequencing, the use of sequencer, data analysis and computing tools, plastics etc. Additional costs for preparation and organizing metagenomics proficiency testing (PT) among partners to evaluate quality matrix, batch effects, and individual performance. APC	1 333	Project meeting, workshop and dissemination	0	

Organisation	Equipment	Justification	Other goods and services	Justification	Travel and subsistence	Justification	Meeting organisation	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0		0		5 000	PMT meeting 1 PMT meeting 2 PMT meeting 3 PMT meeting 4 SSB meeting 2-2019 at RIVM (NL) M15 SSB meeting 3-2019 at UCM (ES) M22 PMC meeting 1-2019 at Anses (FR) M16-M18	0	
WP3-JRPs management	0		0		2 400	4 ASM 2019 FOC delegates	0	
WP4-JIPs management	0		1 500	License Adobe Connect relating to Task 4.3.1	26 000	Project monitoring relating to Task 4.2.2 Implementation of integrative missions relating to Task 4.3.2 Workshop organisation relating to Task 4.3.3 Annual JRP/JIP meeting in Brussels (BE) relating to Task 3.2.1	0	
WP7-Sustainability	0		3 250	Tuition fee relating to T7.4	2 700	Travel for PhD relating to T7.4	0	
GRAND TOTAL	15 159		2 220 463		774 997		80 698	

3 Planned activities for the third year

3.1 WP1

In the third year the Coordination will ensure that all administrative and contractual procedures are followed up in order to ensure the timely implementation of the project and a smooth running of all activities. The Coordination team will liaise with the REA project officers when necessary and submit all expected deliverables.

3.2 WP2

Activities will also be undertaken to disseminate the SRA among OHEJP partners, stakeholders and other EU projects. Furthermore, relevant scientific developments will be monitored, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations. The results of this subtask will provide the basis for development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7.

3.3 WP3

In 2020 the second call JRP (and JIP) will start; therefore, the project leaders of these projects will be asked to report (first feedback and 9 month report). The ongoing projects from the first call (three year projects) have to report also (9 month and final reports); the final reports have to be evaluated by external experts. As for the Annual Scientific Meeting, in year 3 the second one will take place and a report will be delivered. The organisation of the third ASM that will take place in year 4 will start.

3.4 WP4

In Y3, WP4 will prepare guidelines for external final evaluation of COHESIVE and ORION, and engage reviewers. Startup support including training on DMP implementation will be provided to the 2nd round projects. Activities to facilitate internal integration with JIPs as well as thematically cross-domain will continue, and two more cogwheel workshops will be arranged.

3.5 WP5

During year 3, WP5 will continue the close interaction with the key EU stakeholders. Additional research and integrative needs will be identified and addressed where feasible. The dissemination strategy will be used to disseminate the outcomes of the One Health EJP to the stakeholders efficiently.

3.6 WP6

In Year 3, WP6 will organise the second satellite workshop and run this alongside the ASM in May 2020. WP6 will also organise a call for a further 10 Short Term Missions (STM), the reports of which will be made available on the One Health EJP website. Furthermore, WP6 will also organise the second CPD module in One Health.

3.7 WP7

The following activities will take place in WP7 during Year 3:

- Final mapping of the stakeholders at national, European and international and collection of their needs and expectations with regard to EJP
- Analysis of funding opportunities and sustainable legal basis of EJP related to its potential leverage effect
- Challenging the different scenarios to make the EJP sustainable to the relevant stakeholders

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